

Integration of ethical standards and the principles of gender equality, diversity, inclusion in the project activities

Deliverable N. 1.12

27 June 2025

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Deliverable Name	Integration of ethical standards and the principles of gender equality, diversity, inclusion in the project activities
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¹ R=Document, report; DEM=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; DEC=website, patent fillings, videos, etc.; OTHER=other

² PU=Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), CI=Classified

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1 Background and Project Context

Mainstreaming gender equality and ensuring oversight of ethical compliance are **mandatory obligations** for all RESIST partners, as stipulated by both the **RESIST Grant Agreement (GA)** and broader EU frameworks (**EU Regulation 2021/695, Horizon Europe Programme, EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020–2025**).

Under the Grant Agreement, Description of Action (Part A) - **Task 1.4** aims to ensure that all RESIST activities remain fully aligned with ethical standards and the principles of diversity, gender equality, and inclusion:

“This task will focus on implementing an analytical framework to monitor the ethics and gender dimensions throughout the project, assuring the alignment of RESIST’s scope, aims, and activities with the adopted ethical standards and with the principles of diversity and inclusion. The task will: 1) implement and monitor compliance with adopted ethical standards and procedures, providing support and assistance to teams’ ethical challenges and updating the ethical guidelines in T5.3 as necessary; 2) set the framework and monitor the gender dimension and balance across the project by developing specific indicators and KPIs (data collection every 6 months); 3) co-create with WP/Task leaders a set of guidelines on the organisation of inclusive and gender equal activities, including collaborative demonstrator actions (WP3), stakeholder consultations (e.g. workshops, surveys in WP4), and other events to assure a shared knowledge on inclusive and gender equal practices; 4) review communication/dissemination activities and outputs with an inclusive gender lens to assure that diversity (of genders, ages, ethnicities, social backgrounds), inclusiveness and prevention of gender stereotypes are addressed.”

As part of project’s management structure, the European Science Foundation (ESF) has been appointed as Ethics Manager through the **Consortium Agreement**, with responsibilities aligned under Tasks 1.4 and 5.3. ESF also holds a position on the consortium’s Executive Board (EB), ensuring that ethical oversight and gender equality principles are embedded in the project’s strategic decision-making processes.

In support of these obligations, RESIST project has developed and adopted the **Inclusive Gender Equality & Ethics Framework D1.9** (the Framework). This Framework **integrates ethics and gender equality considerations** at both the institutional and operational levels, ensuring their application throughout the project. It **promotes** ethical research practices, diversity, inclusion, and the mainstreaming of gender equality across all activities.

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The Framework provides a **structured analytical approach for active data gathering, continuous monitoring, and capacity-building** to support RESIST teams in addressing ethical and gender-related challenges. It builds upon the findings of the EC-funded **PRO-RES project**³, adopting and expanding state-of-the-art practices for integrating ethics and gender considerations into research and innovation projects, additionally ensuring robust, evidence-based policy advice.

For clarity, it is worth noting that the Framework's emphasis on ethics, gender and inclusion over broader themes of social equity and justice is based on the fact that ethics and gender are clearly defined, required components of the project's legal requirements, with established processes and obligations. In contrast, social equity and justice are as of yet less clearly defined concepts, and thus more open to interpretation and subsequent contestation, risking avoidable complications to apply them consistently across activities. There was accordingly a conscious decision not to have social justice and equity as the central focus, also due to concerns that this could enable narrow thinking in siloes, and thus complicate the project's goal of maintaining an integrated, balanced approach — a challenge already observed in EU-funded activities addressing various 'just' themes.

In addressing **ethical considerations**, the Framework establishes mechanisms for continuous self-assessment, ethics support, active monitoring, the development of ethical guidance, capacity building, and iterative refinement of practices.

Regarding **gender equality and inclusion considerations**, the Framework specifically addresses both **general actions at the institutional level** and **targeted measures at the project activity level**. This dual approach ensures that gender equality and inclusion principles are systematically embedded in the design, implementation, and management of RESIST's research and innovation activities, as well as in the composition of its project teams.

Both ethics and gender considerations of the Framework are supported by **implementation timelines, practical guidelines, data collection activities, webinars, and cooperation mechanisms** across project partners. **Annexes to this document** provide essential background information, best practices, and operational guidance to help RESIST partners in effectively mainstreaming ethics and gender equality into their work.

As outlined in the RESIST Grant Agreement, by Month 30 of the project (June 2025), the consortium is required to produce **Deliverable D1.12: Integration of Ethical Standards and the Principles of Gender Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion in Project Activities (D1.12)**.

³ PROmoting integrity in the use of RESearch results, Grant agreement ID: 788352; <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/788352>

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This deliverable serves to document and demonstrate how the RESIST project has operationalised its Framework for embedding gender equality, ethics, and inclusion within its activities. It begins by presenting a **summary of the Framework’s objectives and the approach adopted to achieve them**, providing essential context for the activities detailed in the subsequent sections. While the Framework itself provides an analytical structure for integrating these principles at the project level, **the core purpose of this deliverable D1.12 is to showcase, in detail, the specific actions undertaken to implement the Framework within the RESIST project.**

The document then proceeds to **describe the key activities initiated to embed ethical standards and promote gender equality, diversity, and inclusion throughout the project’s research and operational processes.**

In addition, it features a dedicated section titled **“Reflections on Gender Equality and Ethics Integration”**, which **highlights major achievements, identifies challenges encountered, and captures lessons learned during the implementation process.** This reflective and reflexive analysis directly informs the **concluding “Way Forward” chapter, which outlines recommendations and defines the next steps** for consolidating and further enhancing gender equality, ethics, and inclusion within the RESIST project’s ongoing and future activities.

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2 Framework's Objectives & Approach

The Inclusive Gender Equality & Ethics Framework ensures that RESIST's research and innovation activities remain ethically robust, inclusive, and gender-equal. It follows a structured, cyclical methodology combining a) monitoring, b) capacity building, c) peer support, and d) iterative improvement. Its implementation relies on active involvement of all project partners and adapting to their evolving needs through tailored tools and guidance.

The Framework's **overarching objectives** are to:

- ensure **continuous ethical compliance** through:
 - continuous self-assessment
 - ethics support services
 - guidance development

and

- **promote gender equality and inclusivity** at both institutional and activity levels by:
 - collecting gender-disaggregated data for intersectional analysis
 - aiming for gender balance with a target of 50% women in R&I roles
 - using gender-sensitive, inclusive language across all communication and dissemination activities.

The Framework structures its **action lines** according to standard scientific logic:

- **define** the nature, scale, and scope of analysis — identifying where and why action is needed
- **identify** the drivers of change — determining the relevant actors and stakeholders
- **set anticipated outcomes** — establishing indicators, checklists, and monitoring mechanisms
- **examine impacts** and **iteratively reassess actions** — ensuring adaptive, responsive implementation.

The **implementation** of the Framework was planned in **6-month cycles**, with dedicated data collection on ethics and gender equality running alongside other project activities. To **operationalise the objectives**, the following **actions were initially envisaged**:

- **set general indicators for monitoring and data gathering** to track progress and identify areas for improvement
- **support to project teams**, through:

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- the development of dedicated resources
- the establishment of an Ethics HelpDesk, and
- the provision of ongoing advice to address emerging needs and challenges across the project lifecycle
- **capacity building and awareness-raising activities**, including webinars, outreach initiatives, and tailored guidance
- **development of a common Action Plan for Communications with the partner responsible for communication (REVOLVE)** to ensure inclusivity in communication outputs
- **collaborative actions** with sister projects, to promote knowledge exchange and shared good practices.

The above-mentioned activities are described in detail in the subsequent sections of this document.

This implementation structure was designed to **ensure continuous monitoring, capacity building, and adaptive implementation** of the Framework throughout the project.

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3 Embedding Gender Equality and Ethical Practices at the Project Level

From the outset, to ensure that RESIST’s activities consistently align with ethical standards, and uphold the principles of diversity, gender equality, and inclusion, the implementation of the Framework included a series of structured actions, including an initial mapping of the state of the art, early stakeholder engagement, and the development of tailored monitoring tools. **A phased approach to self-assessment, data collection, and capacity-building activities allowed the consortium to continuously reflect, adapt, and improve.**

Drawing on the insights gathered through the implementation of the above-mentioned activities, and in coordination with the management team, **resources such as guidelines and capacity-building initiatives (including webinars) were developed** and disseminated to support project teams in their activities.

Key milestones included **a new round of data collection in July 2024 (M19)** using the updated ethics monitoring tool alongside a dedicated questionnaire addressing the gender dimension. The results were consolidated into a paper and presented at the Consortium Meeting in Extremadura in November 2024 (M23), followed by targeted actions to address the identified challenges and gaps. **A subsequent round of data collection took place in February 2025 (M26)**, incorporating revised ethics and gender surveys reflecting the project’s progress and emerging priorities. Results were again consolidated into a document and presented at the Executive Board meeting in May 2025 (M28).

In parallel, **synergies were established with REVOLVE – the partner responsible for communication – to promote inclusive communication practices. Cooperation also took place with VTT’s designated ethics manager in the sister project R4C⁴**, facilitating ethics-related collaboration and continuous exchange of insights, strengthening the ethical dimension of the project.

Building on the summary above, the following section offers a **comprehensive overview of these activities**, structured around four main categories:

⁴ Regions4Climate; Grant agreement ID: 101093873; <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093873>

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monitoring: systematically tracking adherence to ethical standards and gender equality mainstreaming across the project

support to project teams: providing guidance on ethical challenges and promoting gender equality both within project activities and at institutional levels

capacity building & awareness raising: organizing webinars, training sessions, and dissemination of resources to increase awareness and competence

collaborative actions: fostering partnerships and knowledge exchange on ethics and gender equality with project partners and sister projects

3.1 Monitoring

Under the monitoring stream of activity, mandatory data collection campaigns for Gender Equality and Ethics were conducted, as outlined in the RESIST [Grant Agreement](#) and the [Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework D1.9](#) (the Framework).

This monitoring process involved:

- designing and updating the gender equality questionnaires
- designing and updating the ethics monitoring tools
- assessing the data collected through the data gathering cycle
- drafting annotated aggregated data documents and the related factsheets on gender equality and ethics following data collection campaigns
- planning the subsequent data gathering cycles
- addressing identified gaps notably by planning relevant project activities.

The most suitable approach for monitoring was identified to be the inclusion of indicators directly in survey questions to assess and improve the state of the art at the project level of gender equality mainstreaming and ethics compliance. The topics for the indicators are briefly presented in this deliverable, while more detailed information is contained in Annexes 1 to 4 to this deliverable.

The data gathering campaigns have enabled continuous assessment of ethics compliance and awareness of ethical standards, alongside principles of diversity, inclusion, and gender equality

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within the project. The information gathered through the monitoring tools has helped identify gaps, creating opportunities for timely interventions and improvements to address potential ethical risks and gender mainstreaming challenges.

The activities presented are grouped by blocks or time periods — largely aligned with official milestones and internal reporting cycles — and will address ethics compliance and gender equality in parallel, recognizing the interconnection between these two dimensions.

3.1.1 January – December 2023 (M1 – M12)

In the initial stages of the project (M1–M6), considerable emphasis was placed on laying a solid foundation for the monitoring activities envisioned under Task 1.4. During this period, **methods of engagement with project partners were sought and explored to support the process of addressing ethical challenges and considering the gender equality dimension throughout the project.**

Alongside these efforts, work focused on the **development of the analytical framework** set out in Deliverable D1.9 (the Framework), as well as the **creation of an initial tool to monitor the gender dimension** across the project. This monitoring approach has been founded on bi-annual rounds of data gathering, coupled with continuous discursive engagement with consortium partners.

The **first round of data collection began alongside the project's kick-off**, aimed at preparing the consortium for the data gathering efforts ahead, including baseline gender equality study. This initial phase was planned to include bespoke bilateral meetings on relevant issues with concerned partners in the regions to discuss needs and support the data collection process.

The **second round of data collection** – July – September 2023 (M7–M9), results by October 2023 (M10) - was carried out, building on the use of the monitoring tool - spreadsheet available on the project RESIST SharePoint since August 2023 (M8) - to enable easy information provision from partners. The use of a spreadsheet allowed for possibility to flag problems and request aid and elucidations of the issues.

However, the first results of this exercise did not provide sufficient information to validate if and how the tool was being used by all partners, highlighting the need for further efforts to consolidate monitoring practices and ensure consistent, active engagement across the consortium.

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3.1.2 July – December 2024 (M19 – M 24)

3.1.2.1 Ethics compliance

By December 2024 (M24), a **third round of data gathering**: July – September 2024 (M19–M21), results by September 2024 (M21) - took place.

Second and third rounds of data gathering used monitoring sheets based on the five EC-flagged Ethics Issues outlined in the **Grant Agreement**, following the **Ethics Summary Report (ESR)**, covering:

- Ethics Approval
- ALLEA Code & Handbook
- Human Participants
- Vulnerabilities
- Personal Data
- Artificial Intelligence
- Environment, Health & Safety
- Other Ethics Issues

It was necessary to stress the importance of showing compliance with the requirements of the ESR. The monitoring tools aimed to assess ethics compliance, flag issues, support guideline development and updates, and identify further capacity-building needs. For the third round of data gathering, a 68% response rate (38/56 partners) was recorded.

The results were analysed in **Annotated Aggregated Data** document (Annex 1), outlining methodology, findings, and recommendations. A summarizing **factsheet** was circulated to partners on 18 December 2024 (M24).

The compliance monitoring within the RESIST project revealed both progress and ongoing challenges: while overall commitment to ethical practices remains high, several key areas require particular attention — notably, practices related to involving human participants (especially vulnerable populations), as well as the need for clearer guidance and improved tracking of health and environmental measures.

Excerpts from the **developed factsheet** are presented below, offering a visual overview of key findings and conclusions from the 2024 data collection on ethics compliance:

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1.Key Findings

The compliance monitoring within the RESIST project reveals both **progress and ongoing challenges**. The data indicates that **the number of partners engaging in ethics monitoring has risen significantly** with 38 out of 56 partners (68%) amending or completing the document in 2024, compared to an average of 23 out of 56 (41%) in 2023. This demonstrates a **growing awareness** of the importance of duly signaling ethics compliance across the consortium. While overall commitment to ethical practices is quite high, **several key areas require particular attention**.

Figure 1: Engagement in ethics monitoring

First, five partners reported **delays in obtaining ethics approvals**, which while usual, poses a serious compliance risk, as conducting research without the necessary approvals violates ethical and legal standards. Additionally, the failure to upload these approvals or English summaries thereof further complicates the situation, making it challenging to track compliance and provision of speedy information to the funder.

Second, the data reveals **inconsistent engagement with key ethical documents**. The ALLEA Code and Project Handbook scored well, while a notable number of respondents have indicated that they have not reviewed the Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework.

Further, with regards to the **practices related to involving human participants in research**, the data indicates that **significant gaps** remain in the application of the guidelines and checklists, suggesting a need for better communication and tailored support to ensure that all partners are aware of and can effectively apply the available resources and guarantee consistency in documentation within RESIST partners.

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Concerning **engagement practices with vulnerable populations**, the data reveals that, surprisingly, most partners currently do not directly engage with these groups. However, there is a need to support the few partners who do. Additionally, **an assessment should be conducted to determine whether the others are unaware of the importance of engaging with vulnerable populations or if it is simply not part of their project activities.**

Specifically, tailored assistance should be provided to develop appropriate consent forms and ethical guidelines for working with vulnerable individuals and groups. Ensuring that partners are equipped to handle these vulnerabilities ethically will both enhance the overall integrity of the research and safeguard the rights of the affected populations.

Regarding **the completion of the EC self-assessment for personal data handling**, most of the respondent partners have completed it but some have not consulted the EC Ethics and Data Protection Guidelines. This could lead to gaps in compliance, highlighting the **need for further awareness** and understanding of the importance of these guidelines.

Moreover, it is observed that the **AI ethics engagement is in early stages**, with many partners still in the process of familiarizing themselves with AI ethics guidance. The use of AI within the project is limited, but for those involved, further support on trustworthy AI and tools like ChatGPT is needed.

Lastly, the data collected on the compliance with the environmental, health and safety requirements shows that while most partners are adhering to environmental standards, there is a **need for clearer guidance and better tracking of health and environmental measures.**

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2. Conclusions

In conclusion, the **data-gathering on ethics compliance**, as facilitated by the Framework, has proven to be a **critical tool for identifying significant gaps**. On the face of things, the identified gaps indicate and include delays in obtaining required ethics approvals, inconsistent engagement with project's key documents, and areas where further guidance could enhance practices, such as engagement with vulnerable populations. While this may reflect the incomplete data input, the insights gained already reveal both the commitment of RESIST partners to ethical compliance and the ongoing challenges that must be addressed.

Moving forward, **the results of this analysis will shape the development of specific, actionable steps for the implementation of the Framework and will inform the objectives for subsequent rounds of ethics data collection, ensuring alignment with the adopted standards of ethical research practice**. More precisely, among other things, the ethics monitoring tool will be updated based on past experiences and will incorporate new dimensions, identified as relevant for the next phases of the project, such as the use of AI and the ethics of technology development. Additionally, engagement with partners to enhance their understanding of ethics will occur through direct meetings and/or dedicated thematic webinars, potentially in collaboration with other partners / projects. Finally, the provision of ad hoc support to address emerging areas of concern will continue through the Ethics HelpDesk.

3.1.2.2 Gender equality mainstreaming

To support the collection of sex/gender-disaggregated data at project level and for dissemination events and expert teams, a **gender equality questionnaire** was developed and shared with partners via **MS Forms** on 1 July 2024 (M19). Aligned with the Framework, the questionnaire addressed both its general (institutional level) and specific (project activities) dimensions. Data collected covered:

- presence of GEPs and related institutional policies
- sex/gender-disaggregated data collection within RESIST partner organisations
- use of gender-sensitive communication
- organisation of inclusive dissemination events and research activities

Responses were gathered from 68% of partners (38/56) between July – September 2024 (M19–M21).

Findings from this first data collection cycle were documented in an **Annotated Aggregated Data** document (Annex 3), outlining methodology, key results, and recommendations to address identified gaps. A corresponding **factsheet** summarising the conclusions was shared with partners on 18 December 2024 (M24).

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The gender equality data collection revealed that while most GEPs align with EC requirements and project teams are generally gender-balanced across the consortium, gaps remain in the integration of gender considerations within research practices.

Excerpts from the [developed factsheet](#) are presented below, offering a visual overview of key findings and conclusions from the 2024 data collection on gender equality:

Key findings

1. Institutional Gender Equality Policies

- 74% (n=28) of partners have a Gender Equality Plan (GEP); 87% (n=33) have some form of gender equality-related policies.
- Most GEPs align with EC requirements, but gaps exist in addressing the integration of gender in research practices.

2. Team and Leadership Gender Balance:

- Gender balance achieved within project teams and leadership roles.
- Positive progress towards fostering equitable research environments.

Figure 2: Core team members (January to June 2024)

Figure 3: Team leaders (January to June 2024)

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3. Use of Gender-Sensitive Communication:

- Many partners value checklists and guidelines but report challenges in consistent application.
- Need for ongoing awareness initiatives and training to ensure sustained improvement.

Figure 4: Use of guidelines and resources for gender sensitive communication

Figure 5: Use of RESIST checklist for organising inclusive stakeholder meeting

4. Data Collection at Dissemination Events:

- Limited collection of sex/gender-disaggregated data during events: according to the 14 respondents having organised dissemination events, only 2 partners having collected data in this respect.
- Capacity-building required to improve gender mainstreaming in event organization.

5. Gender Dimension in Research Activities:

Figure 6: use of resources to include gender dimension in research

- 53% of research-active partners integrate gender considerations into their work.
- Efforts include using tools and resources to broaden research perspectives.

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Conclusions and Recommendations

Efficiency of the Framework:

The initial data-gathering campaign (M19–M21, 2024) highlighted trends and challenges in gender mainstreaming across the project.

Identified Needs:

- Greater awareness of EC requirements.
- Enhanced focus on integrating gender dimensions into research.
- Better practices for disaggregated data collection.

3.1.2.3 Follow up process

Concerted efforts were made to engage partners who had not initially responded to the gender and ethics surveys. Recognizing the challenges posed by the summer period, contact was made with the designated persons responsible for gender equality and ethics, and the survey deadline was extended. Additionally, personalized email reminders were sent to those who had not yet completed the survey to encourage participation.

Throughout the entire data-gathering campaign, responses to partner queries were consistently provided, and adjustments were made to accommodate partners' internal situations. This approach ensured the highest possible rate of engagement to a fundamentally voluntary activity.

Following the completion of the data collection cycles for both ethics and gender equality, targeted follow-up actions were undertaken to **support partners in addressing identified knowledge or and/ or capacity gaps**.

Actions included:

- **individual emails** were sent to partners for further clarification and tailored support;
- **update of resources**: based on feedback and identified needs from the data collection and follow-up exchanges, selected project resources were updated (see **section 3.2.1** for further details);
- **presentation at EB meeting** - 13 May 2025 (M29) - to refresh and reinforce awareness by briefly presenting the scope of the Framework and available resources developed under the Framework.

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These follow-up actions aimed to **ensure continuous alignment with the Framework and EU initiatives and support partners in implementing best practices for gender equality and ethics compliance** across all project activities.

The **Ethics HelpDesk** also remained available for ongoing guidance and partner support.

3.1.3 February – June 2025 (M25 – M30)

The design of the questionnaires for the subsequent data gathering round was updated based on the findings from the 2024 surveys, project progress, and lessons learned from previous cycles. The updated monitoring tools also incorporated new dimensions identified as relevant for the next phases of the project.

3.1.3.1 Ethics compliance

A **new ethics compliance questionnaire** was launched (via **MS Forms**) to assess and ensure that RESIST project activities continue to adhere to ethical standards throughout implementation, as outlined in the Grant Agreement and the Framework (D1.9).

Data collection took place between February and April 2025 (M26–M28), covering activities from July 2024 to January 2025. **The response rate increased by 7% from 2024, reaching 75% (42/56 partners).**

The questionnaire addressed the project's dual obligation to:

- **ensure legal compliance** with international, EU, and national law (Section 1)
- align with the **highest ethical standards** (Section 2), covering:
 - ✓ legal compliance
 - ✓ alignment with the highest ethical standards
 - ✓ human participants in research/ project activities
 - ✓ environment, health and safety
 - ✓ artificial intelligence
 - ✓ AI risk categorization: newly introduced complementary survey (shared via **MS Forms**) targeting RESIST project partners using/ planning to use AI technology to implement project activities; it was designed to help RESIST partners assess the risk level of their AI systems based on the classification of the **EU AI Act**;
 - ✓ stimulation of ethical thinking: newly introduced section with scenario-based questions designed to prompt RESIST partners' ethical reflection and gather personal views, helping inform future ethics resources and activities within the project.

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The 2025 first semester data collection on ethics compliance aimed (a) to assess the state of ethics compliance and integration of ethical standards within partner organisations, (b) to identify potential ethical risks and offer opportunities for timely action, (c) to identify potential needs for additional guidelines and/ or capacity building and (d) to foster an ongoing culture of ethical awareness and reflection among partners.

The analysis also highlighted shared good practices in several areas, offering inspiration and practical examples for all RESIST partners to strengthen their own ethics practices.

The analysis of the 2025 – 1st semester data collection results on ethics compliance was documented in the [Annotated Aggregated Data](#) (Annex 2). This document outlines the methodology used, highlights key findings for the EC-flagged ethics issues, object of the monitoring and provides conclusions. Also, it offers recommendations to address identified gaps and challenges. A corresponding [factsheet](#) was also created, summarizing the results and conclusions of the data collection. The factsheet was shared with partners on 13 May 2025 (M29) via EB presentation.

The 2025 data confirmed the overall trends observed in 2024. Importantly, the 2025 results offered deeper insights into recurring challenges, including **limited awareness of international research integrity standards, gaps in ethics training delivery, and persistent difficulties in identifying vulnerable populations and implementing comprehensive safeguarding measures.**

The findings also reinforced the need for clearer transparency and user-awareness mechanisms in AI-related activities to minimise ethical risks and improve responsible communication. Additionally, the integration of climate stress mitigation strategies within project activities continues to require further attention.

Excerpts from the [developed factsheet](#) are presented below, offering a visual overview of key findings and conclusions from the 2025 – 1st semester data collection on ethics compliance:

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Key Findings - at institutional level

1. Legal compliance:

- ✓ Many partners have obtained or are awaiting **ethics approvals** (7 out of 9 who indicated that an approval is needed).
- ✓ A few partners have not yet initiated the approval process, highlighting the need for continuous engagement and action.
- ✓ Significant increase compared to 2024 (5 out of 6 partners requiring ethics approvals had not yet applied)

2. Alignment with the highest ethical standards:

- ✓ Partners show solid **ethics governance** structures, with many partners maintaining formal structures and procedures (code of conducts – 62%, ethics personnel – 40%, professional code of ethics – 26%, mechanisms for managing ethics breaches and misconduct – 83%)
- ✓ Ethics and research integrity **training** among partners is varied, with over half providing RESIST-specific sessions through in-house training, webinars, and documentation, while others rely on occasional, general, or no training at all.
- ✓ **Gaps** exist in:
 - awareness of international research integrity standards and ethics training delivery
 - the provision of tailored ethics training for project-specific activities to ensure all staff are adequately trained and equipped to navigate the ethical challenges unique to the RESIST project.

3. Involvement of human participants in research:

- ✓ Out of 42 partners, **27 (64%) involve human participants in their activities**
 - The vast majority (25) indicated following ethical practices for human participants, such as informed consent and confidentiality.
- ✓ 37% of partners (10 out of 27) involve **vulnerable groups**, mainly addressing geographic, socio-economic, and age-related vulnerabilities.
 - **60% are fully aware of relevant ethical considerations**
 - 30% are partially aware and would benefit from further training
- ✓ **Key safeguarding measures** include anonymity, confidentiality, and informed consent, with common practices for individuals with reduced capacity involving clear information, time for questions, and voluntary participation, though areas like interpreter use and ongoing consent checks remain limited.
- ✓ **Gaps** were identified in recognizing vulnerable populations and implementing comprehensive safeguarding measures. It is recommended to provide ethics training for partners working with vulnerable populations.

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4. Environmental, health, and safety:

- ✓ Out of 42 respondents (35 - 83%) confirmed they have **reviewed the applicable environmental legislation** related to their research and reported no issues
 - Increased compared to 2024: 18/ 24 – 75%
- ✓ **Challenges:**
 - **environmental impact assessment tools use** is limited, with (11/ 42 - 26%) of respondents actively assessing impacts.
 - **climate-related stress protection measures** are also low, with few partners implementing protections for researchers, participants, or other stakeholders.
- ✓ **Key practices** include collaboration to minimise fieldwork risks, regular safety training, and operational sustainability measures like energy-efficient systems, eco-friendly events, and reducing single-use plastics.

5. AI Integration:

- ✓ **AI use is expanding but remains limited**, primarily for data processing, content creation, and planning (only 8/42 partners – 19% - indicated using AI int the project activities).
- ✓ The **AI risk survey** was designed to assess AI systems' risk based on the EU's AI Act criteria, ensuring safety, transparency, and respect for fundamental rights.
 - **AI risk survey shows minimal risks:** no high-risk AI systems were identified in the RESIST project
 - **Limited-risk:** AI in education (1 partner) and user interaction without awareness (1 partner) may require further regulatory review and transparency.
 - **Minimal-risk:** General automation tools (2 partners) and non-personal data processing (5 partners) were used, with no significant decision-making impact (3 partners), suggesting low risk.
- ✓ **Challenge:**
 - strengthening ethical governance and oversight mechanisms for AI use within the project
 - promoting transparency and user awareness, particularly in AI systems used in education and user interactions.
- ✓ 3 partners (7%) in the RESIST project have reported **involvement in technology development with potential ethical concerns**, such as dual-use technologies. To address these, the following measures have been adopted:
 - 2 partners have implemented internal ethical guidelines and best practices.
 - 1 partner provides staff training on ethical technology development.

6. Stimulation of ethical thinking:

- ✓ This section of the survey was designed to **stimulate reflective thinking** among consortium partners about ethically challenging scenarios and to gather personal viewpoints.
- ✓ The data revealed a **strong preference for addressing ethical challenges within the consortium** rather than relying on external legal action.
- ✓ Further clarity and guidance on ethical issues are needed, as indicated by some respondents' uncertainty regarding specific scenarios.

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III. Recommendations for partner organisations:

1 Enhanced ethics training:

- implementation of **systematic onboarding training for all new staff** on research integrity and ethical standards within the RESIST project;
- organization of **annual refresher workshops** to maintain ongoing ethical awareness across all staff;

2 Expansion of environmental impact assessment tools:

- increased **adoption of environmental impact assessment tools** across project activities;
- implementation of **climate stress mitigation strategies** throughout the project to strengthen long-term sustainability and reduce the environmental footprint.

3 Strengthened AI ethics:

- implementation of transparency and user-awareness mechanisms for AI systems to minimize ethical risks and ensure clear communication;
- regularly review AI systems and their data practices to monitor emerging risks and ensure continuous compliance with ethical and legal standards.

3.1.3.2 Gender equality mainstreaming

In line with the Framework, the updated **gender equality questionnaire**, (shared via **MS Forms**), addressed both the general and the specific parts of the Framework as follows:

- **general part:** how gender considerations are embedded in the overall operations of the project, ensuring inclusivity in its implementation
- **specific part:** the integration of gender perspectives within Climate Change Adaptation research and innovation.

The data collected through the questionnaire covered the following **topics**:

- the assessment of the presence of GEPs and related policies at institutional level
- the collection of sex/ gender disaggregated data within RESIST partner organisations
- the inclusion of gender considerations in research activities
- gender implications of AI
- gender implications in the development of nature-based solutions (NBS) at the project level.

As the project progressed and new priorities emerged, it was natural to include questions on AI use and the development of NBS. This ensured alignment with implementation needs and provided deeper insight into partner priorities, helping to guide future activities. **The survey also aimed to collect best practices, offering a valuable resource for the consortium.**

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Data collection took place between February and April 2025 (M26–M28), covering activities from July 2024 (M19) to January 2025 (M25). **The response rate increased by 5% from 2024, reaching 73% (41/56 partners).**

The analysis of the 2025 - 1semester data collection results on gender equality mainstreaming was documented in the [Annotated Aggregated Data](#) (Annex 4). This document outlines the methodology used, highlights key findings related to both general and specific aspects of the Framework, and presents conclusions. Additionally, recommendations are provided to address identified gaps and challenges. A corresponding [factsheet](#) was also created, summarizing the results and conclusions of the data collection. The factsheet was shared with partners on 13 May 2025 (M29) via EB presentation

The 2025 data confirmed the overall trends observed in 2024, with 93% of institutions having gender equality frameworks in place. However, **the integration of gender into research practices remains uneven, often constrained by limited resources and expertise**. While partners continue to make efforts to embed gender considerations into project activities, challenges persist in:

- ensuring gender representativeness among stakeholders
- recruiting underrepresented genders, particularly in early project phases
- addressing local gender biases that affect balanced participation.

Excerpts from the [developed factsheet](#) are presented below, offering a visual overview of key findings and conclusions from the 2025 – 1st semester data collection on gender equality:

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Key Findings - at institutional level

1. Assessment of Gender Equality Plans and Policies Across RESIST Partners

a. As of the first semester of 2025, 93% (n=38/41) of respondent partners are mainstreaming gender equality into their institutional frameworks—either through GEPs, complementary policies, or both.

*The majority of respondents (58%; n=22 out of 38) indicated **good overall integration between GEPs and other gender equality policies**, though some areas for improvement remain.

b. Partners with a GEP: 33/ 41 (80%)

- 17 / 33 respondent partners (52%) with a GEP - have explicitly included gender considerations in research in their GEPs
 - Of these, 13 (76%) partners adopt a **generic approach**, while 4 (26%) partners adopt a combination of generic and tailored to specific fields / topics approaches
- **Key practices** for including gender considerations in research into GEPs include:
 - ✓ communication and language use
 - ✓ monitoring and evaluation
 - ✓ recruitment and governance
 - ✓ awareness and training
 - ✓ institutional structures
 - ✓ research and academic integration
 - ✓ reporting and safety mechanisms
 - ✓ recognition and incentives
 - ✓ gender-focused research
- The **main challenges**:
 - resource constraints
 - limited internal expertise.

Overview of Institutional Gender Equality Policies

- GEP (only)
- Other GE policies (only)
- GEP + other GE policies
- None

Figure 1: The data gathering revealed that the majority of respondent partners have institutional-level policies to mainstream gender equality.

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2. Promotion of Gender Equality in the Workplace

- Most respondents (69%; 28/41) rated their institutions as **effective** in promoting gender equality in the workplace.

3. Impact of EU Projects on Gender Balance

- In terms of the perceived impact of EU project participation on gender balance, a majority of respondents—22 out of 41 (54%)—indicated that **being involved in the EU projects has positively contributed to promoting gender balance within their institutions.**

4. Gender composition of RESIST teams

- **balanced teams** across RESIST partners in terms of gender representation
- Three (3) of the five (5) **work package leaders are women (60%)**, further supporting the positive trend towards the increased participation of women in leadership roles.

Recommendations

Reconfirmed recommendations:

- The **findings from the 2025 data cycle confirm the recommendations from the 2024** annotated aggregated data on gender equality.
- The main challenges remain and emphasise the need for capacity building and tailored guidelines for integrating gender equality into research.

2025 – 1st semester recommendations:

- **embedding gender equality prompts and discussions in internal communications** to ensure gender considerations remain visible and actively addressed across all project activities;

- **providing training sessions on gender mainstreaming in research**, with special attention to intersectional (Gender+) approaches and emerging areas, such as AI and NBS.

3.1.3.3 Follow up process

As the project entered its mid-term phase, the intense workload experienced by partners was taken into account. To respect their time and uphold the principle of voluntary participation, it was decided to extend the deadline and send final reminder emails without applying additional pressure. An increasing trend in questionnaire completion rates was noted, indicating that sufficient data had been gathered. This data provided a comprehensive overview of gender equality and ethics compliance

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within the project, enabling an effective comparison of insights from 2024 with those from the first semester of 2025.

Throughout this period, there were exchanges with partners to provide clarifications, and appropriate modifications were implemented to align with their internal circumstances. This approach ensured that all responses were considered and accurately reflected in the analysis.

Following the completion of the 2025 first-semester data collection cycles for both ethics and gender equality, priority will be given to **maintaining and expanding dedicated initiatives** that support meaningful gender integration and ethics compliance across the project, such as:

- **presentation at EB meeting** - 13 May 2025 (M29) – to present the outcomes of the 2025 – 1st semester data collection
- **capacity building** activities through thematic webinars.

By the end of the project, the identified gaps will be documented through ESF's internal procedures. These gaps will be addressed on a regular basis, according to the project's needs and evolution, within a timeline defined in coordination with the project coordination team. The progress and outcomes of addressing these gaps will be included in the final report, which is due by the end of the project.

In conclusion, the data-gathering on ethics compliance and gender equality mainstreaming, as facilitated by the Framework, has proven to be a critical tool for identifying and addressing gaps.

3.2 Support to the teams

Under the support stream of activity, several initiatives were implemented to help embed ethical standards and principles of diversity, gender equality, and inclusion at the project level, including:

- development of dedicated resources
- establishment of an Ethics HelpDesk

3.2.1 Development of Resources

To provide partners with a shared understanding of inclusive practices, gender equality, and ethics standards, **dedicated guidelines** have been developed and shared with the consortium in February 2024 (M14), offering guidance:

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Document	Short description / Released date	Annex/ Link
RESIST_Repository for gender equality and ethics	This repository centralises relevant completed deliverables from RESIST project, mandatory and key documents, guidelines as well as various tools in one central location. It is a living document, and it essentially functions as a handbook for the project. / 28.03.2024 / updated version 24.01.2025	Annex 5 Link
RESIST_Checklist for Organising Inclusive Stakeholders Meetings	The checklist aims to highlight actions that make the preparation, conduction, finalization, and follow-up of stakeholders' meetings more inclusive, ensuring equitable participation and representation. / 21.02.2024 / updated version 24.01.2025	Annex 6 Link
RESIST_Checklist for Including the Gender Dimension in Research	This checklist aims to assist the researchers of RESIST in achieving excellence by mainstreaming the gender dimension in the different phases of the research cycle, thus promoting more equitable and comprehensive outcomes. / 21.02.2024	Annex 7 Link
RESIST_Gender Sensitive and Inclusive Communication Guidelines	These guidelines provide the RESIST consortium with directions for gender-sensitive and inclusive communication. They cover various communication types and specific topics like addressing gender stereotypes, promoting inclusive language, managing audiovisual representations, and effective communication on climate action. An appendix includes a checklist for agile revision in social media publications. The aim is to empower the RESIST partners in fostering inclusive and impactful communication for sustainable	Annex 8 Link

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	climate outcomes, thus fostering effective engagement and understanding. / 21.02.2024	
RESIST_Inclusive Communications Checklist for Social Media Posts	The checklist aims to ensure that rapid communications on social media reflect inclusivity and sensitivity to gender issues. / 21.02.2024	Annex 9 Link

Following the 2024 data collection campaigns on gender equality and ethics, several identified gaps and challenges were addressed by **updating two key resources and sharing them with partners in January 2025 (M25)**:

- [RESIST_Repository for gender equality and ethics](#)
- [RESIST_Checklist for Organising Inclusive Stakeholders Meetings](#)

Updates included new material on topics such as integrating gender equality into research and NBS, the ethical use of AI, and collecting sex- and gender-disaggregated data for meetings.

While uptake is still progressing, the resources have been well received by those partners who have consulted them, who recognise their relevance and added value.

3.2.2 Ethics HelpDesk

In line with the Grant Agreement and the Framework, the **Ethics HelpDesk was established to support partners with ethical challenges and promote proactive engagement**, aligned with GA commitments. It was launched at the RESIST kickoff meeting. Its nature and scope were further detailed during WP1 and Executive Board meetings to ensure all consortium partners fully understand the HelpDesk’s remit, role, and responsibilities. The Ethics HelpDesk operates under Task 5.3, while its follow-up, monitoring, and integration into the ethics framework are managed under Task 1.4.

Since its inception, the Ethics HelpDesk has provided materials and guidance to project partners. Due to confidentiality constraints, detailed information on the Ethics HelpDesk cannot be disclosed. However, several key points can be highlighted:

- the majority of inquiries received pertained to requests for templates and boilerplate text. These were provided promptly and later evaluated through surveys regarding their usage.

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While such requests are somewhat unavoidable, there is a risk that ethical reflection may be overlooked when users rely solely on standard documents;

- less frequent, yet more substantive, ethical questions included issues such as the necessity of consent when interviewing consortium partners. These inquiries raised important considerations regarding the boundaries and implications of contractual agreements (Consortium Agreement and Grant Agreement).

As anticipated, the usage of the Ethics HelpDesk is gradually decreasing over time. While approximately 200 interventions took place during RP1 (in 12 months), around 75 took place in RP2 (in 18 months). This is a standard progression, indicating both growth in knowledge as complementary initiatives — including dedicated resources and webinars — are contributing positively, and the natural fact that most of the specific ethics issues are solved once and for all. It is worth noting, however, that the focus lies less on the exact number of inquiries and more on the nature and substance of the issues being raised. Furthermore, a simple issue may require several interventions to resolve, whereas agreement on a complex issue may result from a singular intervention. Therefore, simple metrics such as the number of interventions can only give a very superficial basis for analysis of performance and/or state of the ethics in a project.

Two important caveats must be made here. First, Ethics Helpdesk, as originally established, is a reactive support service, hence it tackles the ethics issues partners know they have. Second, to help fill in the gaps regarding the foreseeable but potentially unrecognized ethical issues by the partners is a key rationale to the provision of material, webinars, and monitoring. However, even with response rate of 75%, it is clear that some unrecognized and thus unresolved ethics issues may still persist, and the work remains incomplete until comprehensive ethics compliance is achieved. There is thus a clear need for enhanced and proactive engagement to ensure comprehensive ethical oversight, particularly in RPs 3 and 4. Accordingly, there is underused potential for the Ethics HelpDesk: adopting a more proactive approach in maintaining high-level discursive engagement with project partners should be considered.

3.3 Capacity building & awareness raising

Under the capacity building and awareness-raising stream of activity, several actions were undertaken to promote the adoption of ethical standards and embed diversity, gender equality, and inclusion within project activities, including:

- webinars
- outreach activities
- development of practical guidelines to facilitate effective capacity building.

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3.3.1 Webinars

A webinar series was launched to establish a common understanding of ethics and gender aspects required by the Grant Agreement, while also addressing complex topics like intersectionality, vulnerable populations, and ethical challenges in climate change actions (CCA).

- **Webinar 1:** Gender Equality Mainstreaming in Climate Change R&I Projects/ 22.04.2024 (M16) - 54 participants registered / 29 attended
Covered key concepts of gender equality and intersectionality, the RESIST gender equality framework, and related tools.
It was noted during the webinar that participant vulnerabilities and the ways in which these intersect — across factors such as gender, age, income, ethnicity, ability, and social status — continue to pose a challenge for climate change research and policy development. Effectively capturing and addressing these overlapping vulnerabilities is essential for ensuring inclusive, equitable, and effective climate action, but remains a complex area requiring ongoing attention.
The webinar enhanced partners' understanding and equipped them to integrate gender mainstreaming effectively into their activities.
- **Webinar 2:** Ethics in R&I Projects/ 27.05.2024 (M17) - 31 participants registered / 24 attended
Focused on EU ethics terminology, legal and ethical principles, research integrity, and the RESIST Ethics framework. Participants gained clarity on ethics appraisal procedures, the Ethics Helpdesk, and resources to ensure ongoing ethics compliance.

3.3.2 Outreach Activities

At the Consortium Meeting in Vesterålen in June 2024 (M18), the importance of gender equality and ethics was highlighted through **two roll-up posters** summarizing key messages from the **ethics** and **gender equality** webinars and showcasing relevant resources.

Further presentations of the outcomes from the 2024 and 2025 first semester data collection campaigns, alongside reminders on the RESIST Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework and associated resources were made at the **Consortium Meeting in Extremadura** in November 2024 (M23) and the **Executive Board meeting on 13 May 2025** (M29).

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3.3.3 Development of practical guidelines to facilitate effective capacity building

Throughout the project, a need was identified to **strengthen partners' understanding and implementation of open science and ethical research practices**. Open science is particularly important in research as it promotes, among others, integrity, reproducibility, transparency, accountability and social benefits⁵.

To support this, in November – December 2024 (M23 – M24), a **set of practical guidelines** were developed to help partners embed open science practices throughout the project lifecycle:

- **Zenodo Guidelines** — providing clear guidance on using Zenodo for open access publication and data sharing (included in RESIST DMP updated version)
- **Authorship Guidelines** — outlining the legal framework for authorship, ethical considerations for recognising contributions, and offering practical recommendations and examples tailored to RESIST (to be published by ESF in 2025)
- **IPR Guidelines** — addressing key intellectual property issues relevant to the project, with directly applicable scenarios to support ethical, fair, and open research management (to be published by ESF in 2025).

Together, **these resources aim to foster a culture of ethical, open, and inclusive research** within RESIST and provide a foundation for responsible research practices beyond the project.

3.4 Collaborative actions

As part of joint initiatives and collaborative actions:

- an **Inclusive Communication Action Plan** was established in January 2024 (M13) with REVOLVE – the communication partner - to review communication and dissemination activities through a gender-inclusive lens. The aim was to ensure diversity (across genders, ages, ethnicities, and social backgrounds), inclusivity, and the avoidance of gender stereotypes. The following materials were reviewed:
 - **Heated climate change debate in Norway's Vesterålen**
 - **Normandy Region Turns to Nature-Based Solutions for climate challenges**

⁵ “Two primary reasons why open science is important [to ethics] are: integrity, as it opens publication up to peer review; and it also allows reuse of the data, which retrospectively benefits the society.” (Ethical Evidence and Policymaking, Chapter 5 Interdisciplinary perspectives on ethics and integrity in Europe: acknowledging differences to foster mutual understanding, Eleni Spyrou, Panagiotis Kavouras, Vassilis Markakis, Matias Barberis Rami and Costas A. Charitidis, 2022).

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The review process of communication/dissemination activities and outputs with an inclusive gender lens began in September 2023 (M9) and was discontinued in March 2024 (M15), with REVOLVE continuing to apply the provided guidance document independently, as agreed with the coordination team.

Additionally, in a focused **effort to build synergies with the sister project R4C**, ESF held working sessions with R4C counterparts to exchange and mutually validate the Ethics and Gender frameworks/plans for both projects. This collaboration, initiated in November 2024 (M23), has been productive, with plans for ongoing cooperation, including the mutual sharing of tools, resources, and state-of-the-art practices.

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4 Reflections on gender equality and ethics integration

By June 2025 (M30), while significant progress has been made towards the objectives of the Inclusive Gender Equality & Ethics Framework, further efforts remain necessary to fully embed gender mainstreaming and achieve comprehensive ethics compliance across all project partners.

The adoption of a *sui generis approach*, informed by a thorough review of state-of-the-art literature, has been complemented by active efforts to seek synergies with other projects, with the aim of maximising impact and fostering shared learning.

By the time of writing this document, **monitoring through data collection campaigns on gender equality and ethics** was conducted in 2023, 2024, and the first semester of 2025. These campaigns revealed recurring challenges, areas for improvement, and opportunities for sharing good practices across the consortium.

While the originally planned 6-month monitoring cycles were adjusted, this decision was carefully considered in response to the evolving needs of the consortium and the production timelines of key resources developed to support partners. As explained above, the implementation of the framework has been grounded in continuous, discursive engagement — notably through exchanges in early 2024 between ESF and partners requiring tailored support.

This collaborative process led to a strategic postponement of one data collection round in 2024, to:

- allow the consortium adequate time to review, reflect on, and begin integrating newly provided resources
- focus monitoring and capacity-building efforts on those partners most in need of targeted assistance and
- dedicate time to refine and transition the survey monitoring tools towards methods less reliant on basic spreadsheets, ensuring they are more effective and sustainable in the longer term.

It is worth underscoring that, while completion of the gender equality and ethics questionnaires is voluntary, the current response rate of approx. 75% - though not representing full participation - provides a realistic snapshot of the gender equality mainstreaming and ethical awareness and engagement levels among the partners at this stage of the project. Recognizing the importance of comprehensive ethical compliance and gender equality mainstreaming, ongoing outreach and discursive engagement activities related to these areas will be implemented at the project level to encourage participation from the remaining partners. A snowball effect is anticipated: partners who have already completed the surveys are expected to

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maintain their engagement in future rounds, while those who have not yet responded will be further encouraged to do so through sustained project-wide communication, awareness-raising initiatives, and regular follow-ups.

The monitoring process remains an essential element in fostering an ethical research culture, but it represents just one part of a broader, continuous effort to embed ethics and gender equality dimensions across project activities. Notably, **the results from the first semester of 2025 reaffirmed earlier trends, particularly underscoring ongoing challenges in ethics awareness** — specifically in applying safeguarding measures when involving human participants — as well as in fully integrating gender equality considerations into project research activities. More specifically, there are still notable gaps in the inclusion of vulnerable populations and practices for securing informed consent from individuals with reduced capacity. These findings highlight the value of a flexible, needs-driven approach that balances procedural requirements with the practical realities of achieving meaningful integration of gender equality and ethics.

In terms of **partner support**, objectives were met through the development and ongoing refinement of dedicated resources, tailored to the project's evolving needs and informed by the data gathering results. Although uptake of these resources remains limited, survey feedback shows that partners who have consulted them recognise their value. The Ethics HelpDesk was highly active during the project's first year, providing timely assistance. As mentioned above, its use has gradually decreased over time, which may reflect an improvement in partners' ability to address ethical challenges independently, thanks to support mechanisms such as webinars, guidelines, and ongoing outreach.

Capacity building activities included two consortium-wide webinars covering the basics of gender and ethics considerations, aiming to establish a shared knowledge baseline. These were supplemented by regular outreach activities, such as a roll-up poster displayed at the Vesterålen Consortium Meeting in June 2024 (M18), presentations at the Extremadura Consortium Meeting in November 2024 (M23), and updates at the Executive Board meeting in May 2025 (M29). These efforts kept ethics and gender topics visible, contributing to the development of a more inclusive and ethically aware project culture.

Collaborative initiatives, including joint work on inclusive communication with communication partner REVOLVE and experience exchange on ethical challenges with sister project R4C, further strengthened the project's capacity to embed these values.

While the long-term impact of mainstreaming gender equality and ethics is inherently gradual, some encouraging trends are already visible. Engagement with monitoring tools increased (by 5% for gender and 7% for ethics), suggesting that awareness-raising efforts are taking effect. Webinar participation was consistently good, with around 24 – 29 attendees remaining active until the

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sessions' end. Moreover, while the reduced reliance on the Ethics HelpDesk indicates that the resources and support structures introduced throughout the project have successfully empowered partners to navigate ethical issues more confidently, there remains room for the Ethics HelpDesk to adopt a more proactive role. Strengthening its presence and outreach could further enhance partners' support, engagement, and adherence to ethical compliance.

While there have been many successes, it is important to acknowledge the obstacles encountered along the way, which have provided valuable insights for improving future efforts.

Challenges:

- **limited direct engagement with partners:** not being able to meet partners in one-on-one meetings initially made it difficult to fully understand their specific needs, the nature of their activities, and their level of awareness regarding ethics and gender equality considerations; building these insights took time and continuous effort;
- **convincing partners of the relevance of ethics and gender equality:** one ongoing challenge has been encouraging partners to view ethics and gender dimensions as integral to their work rather than additional administrative tasks; fostering this understanding — and the trust needed to support it — requires sustained, tailored initiatives combined with broad, consortium-wide outreach;
- **internal constraints affecting planned activities:** some of the activities initially planned to support engagement and capacity building could not be implemented due to internal project limitations; this hindered opportunities to build partners' knowledge on the topics, and limited the potential for cross-project learning and synergy-building in the areas of ethics and gender mainstreaming.

While the work is ongoing, preliminary results confirm that the initial approach was sound: building trust, fostering exchange between horizontal and regional partners, and maintaining regular monitoring are essential for the effective application of the Framework. Trust, shared understanding, and engagement cannot be imposed — project partners must be nurtured through consistent dialogue, appropriate tools, monitoring mechanisms, and collaborative methods.

The experience gained throughout the project underscores the necessity of early and continuous partner engagement to understand their unique contexts and needs. Flexibility and adaptability in planning are crucial to overcoming internal constraints and ensuring sustained momentum. Importantly, integrating ethics and gender equality requires framing these topics not as add-ons but as fundamental components of the project's core mission. Building a culture of ethics compliance

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and gender mainstreaming can only be achieved through persistent, trust-building communication and accessible support mechanisms. Future efforts will benefit from these insights by emphasizing proactive dialogue, enhanced resource dissemination, and fostering a shared sense of responsibility across the consortium.

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5 Way Forward

Building on the achievements and insights gained so far, the next phase of the project will focus on consolidating and expanding the integration of gender equality and ethics across all project activities. The journey toward fully embedding a culture of ethics compliance and gender mainstreaming is ongoing and requires sustained commitment, adaptive strategies, and inclusive engagement.

1. Strengthening partner engagement and communication

- Organize more frequent and tailored partner meetings—both virtual and in-person—to enhance understanding of local contexts and specific needs.
- Develop targeted communication strategies to demonstrate the relevance of ethics and gender equality to each partner’s work, helping shift perceptions from additional tasks to core project values.

2. Enhance monitoring activities

- Resume and maintain the planned 6-month monitoring cycles to ensure consistent data collection.
- Introduce simplified and user-friendly monitoring tools to encourage higher participation and reduce the burden on partners.
- Use monitoring results proactively to adapt support mechanisms and address emerging challenges promptly.

3. Expand capacity building initiatives

- Design more interactive training formats such as workshops, case studies, and peer-learning sessions to deepen partners’ understanding and practical skills.
- Increase visibility and accessibility of resources to maximize uptake.
- Continue leveraging the Ethics HelpDesk while promoting self-sufficiency through other support tools.

4. Fostering collaborative synergies

- Facilitate regular exchanges with sister projects and external experts to share best practices and lessons learnt in ethics and gender mainstreaming.
- Foster cross-consortium working groups focused on ethics compliance and gender equality to build stronger internal communities of practice.

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5. Cultivate research culture of ethics, compliance and gender mainstreaming

- Promote a culture of ongoing dialogue, reflection, and mutual accountability among all partners.
 - The introduction of a **reflective/reflexive journal exercise** could be considered as a means to strengthen ethics support across the partnership, address identified challenges, and enhance partner engagement. Each partner could nominate a lead member to contribute personal reflections on the ethical challenges they encountered during the project. These accounts would offer valuable insights into the practical application of ethics processes, highlight areas of effective support, and identify issues or concerns that may have been overlooked. Key areas for reflection might include:
 - Which ethical issues mattered most to them in practice?
 - How accessible and useful was the ethics support provided?
 - Were there gaps or areas not adequately covered?
 - What unexpected issues emerged that were missed by existing mechanisms?
 - What specific or context-sensitive concerns did they encounter?
 - Recognize and celebrate progress and good practices to motivate continued engagement and ownership.

By following these next steps and recommendations, the consortium can build on existing foundations to achieve deeper integration of ethics and gender equality, ultimately enhancing the quality, inclusiveness, and impact of the project.

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6 Annexes

The annexes presented in this report compile annotated and aggregated data collected during the data collection campaigns conducted throughout 2024 and the first semester of 2025 at the project level (Annexes 1 to 4). They provide detailed insights supporting the main findings and recommendations presented earlier in the deliverable.

Additionally, the annexes include resources and tools developed since the project's beginning, reflecting the evolving needs of the partners and the dynamic progression of the project (Annexes 5 to 9). These materials serve as practical tools designed to advance the integration of gender equality and ethics within project activities.

List of Annexes:

Annex 1: Ethics Compliance in the RESIST Project - Annotated Aggregated Data - 2024

Annex 2: Ethics Compliance in the RESIST Project - Annotated Aggregated Data – 2025, 1st semester

Annex 3: Gender Equality Mainstreaming in the RESIST Project – Annotated Aggregated Data - 2024

Annex 4: Gender Equality Mainstreaming in the RESIST Project - Annotated Aggregated Data – 2025, 1st semester

Annex 5: Repository for gender equality and ethics in climate change research and innovation projects, updated version 2025

Annex 6: Checklist for Organising Inclusive Stakeholders Meetings, updated version 2025

Annex 7: Checklist for Including the Gender Dimension in Research, 2024

Annex 8: Guidelines for inclusive communication, 2024

Annex 9: Diversity & Inclusivity Checklist for Social Media Posts, 2024

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6.1 Annex 1: Ethics Compliance in the RESIST Project - Annotated Aggregated Data - 2024

Ethics Compliance in the RESIST Project

Annotated Aggregated Data

15 November 2024

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Introduction

The [EU Regulation 2021/695](#) and the [RESIST Grant Agreement](#) require compliance with EU, international, and national laws, promoting research integrity.

The RESIST [Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework D1.9](#) (the Framework) provides for an analytical framework to monitor the gender and ethics dimensions throughout the RESIST project. The Ethics Framework provides for reiterative self-assessment, ongoing ethics support, monitoring, development of guidance and building capacity on the topic, among others. According to the Framework, ethics compliance monitoring is conducted through active data-gathering rounds to identify outcomes related to ethics.

This document presents the results of the data collection on ethics compliance conducted in 2023 and 2024 within RESIST project partners. It outlines the methodology used, highlights key findings for the EC-flagged ethics issues, object of the monitoring and presents conclusions. Additionally, recommendations are provided to address identified gaps and challenges.

It should be noted that this analysis is part of a broader data gathering activity, as outlined in the RESIST Framework, and should therefore be considered alongside its counterpart, the RESIST Gender Equality Annotated Aggregated Data. While addressing common issues, different perspectives are observed, aiming to assess the state of the art in their respective areas and to identify the best ways of supporting the RESIST partner organizations in advancing compliance with gender+ equality and ethics standards.

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1. Methodology

To date, two rounds of data gathering have taken place in the RESIST project:

- the first round was launched at the end of July 2023 (M7), with a cut-off date on the 4th of September 2023 (M9), and results coming in by the end of October 2023 (M10);
- planned round of data-gathering in January-April 2024 did not take place due to the demands of the RESIST RP1 reporting. This bottleneck was duly recognised, and corrective measures to the timing and implementation of future cycles (2025 in particular) will take into account the demands of the reporting to CINEA. Hence, activities planned to start in early 2025 were continued as the second round of data gathering, initiated in July 2024 (M19), with a cut-off date on the 20th of September 2024 (M21).

Both rounds of data gathering were supported by the following monitoring tools, and the structure of these tools, along with the partners' answers, can be accessed at the links below:

[RESIST_Ethics monitoring tool_July 2024.xlsx](#)

[RESIST ethics and gender monitoring tool.xlsx](#)

As stated in the [Grant Agreement](#), following the [Ethics Summary Report](#), the project activities raise ethics issues in the following fields: Humans, Personal Data, Non-EU countries, Environment, health and safety, Artificial intelligence.

It should also be noted that the term “ethics issues” is a reference to the common topics as outlined in the EC self-assessment guide. It is not to be construed as a) the only topics that need to be handled or b) topics necessarily involving ethics problems, challenges, or moral dilemmas. It is reiterated that RESIST was considered “ethics ready” since there were no complex or serious ethics issues involved in project at proposal time. As the term “ethics issues” is widely adopted across diverse fields, it is also explicitly used by the EC to evaluate research proposals, as it conveys concerns about adherence to fundamental ethical principles, such as respect for human dignity, fairness, transparency, and accountability in research.

The monitoring tools were developed based on the five EC-flagged Ethics Issues listed for RESIST and mentioned above, and contain the following sheets:

- Ethics approval
- ALLEA Code & Handbook
- Human participants

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- Vulnerabilities
- Personal Data
- Artificial Intelligence
- Environment, Health and Safety
- Other ethics issues

The purpose and description of each sheet are outlined in their respective sections within the “Key Findings” chapter.

The overall objectives of the monitoring tools are to assess the current state of ethics compliance of RESIST partners, allow partners to flag ethical issues in their project activities, provide support for tailoring and updating all operational guidelines within the project, and identify potential needs for additional guidelines and/ or capacity building.

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2. Key Findings

This section presents a detailed overview of the ethics compliance status and practices of RESIST project partners. Key findings are presented thematically, based on the monitoring tools sheets.

A comparison of results between July 2024 and the initial data gathering cycle of 2023 indicates an increase in participation, with 38 partners (68%) amending or completing the document in 2024, compared to an average of 23 (41%) in 2023. Relevant progress is noted where applicable in the sections below.

2.1 Ethics approvals

Purpose: the “Ethics approval” sheet serves to indicate whether partners have obtained or are required to obtain national, local, or institutional ethics approval for their RESIST (research) activities.

Results: out of 38 partners, 32 reported that ethics approval was not required for their research; 4 partners indicated that they needed institutional approvals; 2 partners indicated that they needed local approvals.

- Status of the ethics approval for those who need ethics approvals:

Out of the 6 partners who declared that an ethics approval (national/ local/ institutional) is mandatory for their research activity, only 1 acquired the institutional approval; 5 partners have not provided information whether they have applied yet to obtain the required ethics approval (national/ local/ institutional).

- Ethics approval acquired & uploaded on the RESIST SP: the 1 partner who acquired the ethics approval has not yet uploaded the document on the RESIST SP, as they are uncertain whether a formal document exists. Note that partners are required to be able to produce necessary documentation in English if requested but uploading it to SP is not a requirement but only a recommendation.

Assessment: the majority of respondent partners (5 out of 6) who indicated that they require ethics approvals (national/ local/ institutional) have not yet applied. Additionally, while one partner has successfully obtained the necessary ethics approval, they have not uploaded the required documentation to RESIST SP. The lack of ethics approvals from the 5 partners raises significant

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compliance concerns. The lack of ethics approvals once research activities have started can lead to potential non-compliance with national/ local/ institutional regulations thus jeopardizing the integrity and credibility of the project research outputs. Urgent action is needed to ensure all approvals are obtained and properly documented to avoid these risks.

2.2 ALLEA Code & Handbooks

Purpose: the “ALLEA Code & Handbooks” sheet is intended to verify that all aspects of **ALLEA Code** are clear and that the key linked project documents (**Project Handbook**, **Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework**) and tools (Ethics HelpDesk), are appropriate and fit for purpose.

For the second round of data gathering, a question regarding the Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework was added to bring forward this document to the partners.

Results:

- ALLEA Code: out of 41 answers, 36 partners indicated they have read and understood the ALLEA Code (2023 – only 23 partners answered). Only 5 partners indicated that they have not yet read the document (2023 – 4 partners, 2024 – 1 partner).
- Project Handbook: Out of 38 answers, 37 partners indicated they have read and understood the Project Handbook (2023 – 24 partners answered). Only 1 partner indicated that they have not read the document yet.
- Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework: Out of 25 answers, 22 partners indicated they have read and understood the Framework. Only 3 partners indicated that they have not read the document yet.
- Ethics HelpDesk: Out of 29 answers, 26 partners indicated they have not yet contacted the HelpDesk (2023 – 17 partners answered). Only 3 partners indicated they contacted the Ethics HelpDesk, whereas the internal metrics indicate that 20 partners sought support. All issues raised by those who contacted the HelpDesk were successfully addressed.

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Assessment: while the majority of partners are familiar with the ALLEA Code and Project Handbook, there are gaps in awareness of key resources like the Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework. Greater efforts are needed to ensure all partners engage with this essential tool. However, the initial predictions regarding a decrease in the use of the Ethics HelpDesk as the project progresses have been confirmed.

2.3 Human Participants

Purpose: the “Human Participants” sheet is designed to collect data on whether partners’ research involves human subjects (e.g., surveys, interviews); additionally, they could also have marked the last two columns if involved in stakeholder mapping or engagement.

For the second round of data gathering, a question regarding the use of the [Checklist for organising inclusive stakeholders meetings](#) was added to bring forward this document to the partners.

Results:

- Common standards of outreach: out of 34 answers, 14 partners indicated they have read and applied them; 19 partners indicated they read them but not relevant to their work; 1 partner indicated they read them but need help applying (the issue was addressed directly with the partner).
- Checklist: out of 34 answers, 17 partners indicated they have read and applied it; 15 partners indicated they read it but not relevant to their work; 1 partner indicated they read it but need help applying (the issue was addressed directly with the partner); 1 partner indicated they read it and have suggestions.
- Project templates: out of 21 answers, 17 partners indicated they use the templates as they are; 2 partners indicated they adapted to their own use; 2 partners indicated they use their own templates.
 - The 2 partners who indicated they adapted the templates to their own use, have not yet submitted a copy in the RESIST SP.
 - The 2 partners who indicated they use their own versions of templates, have not yet submitted a copy in the RESIST SP.

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- Inclusion criteria for stakeholders: out of 18 answers, 11 partners indicated they can provide the inclusion criteria for the stakeholders (2023 -7 partners answered); 5 partners indicated they can start document this from now on; 2 partners indicated they were not aware this is needed.
 - Stakeholder events / represented groups: out of 20 answers, 14 partners indicated they can provide this information; 6 partners indicated they can document this from now on.
 - Checklist for organizing inclusive stakeholders meeting: out of 20 answers, 8 partners indicated they read the document; 9 partners indicated they have not read the document yet; 3 partners indicated they were not aware of the checklist.

Assessment: the data gathered reveals a mixed level of engagement among partners regarding outreach standards and related documentation. While some partners have read and applied the common standards of outreach and checklist, others find these documents not relevant to their work or have expressed a need for assistance in applying them. Therefore, support is needed to help partners align with outreach standards.

The project templates are being utilized by the majority, but two partners have adapted them, while two others are using their own templates without submitting their (modified) versions to the RESIST SP. This raises concerns about consistency in documentation.

Concerning stakeholder inclusion criteria, the responses indicate that many partners are ready to provide the necessary information. However, some are either unaware of this requirement or plan to document it for future events, while others are not presently involved in activities that necessitate this documentation.

The checklist for organizing inclusive stakeholder meetings has not been extensively consulted, with several partners unaware of its existence. The reasons for not utilizing the checklists highlight a lack of current outreach activities or a lack of alignment between the available resources and partners' operational needs.

2.4 Vulnerabilities

Purpose: the "Vulnerabilities" sheet is intended to indicate if partners' research involving human subjects also includes mapping or contact with vulnerable individuals or groups.

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Result: regarding the question “Common standards of outreach, setting 1: dealing with vulnerable groups and individuals”, out of 35 answers, 29 partners indicated they read it but not relevant for their work, 5 partners indicated they have read and applied it; 1 partner indicated they read it but needs help with their application.

The partners addressing vulnerabilities were required to specify what type of vulnerability they are dealing with, by selecting from the options provided. The answers are ordered by majority:

- fully informed consent not possible (children, diminished mental faculties);
- socio-economic vulnerabilities;
- “several of the above” only 1 partner provided details (work with disabilities, elderly and children);
- vulnerability based on category of population (women, migrants etc.).

Assessment: the results from the Vulnerabilities sheet reveal that the majority of partners do not find the common standards for outreach regarding vulnerable groups relevant to their work. However, five partners have both read and applied these standards, while one partner has expressed a need for help with their application. This suggests that while a significant portion of partners are not directly engaged with vulnerable populations, a smaller group is actively involved and requires additional support.

Among the partners dealing with vulnerabilities, the most common issue identified is situations where fully informed consent is not possible, such as when working with children or individuals with diminished mental faculties. Socio-economic vulnerabilities also rank high, followed by a few partners addressing multiple vulnerability factors, including disabilities, the elderly, and children. Only a small number of partners are addressing vulnerabilities based on population categories, such as women or migrants.

The data reveals a specific need for development of case-appropriate information and consent forms to ensure ethical compliance and protection of vulnerable groups during research activities in the upcoming period.

2.5 Personal Data

Purpose: the “Personal Data” sheet focuses on the results of the partners’ self-assessment and any specific needs for guidance.

Result: out of 36 answers, 35 partners did the **EC self-assessment** and informed everything was clear to them; only 1 partner indicated they haven’t done it yet.

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- Consultation of **EC Ethics and data protection guidelines**: out of 32 answers, 25 partners have read it and have nothing to flag; 7 partners indicated they have not read the document yet.

The partners who collect personal data for RESIST purposes, were required informing how do individuals know what they are collecting data, what for, and for how long by selecting from options provided. The answers are ordered by majority:

- the info is provided via a consent form;
- we are collecting publicly available info;
- both of the above.

Assessment: almost all the respondent partners (35 out of 36) have completed the EC self-assessment and found it clear. This indicates strong overall compliance and understanding of personal data protocols among most partners.

For those involved in collecting personal data for RESIST, most partners are following appropriate procedures by informing individuals through consent forms or using publicly available information. A few partners are employing both methods.

The comments provided offer additional context, with some partners clarifying that their activities do not involve significant data collection, processing, or control beyond minimal project needs. Others have noted that they have yet to start data collection and will complete their self-assessments at that stage.

2.6 Artificial intelligence

Purpose: the “Artificial intelligence” sheet is intended for the partners who develop AI tools, or if there is a serious risk of ethics concerns raising from their use of AI in their project activities. This sheet is intended to gain thorough elaboration from those partners most concerned with AI Ethics issues in RESIST.

Results: out of 37 answers (2023 – 21 partners answered), 19 partners indicated they consulted the **EC guidance on AI** and they have nothing to flag; 17 partners indicated they will read it soon; 1 partner indicated they read the document but need guidance on use of ChatGPT. There was no follow-up from this partner, but the matter will be addressed in the next guidelines.

- Compliance of the AI system/ technique used, as described in the **EC Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI**, from technical and social perspectives: out of 20 answers (2023 – 7 partners answered), 13 partners indicated their AI system is compliant; 7 partners indicated they will check soon the document.

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- Signed in and tested the **Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI)**: out of 17 answers (2023 – 6 partners answered), 14 partners indicated they will test the tool soon; 3 partners (2023 – none) indicated they have already tested the tool and they have nothing to flag.

Assessment: a large portion of partners are in the early stages of engaging with AI ethics tools. There is a need for further guidance on AI-related ethics, particularly regarding specific tools like ChatGPT.

Regarding the compliance of AI systems with the EC Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI, the responses indicate that a significant number of the respondent partners (13 out of 20) are confident that their AI systems meet the technical and social criteria for compliance. However, several partners have yet to verify this by reviewing the relevant guidelines.

In terms of testing the Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI), the majority of the respondent partners (14 out of 17) plan to explore the tool, while only 3 partners have already tested it and found no concerns. This suggests that most partners are in the early phases of using the assessment tool, with a few having already made progress.

The comments further reveal that a significant number of partners do not engage with AI in their research, which explains why many results indicate forthcoming actions rather than completed assessments.

2.7 Environment, health and safety

Purpose: the “Environment, health and safety” sheet addresses both the health and safety of stakeholders and researchers, as well as environmental concerns.

For the second round of data gathering a question regarding the **Guidelines for inclusive communication**, section 5 "Communicating on Climate Action" was added to bring forward to partners this tool.

Results: 31 partners (2023 – 14 partners answered) indicated they are following the minimum standard checklist provided in **D1.9 The Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework**.

- Taking measures against causing stress and anxiety to stakeholders in the context of dealing with climate change: out of 25 answers, 14 partners indicated they are planning to but need good practices; 8 partners indicated they are planning on taking measures; 3 partners indicated they are taking measures but have not documented them.

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- In February 2024 (M14), ESF shared with the project partners the [Guidelines for inclusive communication](#) (contains a dedicated section on "Communicating on Climate Action"); out of 21 answers, 13 partners indicated they consulted the guidelines; 8 partners indicated they are planning on checking the document.
- Checking what environmental legislation applies to their research: out of 24 answers, 18 partners indicated they checked the applicable legislation and that everything is clear; 6 partners indicated they do not know yet the scope of their research.

Assessment: the data collected reflects partners' awareness and actions concerning the safety of stakeholders, researchers, and environmental issues. A positive finding is that 31 partners are adhering to the minimum standards outlined in the D1.9 Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework, which indicates a widespread commitment to these principles.

When addressing climate-related stress and anxiety, the results indicate a mixed response, with many partners expressing an intention to take action but needing guidance on best practices. This underscores the necessity for practical examples of effective practices as well as guidance.

Regarding the Guidelines for inclusive communication, particularly the section on "Communicating on Climate Action," the majority of respondent partners have reviewed the guidelines. However, ensuring all partners are familiar with these guidelines is essential for effective and sensitive communication in climate change area.

In terms of environmental legislation, most respondent partners (18 out of 24) have checked the relevant regulations and feel confident in their understanding, but 6 partners are still unclear about the scope of legislation applicable to their research. This indicates a need for further clarification and support, especially for those partners still defining the boundaries of their research.

2.8 Other ethics issues

Purpose: the "Other ethics issue" sheet is intended for partners to flag any other ethics issues and/or to ask questions.

Results:

- 2 partners indicated they have an Ethics and Conduct Code in place, as well as a Gender Equality Plan and a Conduct Code for the Prevention and Fight Against Harassment at the Work Place;

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- 1 partner indicated monitoring equality and gender balance stated by company values and Code of Conduct. Implemented non-discrimination act through ESG report obligations.

Assessment: while the responses indicate that a few partners have comprehensive ethics policies and systems in place, the low number of responses suggests that not all partners have flagged or shared details on other ethical issues. It may be beneficial to encourage more partners to assess and report on their ethics issues/ policies adoption to improve ethics compliance and alignment across the project. This has evident synergy gains and capacity-building potential through mutual learning.

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3. Conclusions

The compliance monitoring within the RESIST project reveals both progress and ongoing challenges. The data indicates that the number of partners engaging in ethics monitoring has risen significantly in 2024 compared to 2023, showing a 27% increase (15 additional partners, n=56). This demonstrates a growing awareness of the importance of ethics compliance across the consortium. While overall commitment to ethical practices is quite high, several key areas require particular attention.

First, five partners reported delays in obtaining ethics approvals, which, while usual poses a serious compliance risk, as conducting research without the necessary approvals violates ethical and legal standards. Additionally, the failure to upload these approvals or English summaries thereof further complicates the situation, making it challenging to track compliance and provision of speedy information to the funder.

Second, the data reveals inconsistent engagement with key ethical documents. The ALLEA Code and Project Handbook scored well, while a notable number of respondents have indicated that they have not reviewed the Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework.

Further, with regards to the practices related to involving human participants in research, the data indicates that significant gaps remain in the application of the guidelines and checklists, suggesting a need for better communication and tailored support to ensure that all partners are aware of and can effectively apply the available resources and guarantee consistency in documentation within RESIST partners.

Concerning engagement practices with vulnerable populations, the data reveals that, surprisingly, most partners currently do not directly engage with these groups. However, there is a need to support the few partners who do. Additionally, an assessment should be conducted to determine whether the others are unaware of the importance of engaging with vulnerable populations or if it is simply not part of their project activities. Specifically, tailored assistance should be provided to develop appropriate consent forms and ethical guidelines for working with vulnerable individuals and groups. Ensuring that partners are equipped to handle these vulnerabilities ethically will both enhance the overall integrity of the research and safeguard the rights of the affected populations.

Regarding the completion of the EC self-assessment for personal data handling, most of the respondent partners have completed it but some have not consulted the EC Ethics and Data Protection Guidelines. This could lead to gaps in compliance, highlighting the need for further awareness and understanding of the importance of these guidelines.

Moreover, it is observed that the AI ethics engagement is in early stages, with many partners still in the process of familiarizing themselves with AI ethics guidance. The use of AI within the project is limited, but for those involved, further support on trustworthy AI and tools like ChatGPT is needed.

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Lastly, the data collected on the compliance with the environmental, health and safety requirements shows that while most partners are adhering to environmental standards, there is a need for clearer guidance and better tracking of health and environmental measures.

In conclusion, the data-gathering on ethics compliance, as facilitated by the Framework, has proven to be a critical tool for identifying significant gaps. On the face of things, the identified gaps indicate and include delays in obtaining required ethics approvals, inconsistent engagement with project's key documents, and areas where further guidance could enhance practices, such as engagement with vulnerable populations. While this may reflect the incomplete data input, the insights gained already reveal both the commitment of RESIST partners to ethical compliance and the ongoing challenges that must be addressed.

Moving forward, the results of this analysis will shape the development of specific, actionable steps for the implementation of the Framework and will inform the objectives for subsequent rounds of ethics data collection, ensuring alignment with the adopted standards of ethical research practice. More precisely, among other things, the ethics monitoring tool will be updated based on past experiences and will incorporate new dimensions, identified as relevant for the next phases of the project, such as the use of AI and the ethics of technology development. Additionally, engagement with partners to enhance their understanding of ethics will occur through direct meetings and/or dedicated thematic webinars, potentially in collaboration with other partners / projects. Finally, the provision of ad hoc support to address emerging areas of concern will continue through the Ethics HelpDesk.

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4. Recommendations

To address these gaps, the following recommendations are proposed for partners:

- 1) Ethics approval processes should be enhanced by reminding partners to apply early enough for the necessary ethics approvals and encouraging them to flag problems. Also, preparing and sharing the required summaries in English in-consortium should be a requirement.
- 2) Awareness and understanding of the Ethics Framework should be increased.
- 3) Promotion of the guidelines and checklists produced within the project should be conducted regularly.
- 4) Capacity building and guidelines on identifying and documenting vulnerabilities, including those for consent forms and ethical treatment, should be provided.
- 5) To support partners, take meaningful actions, resources on best practices for addressing climate-related mental health concerns should be provided.
- 6) Partners should document measures taken to protect stakeholders' mental health.
- 7) Partners should contact the Ethics HelpDesk if they identify challenges related to their research activities in the RESIST project, when they are in doubt about their situation, or if they need further assistance in identifying ethical issues.

These recommendations are intended to provide partners with guidance to address challenges and leverage best practices moving forward. All partners are encouraged to review these findings and recommendations to foster a stronger commitment to ethical practices within the RESIST project.

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6.2 Annex 2: Ethics Compliance in the RESIST Project - Annotated Aggregated Data – 2025, 1st semester

Ethics Compliance in the RESIST Project

Annotated Aggregated Data

15 April 2025

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Introduction

In line with the [EU Regulation 2021/695](#) and the [RESIST Grant Agreement](#) all RESIST partners are mandated to comply with EU, international, and national laws, promoting research integrity.

In support of this, RESIST established the [Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework D1.9](#) (the Framework) designed to embed gender equality and ethics considerations throughout the project. The Ethics Framework provides for reiterative self-assessment, ongoing ethics support, monitoring, development of guidance and building capacity on the topic, among others. According to the Framework, ethics compliance monitoring is conducted through active data-gathering rounds to assess and ensure that the project activities adhere to ethical standards throughout their implementation.

This document presents the **outcomes of the ethics data collection cycle** conducted across the RESIST project during the first semester of 2025. The data collection spans the period from July 2024 to January 2025 (included). It builds on the [RESIST_Ethics Compliance Annotated Aggregated Data_2024](#) and it outlines the methodology used, highlights key findings for the EC-flagged ethics issues, object of the monitoring and presents conclusions. Additionally, recommendations are provided to address identified gaps and challenges.

It should be noted that this analysis is part of a broader data gathering activity, as outlined in the RESIST Framework and should therefore be considered alongside its counterpart, the RESIST Gender Equality Annotated Aggregated Data 2025 – 1st semester.

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1 Methodology

For the 2025 first round of data gathering on ethics compliance two questionnaires were developed - **ethics compliance** and **AI risk categorization** - and shared (via MS Forms: **ethics compliance**; **AI risk categorization**) with the partners on February 12th, 2025 (M26).

Responses to the **ethics compliance** and **AI risk categorizations** questionnaires were gathered between M26 - M28 (February 2025 and April 2025) with a cutoff date of April 3rd, 2025. **A total of 42 responses were received, representing approximately 75% of RESIST partners.**

For reference, the total number of RESIST partners was set at 56, based on the full **contact list**, to reflect project dynamics and ensure representativeness. These figures serve primarily as a reference point, providing a snapshot of the current status. However, the focus lies on identifying trends over time, which offer deeper insights into the evolving engagement and practices of the partners regarding ethics.

It is also worth noting that 41 out of 42 individuals who completed the survey are part of the RESIST project team, further reinforcing the relevance and reliability of the results.

Compared to the 2024 data collection, a 7% increase in engagement was observed (from 68% in 2024 to 75% in 2025), underscoring the tangible impact of the awareness-raising activities conducted at the project level. It is also noteworthy that for the first round of data collection on ethics compliance, in 2023, the average engagement rate stood at 41%, confirming a consistent upward trend in participation and commitment to ethics monitoring within RESIST.

As stated in the **Grant Agreement**, following the **Ethics Summary Report**, the project activities raise ethics issues in the following fields: Humans, Personal Data, Non-EU countries, Environment, health and safety, Artificial intelligence.

In line with the Framework and considering that the obligation to ensure ethics compliance is twofold, the **ethics compliance questionnaire** addressed both dimensions:

1. ensuring compliance with applicable international, EU, and national law (Section 1 – legal compliance), and
2. ensuring alignment with the highest ethical standards (Section 2):
 - the state of the art at the institutional level regarding adherence to the highest ethical standards,
 - the status of the ethical issues identified for RESIST project and

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- the stimulation of ethical thinking.

To complement the ethics compliance monitoring process — and in the context of the [European Union’s Artificial Intelligence \(AI\) Act](#), which introduces a risk-based framework to regulate AI systems ensuring they are safe, transparent, and respect fundamental rights — a dedicated questionnaire was developed for RESIST partners using or planning to use AI technologies in their project activities. The [AI Risk Categorisation Questionnaire](#) was designed to help RESIST partners assess the risk level of their AI systems, based on the classification criteria set out in the AI Act.

Consequently, the “Key Findings” section of this document is organised into the following sections:

- Legal compliance
- Alignment with the highest ethical standards
- Human participants in research/ project activities
- Environment, health and safety
- Artificial intelligence
- AI risk categorization
- Stimulation of ethical thinking

The purpose and description of each topic are outlined in their respective sections within the “Key Findings” chapter.

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2 Key Findings

This section provides a detailed overview of the ethics compliance status and practices among RESIST project partners, highlighting emerging trends, challenges, and areas for improvement.

The objectives of the analysis of the responses collected through the questionnaires is (a) to assess the current state of ethics compliance and integration of ethical standards within partner organisations, (b) to identify potential ethical risks and offer opportunities for timely action, (c) to identify potential needs for additional guidelines and/ or capacity building and (d) to foster an ongoing culture of ethical awareness and reflection among partners.

The analysis also highlights shared key practices in several areas, providing inspiration and practical examples for all RESIST partners to enhance their own ethics practices.

2.1 Legal compliance

This section serves to indicate whether partners have obtained or are required to obtain national, local, or institutional ethics approval for their RESIST (research) activities.

Out of 42 respondent partners:

- **28 reported that ethics approval was not required** for their research (67%); 5 are not aware of this requirement;

- **9 partners (21%) indicated that they needed institutional/ local approvals:**
 - 5 - acquired- copies not submitted on RESIST SP
 - 2 - decision pending
 - 2 - haven't applied yet

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Fig. 1

The majority of respondent partners (**7 out of 9 – 78%**) who indicated that they require ethics approvals (national/ local/ institutional) have acquired one or the decision is pending. However, those who already acquired the ethics approvals have not uploaded the required documentation to RESIST SP.

For the **2 partners who have not yet applied for the necessary approvals**, if research activities have already commenced, immediate action is required to secure and properly document these approvals. This is essential to prevent potential non-compliance with national, local, or institutional regulations, which could compromise both the integrity of the project and the credibility of its research outcomes.

For the **5 partners (12%) who indicated they are not aware of the requirement for ethics approvals**, further follow-up actions are required.

In case of uncertainty, the **RESIST Ethics HelpDesk** remains available to all partners for clarification and support, ensuring alignment with applicable regulations and project obligations.

Compared to 2024, when 5 out of 6 partners requiring ethics approvals (national, local, or institutional) had not yet applied, the **significant increase in compliance figures in 2025 – 1st semester** reflects both the natural progression of project activities and the positive impact of awareness-raising efforts on the importance of ethics compliance.

2.2 Alignment with the highest ethical standards

This section presents the findings on how the partner organizations of the RESIST project align with internationally recognized standards for research ethics and integrity, including awareness of key research guidelines, ethics governance, and provision of trainings.

The 2025 survey data highlights notable gaps in partner awareness and implementation of central research integrity frameworks across the RESIST project consortium.

Awareness of key research integrity guidelines:

- 60% of respondents (25 out of 42) indicated they are not familiar with the **ALLEA Code of Conduct for Research Integrity** (Fig.2).
- 52% of respondents (22 out of 42) reported being unfamiliar with the **Guideline for Promoting Research Integrity in Research Performing Organisations** (Fig. 3).

This represents a significant decline compared to 2024, when 88% of respondents (36 out of 41) stated they had read and understood the ALLEA Code. The downward trend may be attributed to factors such as staff turnover, organisational restructuring, or insufficient internal communication and training related to research integrity policies. The 2025 survey had already anticipated these issues and was expanded to include questions on internal governance (see section 2.7). This will support the identification of training gaps, enhance understanding of the dynamics, and encourage partner staff to reflect on and consider ethical challenges.

Fig. 2

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Fig. 3

Ethics governance is high, with most partner organisations having dedicated ethics personnel and formal Codes of Conduct in place:

- **40% of respondents (17 out of 42)** confirmed that their organisation has a **dedicated person responsible for ethics and research integrity matters**. Encouragingly, all but one respondent in this group provided contact information, reference details, or a relevant website.
- **A formal Code of Conduct is maintained by 62% of respondents (26 out of 42 - Fig. 4)**. Similarly, nearly all organisations with a Code of Conduct shared reference materials or contact points.

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Fig. 4

Implementation of ethics-related procedures/ policies is good, though some uncertainty remains among respondents:

- **26% of respondents (11 out of 42)** indicated that personnel working on the RESIST project are **bound by a professional Code of Ethics** (Fig. 5).
- **Mechanisms for managing ethics breaches and misconduct** (35 – 83%) were reported as follows (Fig. 6):
 - **15 organisations have a whistleblowing procedure**
 - **20 have another form of internal investigation process**
 - 13 respondents were unsure of existing mechanisms.

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Fig. 5

Fig. 6

The provision of training on ethics compliance and research integrity shows a varied approach across partner organisations (Fig. 7). In particular, the frequency and target groups for such training differ between organisations, as shown below:

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- regularly for:
 - all staff: 17% (7/42)
 - some staff: 17% (7/42)
- occasionally for:
 - all staff: 24% (10/42)
 - some staff: 21% (9/42)
- no training provision: 19% (8/42)

Most of the partners organised **in-house training (23 – 55%)**, webinars (17 – 40%) and organisation-specific documentation training (13 – 31%) - Fig. 8.

Among partners who selected “other ethics training activities” (6 – 14%), **several indicated that no additional initiatives are in place beyond those provided through the RESIST project**. A few partners reported offering access to online courses, with one noting a mandatory annual update requirement for certain personnel, while others referenced the distribution of useful resources and information about external webinars and online training opportunities. Some partners described general awareness-raising efforts, such as briefings during team meetings or the dissemination of general information on research integrity topics.

Fig. 7

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Fig.8

Training on ethics-specific compliance and related themes also varies across partner organisations. Notably, **24 partners reported their organisation provides training on ethics related to human participants**, while **36 partners highlighted training in data protection and 33 partners in environmental health and safety**. Fewer partners, 19 in total, received training on the use of AI in research, and only 2 partners mentioned training in other related areas (Fig.9).

The partners who indicated their organisation provides “other trainings” referenced GDPR training and periodic informative sessions, such as biannual briefings.

Fig. 9

Further, the survey reveals that **57% of partners (24 out of 42) provide ethics training specifically tailored to RESIST activities**, while 43% (18 out of 42) do not (Fig. 10).

This indicates a relatively strong commitment to ensuring that project-specific ethics considerations are addressed, with more than half of the partners recognizing the importance of specialised training for the successful and responsible execution of RESIST activities. However, the fact that 43% of partners have not implemented such targeted training suggests potential gaps in ensuring that all staff members are adequately equipped to handle the ethical challenges specific to RESIST research, highlighting the need for further capacity building in this area.

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Fig.10

In conclusion, while the RESIST project partner organisations demonstrate a strong commitment to research ethics and integrity through established governance structures and ethics training, significant gaps remain in awareness of key international research integrity guidelines and the provision of tailored ethics training for project-specific activities. Addressing these gaps, particularly through capacity building efforts, strengthens the ethical standards and integrity of the RESIST project, ensuring more effective and responsible research practices.

2.3 Human participants in research/ project activities

This section focuses on gathering insights into the involvement of human participants in research, including vulnerable groups, and project activities across partner organisations. Specifically, it aims to assess whether the research conducted by partners includes human subjects—such as in surveys, interviews, or other direct interactions—and to identify the key safeguarding measures implemented to protect the rights and well-being of these participants.

Out of **42 project partners**, **27 (64%) involve human participants in their activities**. Among these, the **vast majority (25) confirm participants are properly informed** and have provided consent for data collection and processing. However, 2 partners — both from the public sector — reported that participants are not adequately informed.

Of those 27 involving human participants:

- **18 partners adopt the RESIST D1.9 context-sensitive definition of vulnerable populations**

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- 6 partners are unaware of the definition used
- 3 partners apply alternate definitions, emphasizing specific categories like migrants, the elderly chronically ill, and children in vulnerable situations

Only 10 out of 27 (37%) partners involve vulnerable groups. The most commonly addressed vulnerabilities are:

- **geographic vulnerabilities (9 partners)**
- socio-economic and age-related vulnerabilities (7 partners each)
- vulnerabilities based on category of population (5 partners).

Other categories like mental health (2) and physical vulnerabilities (1) receive less attention, indicating potential gaps in inclusivity and representation.

Among the 10 partners involving vulnerable groups:

- **60% are fully aware of relevant ethical considerations**
- 30% are partially aware and would benefit from further training
- 1 partner indicated uncertainty, warranting targeted capacity-building efforts.

To preserve the rights, dignity and well-being of human participants involved in research, RESIST partners indicated the following **key safeguarding measures**:

- anonymity and confidentiality (9 partners)
- informed consent (7 partners)
- adherence to ethical guidelines and withdrawal rights (5 partners each).

For **securing fully informed consent from individuals with reduced capacity**, widely used practices at the project level include:

- allowing time for questions (7 partners)
- providing accessible information (6 partners)
- ensuring voluntary participation (6 partners).

However, less common practices like using interpreters (2), involving legal guardians (2), and ongoing consent checks (2) suggest areas for ethical process strengthening.

In conclusion, while the majority of RESIST partners involving human participants demonstrate a commitment to safeguarding rights through informed consent and ethical guidelines, there are notable gaps, particularly in the inclusion of vulnerable populations and practices for securing informed consent from individuals with reduced capacity. Enhancing awareness and training on

ethical considerations, especially for vulnerable groups, and improving consent practices, would further strengthen the ethical standards and participant protection across the project.

2.4 Environment, health and safety (EHS)

This section of the report focuses on the environmental, health, and safety measures implemented by partner organisations to protect both stakeholders and researchers involved in project activities. It explores the strategies in place to mitigate risks to physical health and safety, as well as to address environmental concerns arising from research operations.

Legislation compliance awareness is high, with 83% of respondents indicating awareness of relevant regulations. However, some are still in the early stages of their research, with the scope yet to be fully defined:

Out of 42 respondents:

- 35 confirmed they have reviewed the applicable environmental legislation related to their research and reported no issues; this marks an upward trend compared to 2024, when 18 out of 24 respondents confirmed they had checked the relevant legislation.
- 7 respondents indicated uncertainty about the scope of their research and, as a result, had not yet reviewed the applicable EHS legislation; this is similar to the situation in 2024, when 6 partners reported the same uncertainty.

Adoption of environmental assessment tools is currently limited, with only 11 (26%) respondents actively using tools to assess and minimize environmental impacts, while 28 respondents currently do not assess environmental impacts. The most commonly used tools include:

- the **REGILIENCE self-assessment tool to spot risks of maladaptation**
- Forest Good Practices
- Soil and Water Conservation Guidelines
- resources from Danish Environmental Protection Agency and Nature Agency.

Increasing the adoption of environmental assessment tools can be supported by promoting internal awareness sessions at the project level.

Adoption of climate-related stress protection measures remains low:

- 4 respondents have implemented measures to protect researchers
- 4 respondents have implemented measures to protect participants
- 3 respondents have implemented measures to protect other stakeholders.

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The findings reflect a proactive but evolving commitment to occupational safety, environmental responsibility, and climate adaptation. **Shared practices**, that can serve as inspiration for all RESIST partners, include:

- **collaboration with relevant organisations** to ensure that forest-clearing operations by fire sappers are scheduled to reduce risks for both workers and landowners
- **regular safety training** for trainees and new fieldwork staff is conducted
- implemented **operational sustainability practices**:
 - efficient air conditioning and regular system maintenance for energy efficiency
 - organizing public events during summer at cooler hours
 - eliminating single-use plastics
 - maximizing the use of recycled materials.

Consequently, while partner organisations demonstrate a proactive approach to EHS measures, challenges remain in fully integrating environmental assessment tools and climate-related stress protection measures. There is a strong foundation in legislative compliance and safety practices, but increasing the adoption of environmental impact assessments and climate adaptation strategies will further enhance the protection of stakeholders and researchers involved in the project.

2.5 Artificial intelligence

This section focuses on the integration and application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) within the research activities of partner organisations. As AI technologies continue to play a pivotal role in shaping research methodologies and outcomes, it is essential to understand how AI is currently being used or planned for use in the RESIST project.

Among 42 respondents, **8 partners (19%)** — comprising 6 public sector entities, 1 research organization, and 1 private sector partner — **indicated using AI to support project activities**. AI adoption within project activities is modest, with varied applications, primarily in data processing, content generation, and conceptual planning support.

While awareness of ethical AI practices is emerging, structured and formal governance mechanisms like internal ethics committees remain rare. Most efforts focus on staff training and dataset management.

Ethical safeguards implemented by AI-using partners include:

- training staff on ethical AI use and potential risks — 6 partners

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- using diverse and representative datasets to minimize bias — 3 partners
- employing ‘human-in-the-loop’ review processes to validate AI outcomes — 3 partners
- establishing an internal ethics committee — 1 partner

Ethical oversight for broader technology development is still limited. In addition to AI, **3 partners reported that their activities in RESIST involve technology development with potential ethical implications** (e.g., dual-use technologies). Measures adopted to ensure ethical technology development include:

- adopting internal ethical guidelines and best practices — 2 partners
- providing staff training on ethical technology development — 1 partner

To summarise, while AI is being used in a limited capacity within the RESIST project, there is growing awareness of its ethical implications. However, structured ethical oversight remains rare, with most efforts focusing on staff training and dataset management.

This section on the use of AI is further complemented by the AI risk categorization survey, with data analysis presented in the following section.

2.6 AI risk categorization

The **AI risk categorization survey** aims to categorize the AI systems deployed by participating partners based on potential legal and ethical risks, aligned with applicable regulatory frameworks such as the **EU AI Act** and related governance guidelines. By identifying risk categories, appropriate compliance measures and oversight mechanisms can be implemented.

As above mentioned, among the 42 respondents to the **general ethics compliance questionnaire**, 8 partners reported deploying AI systems. However, only 7 of these partners completed the **AI risk categorization survey**, with the private sector partner not participating.

The survey included 16 risk categorization questions covering areas such as biometric identification, social scoring, behavioural manipulation, subliminal techniques, employment applications, law enforcement use, impacts on fundamental rights, personal data processing, education applications, and automated user interactions.

The survey was structured around the following questions:

1. Does your AI system perform biometric identification in real time (e.g., facial recognition in public spaces)?

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2. Does your AI system generate social scoring based on behaviour or personal characteristics?
3. Does your AI system manipulate human behaviour in a way that could cause harm?
4. Does your AI system use subliminal techniques to influence individuals without their awareness?
5. Is your AI system used in recruitment, worker management, or performance monitoring?
6. Does your AI system assess creditworthiness for financial services?
7. Is your AI used in law enforcement, judicial decision-making, or border control?
8. Does your AI system have a significant impact on individuals' fundamental rights?
9. Does your AI generate deepfakes or synthetic media?
10. Does your AI system involve recommendation algorithms (e.g., content curation, product suggestions)?
11. Does your AI system process personal data for non-critical tasks?
12. Is your AI used in education (e.g., automated grading, admissions, assessments)?
13. Does your AI system interact with users without them being aware (e.g., chatbots, virtual assistants)?
14. Is your AI system primarily used for automation with no direct impact on safety or fundamental rights (e.g., spam filters, AI-powered search engines, grammar checkers)?
15. Does your AI system operate without processing sensitive or personal data?
16. Does your AI system not make decisions that significantly impact individuals?

Question	Yes/ partner type	No
Q1–Q11 (biometrics, social scoring, manipulation, subliminal techniques, etc.)	0	7
Q12: AI in Education (grading, admissions, assessment)	1/ public sector	6
Q13: AI interacting with users unknowingly (chatbots, virtual assistants)	1/ public sector	6
Q14: AI for automation with no safety or fundamental rights impact (spam filters, search, grammar checkers)	2/ public sector	5
Q15: AI operating without processing sensitive or personal data	5/ public sector + research organisations	2
Q16: AI not making decisions significantly impacting individuals	3/ public sector	4

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Assessment:

- **No prohibited or high-risk AI systems identified:** none of the participating partners reported AI systems engaged in biometric identification, social scoring, manipulation, subliminal influencing, law enforcement, judicial decision-making, or systems impacting fundamental rights under categories typically classified as prohibited or high-risk.
- **Limited risk use cases:**
 - Education AI systems: 1 public sector partner reported using AI in education. This may be considered limited- or high-risk depending on jurisdictional classification (e.g., under Annex III of the EU AI Act). A formal classification review against relevant regulations is recommended.
 - User interaction without awareness: 1 public sector partner declared AI systems interacting with users without their explicit awareness. This is a limited-risk use case requiring transparency obligations under most AI governance frameworks. It is recommended to implement appropriate transparency disclosures for users.
- **Minimal-risk and low-impact AI systems:**
 - General automation tools: 2 public sector partners confirmed using AI systems for automation tasks such as spam filtering, AI-powered search, or grammar checking — considered minimal-risk use cases. It is advisable to monitor these systems regularly for any unexpected escalation of impact.
 - Non-personal data processing: 5 partners (public sector and research organisation) confirmed their AI systems do not process sensitive or personal data, lowering potential risk exposure. Continued data protection assessments are recommended to ensure sensitive data processing is not introduced inadvertently.
 - No significant decision-making impact: 3 public sector partners reported their AI systems do not make decisions that significantly affect individuals. This further supports a minimal-risk categorization for these systems.

Overall, while the AI systems deployed by partners present limited risks, ongoing monitoring and compliance with regulatory frameworks remain essential to ensure ethical and legal standards are upheld.

2.7 Stimulation of ethical thinking

This section was designed to stimulate reflective thinking among consortium partners by presenting them with a range of ethically challenging scenarios. The aim was not to test knowledge, but to gather personal viewpoints and help inform the development of ethics materials, guidelines, and activities within the consortium. The collected information will also help to develop further material and activities for the integration of ethics into RESIST activities.

The scenarios addressed the following ethical concerns:

- Plagiarism
- Manipulating authorship credit
- Incitement to hate/discrimination in public statements
- Conflict of interest within project consortia
- Falsified research results
- Misuse of research funds
- Undisclosed use of AI in recruitment

The survey was structured around the following questions:

1. **Plagiarism:** reports submitted by the consortium are almost entirely copied from the web. Which answer would be closest to your thinking?
2. **Manipulating authorship:** at submission, lead author demotes co-authors to contributors, thus depriving them from the due benefits of citation metrics. Which answer would be closest to your thinking?
3. **Public statements:** consortium partner makes a public speech inciting to hate and discrimination. Which answer would be closest to your thinking?
4. **Conflict of interest:** in a three-member consortium, partner A asks partner B to fail partner C's work on grounds of quality in order to redistribute partner C's budget between A and B. Which answer would be closest to your thinking?
5. **Research results:** national investigation uncovers that clinical studies were falsified. Which answer would be closest to your thinking?
6. **Use of resources:** researchers use research funds on a trip which the press calls a junket. Which answer would be closest to your thinking?

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7. **Use of AI:** when hiring a post-doc for a project, the HR department of a research organisation uses AI without disclosing it to the appointee. Which answer would be closest to your thinking?

Across almost all scenarios:

- a **clear majority** (between 15–30 out of 42 respondents) believe that the **consortium should have internal rules addressing these situations**. this signals a shared recognition of the value of pre-emptive, codified ethical standards within collaborative research projects;
- **very few partners' representatives (between 1–9 out of 42) opted to leave resolution to legal action by injured parties**, showing a preference for internal, proactive governance rather than reactive, external resolution;
- a **noticeable minority selected 'Not Sure'** (between 3–11 out of 42 respondents), suggesting either ethical uncertainty, scenario complexity, or insufficient contextual information;
- **only a very small number of respondents (between 1–3 out of 42) viewed these scenarios as 'non-issues'**, indicating general ethical awareness and recognition of the potential seriousness of such situations.

On the specific **case of falsified clinical studies (question no. 5 above – Research results)**, a majority of 14 out of 42 respondents recommended terminating the grant entirely. This reflects a particularly low tolerance for research misconduct that compromises public trust and scientific integrity.

To conclude, the majority of respondents recognize the importance of having internal ethical rules to address challenging situations in research. There is a strong preference for proactive, internal governance over reactive legal action, especially in cases of serious misconduct like falsified research. However, a minority of respondents expressed uncertainty or viewed some scenarios as less concerning, highlighting the need for further clarity and guidance on ethical issues within the consortium.

3 Conclusions

The compliance monitoring within the RESIST project confirms the conclusions of 2024 assessment with both progress and ongoing challenges. **The data indicates that the number of partners engaging in ethics monitoring has risen in 2025 compared to 2024, showing a 7% increase (from 68% to 75%).** This highlights an increasing recognition of the importance of ethics compliance within the consortium. While the overall commitment to ethical practices is strong, there are several critical areas that need focused attention.

First, the 2025 first semester review indicates **encouraging progress in ethics compliance among RESIST partners**, with a marked improvement since 2024. Most partners requiring ethics approvals have either obtained them or are awaiting decisions, reflecting increased awareness and responsiveness to ethics obligations. However, some partners have yet to initiate the approval process or are uncertain about the requirements. Continued engagement and prompt action are essential to uphold the project's ethical standards and maintain compliance throughout the next phases. In this context, the project management team plays a pivotal role by requiring the timely securing of all necessary ethics approvals, thereby ensuring compliance with ethics obligations throughout the consortium.

Second, while the RESIST consortium demonstrates **solid foundations in ethics governance, with many partners maintaining formal structures and procedures**. However, the findings highlight gaps in familiarity with international research integrity standards and inconsistent delivery of ethics training. To maintain alignment with the highest ethical standards, efforts should focus on enhancing awareness, improving internal communication, and expanding tailored training initiatives. Additionally, improving dissemination strategies, especially during personnel changes, and integrating ethics training more thoroughly into project activities will help address diverse ethical concerns across research areas.

The majority of RESIST project partners ensure informed consent and adhere to essential ethical practices when involving human participants in research. However, there are notable areas that require improvement. Not all partners are familiar with or apply standardized definitions of vulnerable populations, and only a small proportion engage with these groups. Although common safeguarding measures, such as confidentiality and informed consent, are widely practiced, less frequent actions like involving legal guardians or using interpreters indicate gaps in inclusivity and thoroughness. To address these gaps, further training and capacity-building efforts are needed, especially for partners working with vulnerable populations, to ensure consistent and high ethical standards across all organizations.

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Significant progress has been made in implementing environment, health, and safety measures, with partner organizations showing adherence to relevant legislation and a proactive approach to safety. However, challenges remain in fully incorporating environmental impact assessments and climate-related stress mitigation strategies. To further protect researchers and stakeholders, it will be essential to expand the use of environmental assessment tools and strengthen climate adaptation measures, ensuring the continued sustainability and accountability of project activities.

The **integration of AI within the RESIST project is still limited** but gradually expanding, particularly in areas like data processing, content creation, and planning assistance. Although awareness of the ethical considerations surrounding AI is growing, formal structures for ethical oversight, such as internal ethics committees, are still uncommon. Most partners are focused on training staff and managing datasets to reduce potential risks, with some efforts aimed at minimizing bias and promoting ethical AI practices. As AI becomes more integral to the research process, developing more structured ethical governance will be essential for its responsible deployment.

The **AI risk categorization survey revealed that none of the participating partners are using AI systems classified as high-risk or prohibited**, such as biometric identification, social scoring, or systems impacting fundamental rights. Most AI systems in use are categorized as minimal- or low-risk, including automation tools and systems that do not process personal data. However, certain use cases, such as AI in education and user interactions without explicit awareness, require further review and may be subject to transparency obligations. Although the AI systems used by partners pose minimal risks, ongoing oversight is necessary to ensure alignment with regulatory frameworks and uphold ethical and legal standards.

The **responses to the “stimulation of ethical thinking” section of the survey revealed a clear preference for managing ethical concerns through internal governance, rather than relying solely on legal actions.** However, a small group of respondents expressed uncertainty or viewed some situations as less serious, indicating a need for more detailed guidance on ethical matters. The strong preference for internal rules highlights the importance of addressing ethical issues such as plagiarism, authorship, public conduct, conflicts of interest, fund use, AI transparency, and research integrity internally, at the project level, through enhanced frameworks and capacity building. Additionally, the limited support for legal-only solutions demonstrates that partners favour managing ethical risks within the consortium, emphasizing the need for strong internal governance and support mechanism, such as the HelpDesk.

A **common suggestion from partners** is to communicate before distributing the questionnaires to clarify the scope of each section and ensure valuable data is collected. Some partners mentioned

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that the research-focused questions did not align with their roles in the consortium, highlighting the need for more relevant and targeted questions that fully reflect the diverse tasks of all partners.

In conclusion, the **findings from the first-round of 2025 data-gathering campaign conducted between M26 and M28 (2025) confirm the ongoing need to continue implementing the Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework**. This remains an important tool for monitoring ethics compliance trends and identifying challenges across RESIST activities—ultimately supporting alignment with the highest ethical standards within the consortium.

Ethics compliance within the RESIST project appears to align well with the overall project implementation. However, efforts to raise ethics awareness must be maintained and strengthened. Key areas requiring continued attention include training, ethical oversight, and environmental sustainability. Ongoing initiatives to improve ethical governance, AI oversight, and staff training will be essential to ensuring the project upholds high ethical standards and adheres to international research integrity principles as it progresses.

Moving forward, the results of this analysis will shape the development of specific, actionable steps for the implementation of the Framework and will inform the objectives for subsequent rounds of ethics data collection, continuing to foster a culture of ethical research practice. More specifically:

- to ensure ethical compliance, **ongoing engagement and timely action** are essential to uphold the project's ethical standards;
- efforts should focus on **raising awareness of international research integrity standards**; for this, work package meetings, EB meetings, and other gatherings should be used to encourage partner staff to regularly consult the centralized ethics repository and resources to stay updated on the latest guidance;
- priority should be given to **capacity building** for partners:
 - working with vulnerable populations
 - using or planning to use AI
- the **ethics questionnaire will be updated** to fully reflect the diverse activities of all partners.

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4 Recommendations

The 2024 recommendations, including (i) contacting the Ethics HelpDesk for assistance with research challenges, uncertainties, or identifying ethical issues, and (ii) addressing gaps in safeguarding vulnerable populations, have been confirmed by the 2025 – 1st semester data collection.

Additionally, specific recommendations emerged from the 2025 first semester campaign, highlighting the need for increased attention to ethical practices and ongoing support to address emerging challenges in the RESIST project.

In light of these findings, it is recommended that partner organisations implement the following actions:

1) Enhanced ethics training:

- implementation of **systematic onboarding training for all new staff** on research integrity and ethical standards within the RESIST project
- organization of **annual refresher workshops** to maintain ongoing ethical awareness across all staff

2) Expansion of environmental impact assessment tools:

- increased **adoption of environmental impact assessment tools** across project activities
- implementation of **climate stress mitigation strategies** throughout the project to strengthen long-term sustainability and reduce the environmental footprint

3) Strengthened AI ethics:

- implementation of **transparency and user-awareness mechanisms** for AI systems to minimize ethical risks and ensure clear communication
- regularly review AI systems and their data practices to monitor emerging risks and ensure continuous compliance with ethical and legal standards.

6.3 Annex 3: Gender Equality Mainstreaming in the RESIST Project - Annotated Aggregated Data - 2024

Gender Equality Mainstreaming in the RESIST Project

Annotated Aggregated Data

15 November 2024

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Introduction

Gender equality is a core value of the EU, a fundamental right and key principle of the European Pillar of Social Rights. It is, among others, an essential condition for an innovative, competitive and thriving European economy.

The European Commission is committed to promoting gender equality in research and innovation through **Horizon Europe Programme** (2021 – 2027). This effort aligns with the **Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025**, which sets out the Commission's broader commitment to equality across all EU policies.

The overall goal is to improve the European research and innovation system, create gender-equal working environments where all talents can thrive, and better integrate the gender dimension in projects to improve research quality.

The **RESIST Grant Agreement** mandates that all partners mainstream gender balance throughout the project. Beneficiaries are required to actively promote equal opportunities between men and women throughout the implementation of the action, aligning with the gender equality plan when applicable. Efforts should be made to achieve gender balance across all levels of personnel involved in the action, including supervisory and managerial roles.

The **Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework D1.9** (the Framework) provides an analytical framework to monitor the gender and ethics dimensions throughout the RESIST project. According to the Framework, the gender equality dimension cuts across all project activities, with gender balance and gender mainstreaming pursued at every step of the project. This objective is being achieved through two lines of action – general and specific. The general part includes gender consideration across the project's operations, whereas the specific part focuses on including gender considerations in the Climate Change Adaptation research and innovation activities being pursued by the four demonstrators, their eight twinning regions and in the horizontal activities of the project. Implementing the Framework in the RESIST project requires essentially assessing the needs of the project activities and providing specific guidance documents and checklists, collecting sex/ gender disaggregated data, applying gender-sensitive language in all communication, dissemination, and outreach activities, building partners' capacity on the topic.

This document presents the results of the first cycle of data collection conducted across the entire RESIST project to measure the mainstreaming of Gender Equality, including dissemination events and expert teams. It outlines the methodology used, highlights key findings related to both general and specific aspects of the Framework, and presents conclusions. Additionally, recommendations are provided to address identified gaps and challenges.

It should be noted that this analysis is part of a broader data gathering activity, as outlined in the RESIST Framework, and should therefore be considered alongside its counterpart, the RESIST Ethics Compliance Annotated Aggregated Data 2024. While the two documents focus on distinct

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areas, they are inherently interlinked through shared themes, such as the involvement of all human participants in research. While addressing common issues, different perspectives are observed, aiming to assess the state of the art in their respective areas and to identify the best ways of supporting the RESIST partner organizations in advancing compliance with gender+ equality and ethics standards.

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1. Methodology

For the collection of sex/ gender-disaggregated data at the overall project as well as dissemination events and expert teams, a **gender equality questionnaire** (shared via **MS Forms**) was developed and shared with the partners on July, 1st 2024 (M19). To align with the Framework, the questionnaire addresses both the general and the specific parts of the Framework. The data collected through the questionnaire covers the following topics: the assessment of the presence of GEPs and related policies at institutional level, the collection of sex/ gender disaggregated data within RESIST partner organisations, the use of gender sensitive communication, the organisation of inclusive dissemination events and inclusive research activities.

Responses to the gender equality questionnaire were gathered between M19 - M21 (July 2024 and September 2024) with a cut off date of September 20, 2024. A total of 38 responses were received, representing 38 (68%) out of the 56 partners of RESIST.

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2. Key Findings

This section presents the analysis of the responses collected through the questionnaire, offering a comprehensive assessment of the partners' current state of progress on gender equality, both within research teams (Section A – general part of the Framework) and in the integration of gender equality into project activities (Section B – specific part of the Framework). The analysis contextualizes the collected data within the frame of the EC requirements and examine the responses to each question, highlighting emerging trends, challenges, and areas for improvement reported by the respondents.

A. General Part of the Framework

2.1 Gender equality at institutional level

The data gathered on the existence of a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) and other policies related to gender equality, diversity, and inclusion aims to provide insights into the current status of commitment within RESIST partners to uphold gender equality principles at the institutional level.

This analysis is particularly relevant in light of the European Commission's requirement for public bodies, research organizations, universities, and higher education institutions to implement a GEP as a mandatory criterion for accessing funding, especially within the Horizon Europe Programme. This initiative aims to eliminate gender inequality and intersecting socio-economic disparities within research and innovation systems.

To meet the eligibility criterion for accessing EU-funding in Horizon Europe, a GEP must fulfil **four mandatory requirements**:

- the GEP must be a public document;
- there must be adequate resources and expertise allocated to implementing the GEP;
- the GEP must include data collection on gender-related issues and indicators;
- the institution should raise awareness/ train their staff on gender equality and unconscious gender biases.

While institutions have flexibility in designing their GEPs, in terms of content, the EC recommends covering the following **thematic areas**:

- work-life balance and organisational culture;

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- gender balance in leadership and decision-making;
- gender equality in recruitment and career progression;
- integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content;
- measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

The analysis of the data collected revealed that, out of the 38 respondents, 28 partners (74%) confirmed that they have a GEP in place (Fig.1). Among those with GEPs, the majority are public sector organizations or research-performing organizations. One partner, a non-profit organisation not mandated to have a GEP, also reported having implemented one.

Fig. 1

Out of the 28 respondents with GEP, 27 (96%) declared that their GEP complies with the four mandatory EC requirements, while only 24 (86%) partners stated that their GEP is publicly available (Fig.2).

The 5 partners who indicated that either their GEP is not public or explicitly indicated that their GEP does not comply with EC requirements, had previously declared at the time of signing the GA, that their GEP fully complies with the EC requirements, including the criterion of public accessibility. This apparent discrepancy suggests that the individuals completing the RESIST questionnaire may not have been fully aware of their institutional settings or the EC requirements for Research and Innovation projects funded under Horizon Europe. This highlights the need for capacity-building initiatives to enhance understanding of GEP content and compliance with EC standards.

Fig. 2

Most of the respondent partners with a GEP (approx. 61%) reported that their plans cover 4 to 5 key thematic areas recommended by the EC. The themes covered, ranked by the number of partners addressing them, are:

- gender balance in leadership and decision-making: 25 partners;
- work–life balance and organizational culture: 24 partners;
- gender equality in recruitment and career progression: 24 partners;
- measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment: 24 partners;
- integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content: 16 partners.

It is observed that the thematic area least covered by GEPs is the “integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content”, with only 16 partners addressing this theme. This represents 57% of the partners with a GEP, compared to 86-89% compliance for the other recommended thematic areas. This issue is further highlighted by the fact that only 16 partners (57%) responded affirmatively when asked if their GEP explicitly includes gender dimension in research (Fig. 3). Overall, while the state of the art among most RESIST partners in implementing GEPs and addressing key thematic areas is promising, a significant gap remains in integrating the gender dimension into research within GEPs. This is particularly concerning, given that it is one of the primary goals of the EC under Horizon Europe Programme.

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Fig. 3

Further, the assessment of the data collected also shows that among the 10 partners (26%) declaring not having a GEP:

- 4 partners indicated that they plan to adopt one by the end of 2024 or during 2025, while 1 partner (a region) indicated that they will do so soon;
- 2 partners indicated that their focus is not on having or updating a GEP, but instead, their gender equality objectives have been integrated into broader sustainability programs, including initiatives like data collection, training programs, diversity policies, and embedding gender equality into their corporate strategies.

Among the respondents, 15 partners (39%) indicated they have additional policies in place related to gender equality, diversity or inclusion. These policies include equal employment opportunity measures, work-life balance initiatives, non-discrimination guidelines, a code of conduct to prevent harassment, and dedicated units focused on equality. Regarding the explicit mention of gender in research in these additional policies, 9 partners (60%) confirmed the policies mention gender in research explicitly. Additionally, 10 partners (67%) reported that their additional policies are publicly available, enhancing transparency and accountability in their commitment to gender equality and inclusion.

Moreover, the data collected also shows that out of 38 respondent partners:

- 10 partners have both a GEP and other gender equality policies in place;

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- among the 10 partners who do not have a GEP, 5 partners have other gender equality policies;
- only 5 partners stated that they have neither a GEP nor any other gender equality policies.

Consequently, it is noted that a majority of the respondent partners (87%, n=33) are mainstreaming gender equality into their institutional policies, either through GEPs and / or other policies (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4 The data gathering revealed that the majority of respondent partners have institutional-level policies to mainstream gender equality.

However, out of the 38 respondents, 14 partners do not explicitly address gender in research within their GEP or other institutional policies, emphasizing the necessity for further assistance for partners to both meet EC requirements and contribute to achieving EC goals.

2.2 Gender composition of RESIST teams

To better understand and improve gender equality within the RESIST partners, data was collected on various aspects of gender representation within RESIST partners teams.

The core teams from January to June 2024 had the following gender composition: 129 women (46%), 147 men (52%), 4 non-binary individuals (1,4%), and 1 person who preferred not to disclose their gender (0,35%), demonstrating an almost balanced gender representation (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5

Among the team leaders during this period, **gender balance was observed with 18 (47%) women and 19 (50%) men leading the teams, with 1 (3%) individual opting not to specify** (Fig. 6). **Notably, it was reported that five of the work package leaders are women (100%), although in reality, only three work packages are led by women. Nonetheless, this still highlights a positive trend towards the participation of women in leadership roles.**

Fig. 6

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B. Specific Part of the Framework

2.3 Gender Sensitive Communication

Gender-sensitive communication strategies play a pivotal role in fostering an inclusive environment where all individuals feel respected and valued. Data on gender-sensitive communication practices was collected to identify best practices and areas for improvement in how RESIST partners communicate in an inclusive way.

The feedback on the use of the **RESIST Gender Sensitive and Inclusive Communication Guidelines** reflects a significant commitment to promoting gender sensitivity among RESIST partners. **Out of 38 partners, 24 respondents (63%) affirmed the use of these guidelines, many declaring that they actively incorporated these principles into their daily practices, particularly in internal communications and social media.** Although some partners have not extensively utilized the guidelines yet, they remain confident in their existing practices for fostering inclusivity. While relatively few responses were received about the **RESIST Checklist for Social Media Publications**, among those who did respond, a high percentage (69%, n=9 partners out of 13 respondents) indicated awareness and acknowledged it as a valuable resource (Fig. 7).

Alongside the RESIST resources, out of 38 respondents, 10 partners (26%) also utilize a variety of other resources for their communication and gender equality initiatives. These include the picture database for visual content, as well as adherence to specific laws and protocols and the internal guidelines of organizations. Some partners rely on their corporate communication departments for support with communication needs, while others refer to internal guides or utilize public online resources. Additionally, many respondents mention using search engines to find relevant information quickly and efficiently, indicating a proactive approach to accessing the necessary resources for effective communication and compliance with gender equality standards (Fig. 7).

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Fig. 7

Overall, the responses reflect a positive trend towards embracing inclusive communication, with many expressing a readiness to engage with the RESIST guidelines as relevant opportunities arise. This indicates a shared commitment to fostering respectful and equitable communication practices in their respective environments and activities.

2.4 Gender composition in dissemination events (external)

To monitor that dissemination activities organized by RESIST partners were inclusive and represent diverse voices, data was gathered on attendees to external events, including speakers and panelists. This initiative aims to assess the effectiveness of RESIST checklists and guidelines in promoting inclusivity and to identify areas where improvements can be made.

Among the 38 respondents, 14 partners (37%) organized between 1 and 4 dissemination events since the start of the project. Of these, most partners (8 partners - 57%) have consulted the **RESIST Checklist for Organising Inclusive Stakeholder Meetings**, reflecting a commitment to inclusivity in their planning (Fig. 8).

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Fig. 8

However, only 14% (2 out of 14) of the partners who organized dissemination events reported collecting disaggregated data by sex and/or gender regarding the speakers and panelists presenting in these events, with none of them collecting data on the participants (Fig. 9). This observation suggests an opportunity to strengthen data collection practices within the RESIST project, which could support efforts to enhance gender mainstreaming.

Fig. 9

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2.5 Gender dimension in research & innovation

Equitable outcomes in research require a commitment to inclusivity that accurately reflects diverse perspectives and experiences. By gathering data regarding the research conducted by the RESIST partners, enables intersectional analysis, allowing for tailored support and the development of guidance to specific project activities.

The data shows that 15 (39%) of the 38 respondent partners are actively conducting research as part of the project (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10

Of the 15 partners who declared they conduct research in RESIST, 3 partners (20%) indicated they consulted only the **RESIST Checklist for Including the Gender Dimension in Research** (the Checklist). Similarly, 3 partners (20%) reported using only the **RESIST Repository for Gender Equality and Ethics** (the Repository). The majority of partners (53%; n=8) consulted both the Checklist and the Repository, demonstrating their commitment to incorporating the gender dimension into their research activities (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11 The results are based on the responses received from 15 out of 38 partners who indicated they conduct research as part of the project.

3. Conclusions

At the institutional level (general part of the Framework), the comprehensive data gathering exercise has yielded significant insights into the current state of GEPs and other gender equality related policies within RESIST partners' institutions. The findings indicate that the majority of respondents possess a GEP (74%; n=28), including one partner who is not mandated to have one. When considering the respondents that declared having other gender equality related policies in place, it sums to a total of 87% of the respondents (n=33). This highlights a strong commitment within RESIST partners to fostering gender balance and equity at the institutional level. Moreover, the majority of GEPs are aligned with the EC mandatory requirements and cover most of the EC-recommended areas, indicating a comprehensive approach to gender equality.

However, the data gathering also reveals a gap where a small number of partners either lack clarity on the EC requirements or lack the information needed to accurately answer these questions. The identification of discrepancies will inform the activity plan for implementing the Framework, highlighting the need to raise greater awareness about the EC requirements and their practical implications. Regarding the recommended areas, there is a need to specifically address the topic of the integration of gender dimension in research practices within the GEPs. This indicates an opportunity for partners to improve their policies and align more closely with EC guidelines and objectives under the Horizon Europe Programme.

Importantly, the data collected about the gender composition of the RESIST teams demonstrates that gender balance is being achieved both within the teams and in leadership roles, which is an essential step towards fostering a more equitable research work environment.

At the level of research activities (specific part of the Framework), the data collection exercise has shed light on partners' awareness and efforts regarding the use of sensitive language in communication. While many find the checklists and guidelines to be valuable resources, with users appreciating their clarity and accessibility, some highlight challenges in their application. To sustain this momentum and facilitate better understanding and adoption of these guidelines, continuous awareness initiatives, further ad-hoc support and capacity building activities are needed.

Regarding the gender composition in the organisation of external project events, the data reveals a concerning trend: although only a few partners organized dissemination events, there is a notable lack of sex/gender-disaggregated data collection related to these activities. Dedicated capacity-building efforts are needed to empower partners to improve their data collection practices, especially those planning to organize such events in the future in order to improve gender mainstreaming within the activities organised in the RESIST project.

Finally, by leveraging various tools and resources, the majority of the partners conducting research in the project show a commitment to enhance the quality of their research results by including a broad range of perspectives. Ongoing reminders and awareness campaigns will be needed to sustain this progress.

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In conclusion, the findings from the first data-gathering campaign conducted between M19 and M21 (2024) confirm the efficiency of the Framework and demonstrate that this exercise is an essential mechanism for identifying trends and challenges related to gender equality and mainstreaming at both the research level and within the activities of the RESIST project.

Moving forward, the insights gathered will inform future developments and guide the necessary next steps for the tailored implementation of the Framework, as well as the objectives for the next round of data collection on gender equality. More precisely, among other things, the gender equality questionnaire will be updated based on these results to enhance the integration of gender equality in research. New dimensions, such as the gender implications of AI use and the nature-based solutions, will also be incorporated. Finally, capacity building for RESIST partners on integrating gender+ equality into research will be a central focus of upcoming activities.

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4. Recommendations

To address the identified gaps, the following recommendations are proposed for partners:

- 1) where applicable, enhance understanding of the EC requirements regarding institutional GEPs by, among others, consulting the RESIST Repository, which provides guidance and references related to these requirements;
- 2) enhance GEP content: while many GEPs cover the basic EC recommended thematic areas, there is a need to strengthen the integration of the gender dimension within research practices; partners are recommended to review and suggest updates to their GEPs to include clear strategies and actions for embedding gender perspectives throughout the research process, from design to dissemination;
- 3) improve data collection in dissemination activities: a critical gap has been identified in the collection of sex/gender-disaggregated data from presenters and participants of external dissemination events; capacity-building efforts should focus on improving data collection practices among all RESIST partners.
- 4) sustain awareness of gender-sensitive language use through ad-hoc support and capacity-building activities to help partners better embrace this practice;
- 5) ongoing awareness raising campaigns and capacity-building efforts are needed to facilitate the integration of the gender dimension into research and innovation practices, thus improving the quality of RESIST research.

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6.4 Annex 4: Gender Equality Mainstreaming in the RESIST Project - Annotated Aggregated Data – 2025, 1st semester

Gender Equality Mainstreaming in the RESIST Project

Annotated Aggregated Data

15 April 2025

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Introduction

In line with the [Horizon Europe Programme](#) (2021 – 2027), the [Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025](#) and the [RESIST Grant Agreement](#), all RESIST partners are mandated to mainstream gender balance across the project.

One of the **overarching EU goals is to foster gender-equal working environments** where all talents can thrive and to better integrate gender dimensions into research to enhance its quality and societal relevance. In support of this, RESIST established the [Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework D1.9](#) (the Framework) designed to embed gender equality (GE) and ethics considerations throughout the project. The gender dimension addresses both general (institutional level) and specific actions (project activities). Implementation includes needs assessments, development of guidance tools, collection of sex/gender-disaggregated data, use of gender-sensitive language, and capacity-building for partners.

This document presents the **outcomes of the second cycle of gender equality data collection** conducted across the RESIST project during the first semester of 2025. The data collection spans the period from July 2024 to January 2025 (included). It builds on the [Gender Equality annotated aggregated data 2024](#), assessing progress, identifying persisting or emerging gaps, while providing insights into the overall direction in which gender equality initiatives are developing within the project. It outlines the methodology used, highlights key findings related to both general and specific aspects of the Framework, and presents conclusions. Additionally, recommendations are provided to address identified gaps and challenges.

It should be noted that this analysis is part of a broader data gathering activity, as outlined in the RESIST Framework and should therefore be considered alongside its counterpart, the RESIST Ethics Compliance Annotated Aggregated Data 2025 – 1st semester.

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1 Methodology

For the collection of sex/ gender-disaggregated data at the overall project level as well as expert teams, a **gender equality questionnaire** (shared via **MS Forms**) was developed and shared with the partners on February 12th, 2025 (M26). To align with the Framework, the questionnaire addresses both the general and the specific parts of the Framework. The data collected through the questionnaire covers the following topics: **the assessment of the presence of GEPs and related policies at institutional level, the collection of sex/ gender disaggregated data within RESIST partner organisations, the inclusion of gender considerations in research activities, as well as gender implications of AI and the nature-based solutions (NBS) at the project level.**

Responses to the gender equality questionnaire were gathered between M26 - M28 (February 2025 and April 2025) with a cutoff date of April 3rd, 2025. **A total of 41 responses were received, representing approximately 73% of RESIST partners.**

For reference, the total number of RESIST partners was set at 56, based on the full **contact list**, to reflect project dynamics and ensure representativeness. These figures serve primarily as a reference point, providing a snapshot of the current status. However, the focus lies on identifying trends over time, which offer deeper insights into the evolving engagement and practices of the partners regarding gender equality.

It is also worth noting that 40 out of 41 individuals who completed the survey are part of the RESIST project team, further reinforcing the relevance and reliability of the results.

Compared to the 2024 data collection, a 5% increase in engagement was observed (from 68% in 2024 to 73% in 2025), underscoring the impact of the awareness-raising activities conducted at the project level.

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2 Key Findings

This section presents the analysis of the responses collected through the [questionnaire](#), offering a comprehensive assessment of the partners' current state of progress on gender equality, both at institutional level (**Section A – general part of the Framework**) and in the integration of gender equality into project activities (**Section B – specific part of the Framework**). The analysis contextualizes the collected data within the frame of the EC requirements and examines the responses to each question, highlighting emerging trends and challenges. It also identifies areas for improvement and highlights shared key practices to gender mainstreaming to serve as inspiration for all RESIST partners.

A. General Part of the Framework

2.1 Gender equality at institutional level

The [2024 data gathering](#) revealed that the state of the art among most RESIST partners in implementing Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) and addressing key thematic areas is promising. In 2024, at the institutional level, 87% of partners have GEPs or related policies, reflecting strong commitment to gender equality. While most GEPs meet the European Commission's [four mandatory requirements](#), the least addressed [recommended thematic area](#) was found to be “*the integration of the gender dimension into research*”.

In 2025, the first round of data gathering showed that **out of 41 respondent partners, 33 (80%) had a GEP in place** (Fig.1). Among these partners, most are public sector organizations (27%; n=9 out of 33) and research organisations (61%; n=20 out of 33), as confirmed by the data in Fig.2.

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Fig. 1

Fig.2

At the time of drafting, respondents who completed the survey in 2024 and the first questionnaire in 2025, and who have declared planning to adopt a GEP in 2024, have not done so yet. Out of the 4 partners who declared planning to adopt a GEP, two confirmed their intention to adopt a GEP in the course of 2025, while the two others have indicated plans to do so in 2026 or in the following years, in line with EU regulations.

Among partners who declared no intention to adopt a GEP, one clarified that, as a non-governmental agency operating under Portuguese law, there is no legal obligation to adopt a GEP. Nevertheless, the partner emphasized a commitment to maintaining gender parity within the organization and upholding respect for all genders as part of its internal practices.

Further, the survey addressed one of the primary goals of the EC under the Horizon Europe Programme and a gap identified in 2024: integrating the gender dimension into research within GEPs. The data revealed that 17 - out of 33 respondent partners (52%) with a GEP - have explicitly included gender considerations in research in their GEPs. However, 6 partners (18%) remain uncertain about whether this integration has been included (Fig.3). Thus, the actual number of partners integrating gender considerations in research into their GEPs may be higher.

These findings further reinforce the results from 2024, where 16 out of 28 respondent partners (57%) with a GEP had explicitly included gender considerations in research into their GEPs.

In addition, the data also underscores the ongoing need for targeted capacity-building initiatives to improve staff understanding of GEP content and ensure better compliance with EC standards.

Fig. 3

In order to deepen the analysis, **the survey explored whether the inclusion of gender considerations is a generic approach or specifically tailored to the areas of activity within each partner organization.** This approach provided deeper insight into how gender integration is being applied in research across RESIST partners. **Out of 17 respondent partners declaring integrating GE considerations in research into their GEPs, 13 (76%) partners adopt a generic**

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approach, while 4 (26%) partners adopt a combination of generic and tailored to specific fields / topics approaches (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4 - 17 out of 33 respondent partners with a GEP declared integrating GE considerations in research into their GEPs

Some partners reported implementing tailored approaches to gender equality within their institutional practices. For example, in the areas of research and publication, one partner indicated the existence of a policy requiring a minimum of 40% female representation in editorial roles. Additionally, initiatives such as a dedicated award for Best Gender Equality Final Degree Work were highlighted, aimed at encouraging students to explore gender-related topics in their academic pursuits. In the area of recruitment, gender equality is promoted through the inclusion of diversity statements, reinforcing institutional commitment to inclusive hiring practices.

Survey responses highlighted a **variety of institutional practices** aimed at strengthening gender equality through both process-oriented and content-oriented measures within GEPs. At the project level, **reported key practices for including gender considerations in research into GEPs** include:

- ✓ **communication and language use:** adoption of plain, neutral, and inclusive language across documentation and internal communications; regular updates on GEP implementation are shared via internal staff mailing lists;
- ✓ **monitoring and evaluation:** verification of GEP indicators through tools such as annual staff satisfaction surveys and gender audits, ensuring continued relevance and progress;

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- ✓ **recruitment and governance:** integration of diversity statements in recruitment processes and inclusion of gender-disaggregated data rules; governance structures promote gender diversity, with women actively represented in leadership and decision-making bodies;
- ✓ **awareness and training:** organization of internal awareness sessions on gender equality and inclusion, and provision of mandatory training on gender sensitivity and unconscious bias for staff and students;
- ✓ **institutional structures:** establishment of dedicated equality offices responsible for overseeing and coordinating gender-related policies and initiatives;
- ✓ **research and academic integration:** specific policies to ensure gender balance in research activities and time allocation; support mechanisms are available for underrepresented genders, particularly in funding applications; gender considerations are also integrated into doctoral education curricula and general study plans;
- ✓ **reporting and safety mechanisms:** implementation of clear anti-harassment protocols and accessible reporting systems; safe spaces are made available for reporting incidents of discrimination or violence;
- ✓ **recognition and incentives:** introduction of prizes that promote gender-specific academic work, such as recognising outstanding student theses on the topic of gender equality;
- ✓ **gender-focused research:** encouragement and support for interdisciplinary research addressing gender issues, including workplace equality, gender-based violence, and women's health.

Another aspect explored was whether **institutions are required to obtain an endorsement or submit a report on the integration of the gender equality dimension in research at the institutional level**. Among the 17 partners who reported including gender considerations in research within their GEPs, only one indicated that a report is required. Three respondents were unsure, while the remaining 13 partners confirmed that such a requirement does not apply to their institutions. This suggests that formal endorsement or reporting obligations related to gender integration in research remain limited or unclear across the majority of RESIST partners. (Fig.5)

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Fig. 5 - 17 out of 33 respondent partners with a GEP declared integrating GE considerations in research into their GEPs

Of the 41 respondents, **20 partners (49%) stated that they have additional strategies in place in relation to equality, diversity or inclusion.** It is worth noting that the survey allowed respondents to select “don’t know,” which may have influenced the results and suggests that the actual number of partners with such policies could be higher.

Moreover, the data from 2025 also reveal the following breakdown among the 41 respondents:

- 15 partners reported having both a GEP and other gender equality-related policies;
- 10 partners indicated they were not aware of any additional gender equality policies within their institution;
- 4 partners (who also have a GEP) declared their intention to adopt a gender equality policy;
- only 3 partners stated that they have neither a GEP nor other gender equality policies in place.

The data from 2025 shows a generally positive trend towards institutional commitment to gender equality, with the majority of partners having implemented a GEP alongside additional measures. However, the results also show that awareness and measures vary. A significant proportion of respondents are unaware of the existence of a wider gender equality policy and a small minority have no formal policy at all. These findings indicate both progress and remaining gaps and

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emphasize the need for continued support and awareness-raising to ensure comprehensive and inclusive gender equality policies across all partner institutions.

Compared to the 2024 data collection, these results reinforce the trends observed in the 2024 data collection and reflect a sustained institutional commitment to gender equality. **As of the first semester of 2025, 93% (n=38) of respondent partners are mainstreaming gender equality into their institutional frameworks—either through GEPs, complementary policies, or both (see Fig. 6).**

Fig. 6 - The data gathering revealed that the majority of respondent partners have institutional-level policies to mainstream gender equality.

The **main challenges identified by partners in implementing gender equality measures** were resource constraints and limited internal expertise. Additionally, some partners reported difficulties in achieving gender balance during recruitment processes, particularly in specialized fields where the majority of applicants are men. Others noted that the implementation of gender equality policies is still in its early stages, with staff across institutions still becoming familiar with the requirements and practices. A few respondents also indicated that they did not feel sufficiently informed or qualified to provide input on this topic (Fig.7).

Fig. 7

In relation to the **overall alignment of GEPs and other gender equality policies**, the majority of respondent partners indicated that their **GEPs and other gender equality policies are either highly integrated and working effectively together, or that there is some integration, though areas for improvement remain**—this combined perspective accounts for 58% of responses (n = 22 out of 38; see Fig. 8).

Out of the 41 total responses received, two were marked as *n/a*. These partners reported having a gender equality policy (but not a GEP), yet selected the option “*Do not have a GEP or other gender equality policy*” instead of one of the four more appropriate options. For the purpose of data assessment, their responses have been marked as *n/a* to maintain objectivity in the evaluation.

Additionally, one partner who reported not having either a GEP or any other gender equality policy selected the option “*Well—there is some integration, but there are areas where improvement is needed*” (rather than “*Do not have a GEP or other gender equality policy.*”), which was not consistent with their stated status. Their response regarding overall alignment of GEP and other GE policies was excluded during data analysis to ensure accurate reflection the overall alignment of GEPs/ other gender equality policies.

As a result, a total of 38 responses were considered valid and included in the final analysis, representing the perception of the partners having a GEP/ other gender equality policy in place.

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Fig. 8

Regarding the **overall effectiveness of promoting gender equality in the workplace, the majority of respondents rated their institutions as either "somewhat effective" or "very effective."** (69%; n=28 out of 41 partners). The entire range of responses suggests that while significant progress has been made, there remains a need for continued efforts to ensure more uniform and comprehensive implementation of gender equality measures across all partner organisations (Fig.9).

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Fig.9

In terms of the **perceived impact of EU project participation on gender balance**, a majority of **respondents—22 out of 41 (54%)—indicated that being involved in the EU projects has positively contributed to promoting gender balance within their institutions** (Fig.10). This suggests that EU-funded initiatives, such as RESIST, can serve as effective drivers for institutional change by raising awareness, encouraging policy development, and fostering the integration of gender considerations into organisational practices. The data points to a growing recognition among partners of the value added by EU projects in supporting gender equality efforts. **However, the remaining responses, which did not indicate a perceived impact, also underline the need for ongoing engagement and clearer pathways to translate project participation into sustainable institutional outcomes.**

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Fig.10

Regarding **the provision of gender equality, diversity or inclusion training for staff involved in RESIST project**, the data indicate that the majority of staff have not received any such training (Fig.11). Several partners reported that general training sessions on gender equality are organized at the regional or institutional level, often as part of onboarding processes for new staff. For example, some institutions include a presentation of the gender equality policy in the standard orientation package, while others provide training through online platforms, offering accessible resources for personnel.

Although not all research groups host dedicated sessions independently, some encourage staff—particularly new researchers—to attend gender equality training offered within the RESIST project framework. This reflects a supportive approach to awareness-raising and knowledge transfer on gender-related policies and practices.

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Fig. 11

2.2 Evolution of gender composition of RESIST teams

To better understand and track progress on gender equality within the RESIST partners, updated data was collected to assess changes in gender representation across partner teams since the previous data collection cycle.

Out of 41 respondents, 9 partners indicated that the composition of their teams had changed since June 2024.

For these organisations, the core teams from July 2024 to January 2025 had the following gender composition: 46 women (62%) and 28 men (38%). No non-binary or trans individuals were reported, and no respondents selected 'prefer not to say' regarding sex or gender (Fig. 12). Therefore, **the trend identified in 2024, which highlighted the presence of balanced teams across RESIST partners in terms of gender representation, has been further confirmed by the first round of data collection in 2025.**

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Fig. 12

It was also reaffirmed that 3 of the 5 work package leaders are women (60%), further supporting the positive trend towards the increased participation of women in leadership roles.

B. Specific Part of the Framework

2.3 Gender equality in RESIST activities

The data show that 17 (41%) of the 41 respondent partners are actively conducting research as part of the project, confirming 2024 findings (Fig. 13).

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Fig. 13

Out of the 17 partners conducting research in RESIST, **13 (76%) reported somewhat or fully including gender considerations in their research activities** (Fig 14).

Fig. 14

The data also show that, out of the 13 partners who consider gender in their research activities, **5 (38%) go beyond and integrate the Gender+ dimension**. This suggests that while a majority of

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research partners are incorporating gender considerations, there is also recognition and adoption of a more intersectional approach, which addresses multiple dimensions of diversity and inequality beyond gender alone.

Strategies for embedding gender considerations in project activities prioritize ensuring diverse representation in decision-making processes, conducting gender assessments, and integrating gender from the outset of planning. These approaches are among the most frequently cited by respondents (Fig.15).

Fig.15

The **challenges related to integrating gender equality in project activities vary across partners**, such as ensuring representativeness both for stakeholders and the population involved in the project, reflect diverse gender perspectives and evaluating the gender sensitivity in the vulnerability of the population. Some partners mentioned that gender equality issues tend to fade into the background when project work needs to be delivered coupled with tendency for gender topics to be forgotten unless actively brought up in discussions, indicating a need for consistent awareness and action.

A significant challenge raised is the recruitment of underrepresented genders, particularly at the early stages of the project. The difficulty in attracting and retaining diverse talent is compounded by the lack of resources to ensure gender balance across all roles, leading to a workforce that may be disproportionately male.

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While some partners report no significant gender-related challenges, others highlight a gender bias in local stakeholders involved in the RESIST project, which further hinders achieving a balanced approach.

Lastly, specific actions, such as increasing the number of women entrepreneurs in fire prevention, were noted as an example of a targeted effort to address gender imbalances in certain areas.

Out of the 13 partners who integrate gender considerations in research activities, 4 reported they **address some of the challenges by:**

- ✓ improving coordination and management of human resources allocated to the project (ensure that allocation of personnel considers gender balance from the outset);
- ✓ women’s empowerment through targeted involvement in workshops and activities (proactively invite and support specific women experts or stakeholders to participate in events).

Partners that do not include gender considerations in the RESIST project activities, cited the following reasons:

- ✓ gender equality measures are embedded in their general recruitment policies rather than tailored to individual projects;
- ✓ they have not yet identified a need to integrate gender considerations into their current activities;
- ✓ one respondent indicated they were not the appropriate person to answer this question and thus did not know.

These responses point to potential gaps in role clarity, perceived relevance, and awareness—areas that may benefit from targeted guidance and capacity-building.

When asked about **training on mainstreaming gender equality in research**, most partners declared they have not received any training (83%; n=34 out of 41 answers – Fig.16).

Fig. 16

Partners who received training reported participation in both RESIST-organized and institution-provided activities. These included workshops and webinars on gender equality, diversity, and inclusion—mandatory for managers and strongly encouraged for all staff. For example, approximately 30% of staff from one organization attended a workshop specifically addressing gender equality challenges in research projects, while discussions in other organizations often involved personnel from other ongoing projects.

Respondents noted that the sessions conducted within the RESIST framework were particularly effective in raising awareness of gender, diversity, and inclusion issues, thereby fostering a deeper understanding of how to integrate gender considerations into their work.

Respondents expressed interest in additional workshops on gender equality, diversity, and inclusion, as well as more comprehensive guidelines to better integrate gender considerations into research and project activities (Fig. 17).

Fig. 17

The survey also explored the **usefulness of the updated Checklist for organising inclusive stakeholders meetings (Checklist) and updated Repository for gender equality and ethics (Repository)** both shared at the end of January 2025, as a follow-up to the 2024 data gathering.

The data revealed that some of the partners have actively engaged with the provided internal resources. Specifically, out of the 41 respondent partners, 6 partners (14%) have consulted the updated Checklist, while 4 partners (10%) deemed it not relevant. Additionally, 22 partners (54%)

indicated plans to consult the updated Checklist in the future. Similarly, 5 partners (12%) have already accessed the updated Repository, with 2 partners (5%) reporting it as not relevant. Once again, 22 partners (54%) plan to utilize the updated Repository going forward.

It is important to note that the updated resources were shared at the end of January 2025, and the data gathering cycle started on February 12, 2025. Given this timeline, there was limited opportunity for partners to consult the materials before completing the survey. This factor may have contributed to the high number of partners planning to engage with the resources in the near future.

However, these findings suggest a significant opportunity to strengthen the integration of gender considerations into research activities. The clear interest in future consultation of these resources highlights the need for more guidance and awareness raising to support partners in incorporating gender equality into their work effectively.

2.4 Exploring gender equality trends in the context of AI and NBS within the RESIST project

Following the 2024 data gathering, the gender equality questionnaire was revised to deepen its focus on research activities. Two new dimensions—the gendered implications of AI applications and the integration of NBS—were added to capture emerging areas of concern. The findings presented below reflect partner responses to these new sections and illustrate how gender considerations are being addressed in these cutting-edge domains.

The **use of AI in the RESIST** project remains limited, with **only 8 out of 41 partners (20%) reporting its use**. Within the project, the AI is primarily used for tasks automation and data analysis (Fig. 18). The survey revealed that partners identified potential gender implications only in relation to AI-generated language versions, with no other connections to broader gender equality issues identified. This limited recognition suggests a lack of awareness regarding intersectional biases in AI and multilingual applications, highlighting the need for targeted guidance on how AI-driven processes can differentially impact gender groups.

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Fig. 18

Out of the 41 respondent partners, 12 (29%) reported **developing NBS in the RESIST project** (Fig. 19).

Fig. 19

To integrate gender considerations into the NBS, most partners reported implementing the following measures: ensuring equal access to NBS benefits, using gender-sensitive

communication strategies and including women and marginalized groups in decision-making processes (Fig. 20).

Fig. 20

3 Conclusions

In comparison to the 2024 data collection, **engagement rose by 5%**, increasing from 68% (n=38 out of 56 partners) to 73% (n=41 out of 56 partners) in 2025. This positive trend reflects the impact of awareness-raising efforts among partners regarding the importance of gender considerations. Coupled with the positive perception of EU project participation contributing to improved gender balance among RESIST partners (54% – 22 out of 41 partners), this momentum presents a valuable opportunity. It is therefore important to maintain and expand dedicated initiatives that further support meaningful gender integration across the project.

The data collection conducted in the first semester of 2025 confirms the commitment of RESIST partners to advancing gender equality at the institutional level (general part of the Framework). This is primarily evidenced by the widespread adoption of GEPs and related policies, with **93% (38 out of 41 partners)** reporting the implementation of such frameworks.

Among these 38 partners, 58% (22 partners) indicated a good perceived overall alignment between their GEPs and other gender equality policies, while 69% (28 out of 41 respondents) reported positive perceptions regarding the overall effectiveness of gender equality promotion within their workplaces.

Additionally, even among partners without formal GEPs or related policies, there is a clear effort to foster gender awareness. This includes encouraging staff participation in gender equality training—both internal and those offered by the project. Also, many partners are actively maintaining gender parity and upholding respect for all genders as part of their organizational culture. Several partners collaborate with sister projects to exchange practices and reinforce collective progress.

Further, the data revealed that **some RESIST partners are adopting a multi-dimensional approach to gender mainstreaming by combining structural reforms, educational programs, and procedural changes**. These efforts align with EC requirements and provide a valuable source of inspiration for the wider consortium. Sharing and building on these tailored approaches can help foster a stronger, more inclusive culture across all partner institutions.

Key challenges identified:

- **a relatively low proportion of partners explicitly address gender integration in research in their GEPs**—an important thematic area recommended by the EC: only 52% (17 out of 33 partners with a GEP) include gender considerations in research within their plans; among these, 76% (13 partners) apply a generic rather than field-specific approach, highlighting the

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need for more tailored and context-sensitive strategies to strengthen gender integration in research;

- **resource and expertise constraints:** limited institutional resources and a lack of in-house gender expertise were frequently cited; this is reflected in a notable number of “don’t know” responses to various questions across the survey, pointing to uncertainty or insufficient information;
- **male-dominated research fields:** persistent gender imbalances in certain research disciplines continue to pose structural barriers;
- **training gaps:** while induction-level training is common, there is a lack of advanced or ongoing provision of gender equality training;
- **limited gender equality reporting:** among the 17 partners who include gender considerations in research through their GEPs, only one reports on gender equality at the institutional level.

The data on the evolving gender composition of RESIST teams **confirms that gender balance is being achieved both within team structures and leadership positions**, contributing to a more inclusive research environment.

At the level of research activities (specific part of the Framework), the first-round of 2025 data collection confirmed trends observed in 2024: of the 41 respondents, 41% (17 partners) are conducting research within RESIST. Among them, 76% (n=13 partners) report incorporating gender considerations into their research activities, and 38% (n=5 partners) of these are adopting a Gender+ approach that addresses multiple dimensions of diversity and inequality.

Despite this progress, several **challenges** persist. Some partners reported difficulties in recruiting underrepresented genders, achieving gender balance in project roles, and ensuring meaningful gender representation among stakeholders and target populations. Additionally, evaluating the gender sensitivity of vulnerability assessments remains complex. A recurring concern is that gender issues are often overlooked unless intentionally raised, highlighting the need for consistent attention and integration.

To address these challenges, **some partners shared specific strategies**—such as gender-sensitive resource allocation and targeted inclusion of women in project activities—which serve as valuable inspiration across the RESIST consortium.

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While 83% of partners have not received training on gender mainstreaming in research, those who did attend RESIST- or institution-organized sessions found them effective in raising awareness. There is **strong interest in further training and clearer, practical guidance**. Partners also emphasized the importance of **maintaining visibility of gender equality topic at the consortium level**, suggesting regular prompts in meetings and internal communications.

Uptake of the updated Checklist for Inclusive Stakeholder Meetings and the Repository on Gender Equality and Ethics—shared in late January 2025—has been limited so far. However, many partners indicated plans to consult these resources in the near future, which suggests promising potential for increased integration going forward.

The updated gender equality questionnaire introduced two new focus areas: the gendered implications of AI applications and NBS.

Findings show limited **AI use (20% of partners)**, with gender considerations largely confined to issues around multilingual outputs. This indicates a broader gap in awareness of how AI systems can embed or amplify gender biases.

Meanwhile, **29% of partners are engaging with NBS**, with many reporting efforts to ensure gender-sensitive communication, equitable access to benefits, and the inclusion of women and marginalized groups in related decision-making processes.

In conclusion, the **findings from the first round of 2025 data-gathering campaign conducted between M26 and M28 (2025) confirm the ongoing need to continue implementing the Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework**, particularly as a means to monitor gender equality trends and identify challenges across RESIST activities—ultimately supporting more effective gender mainstreaming throughout the project.

Moving forward, the insights gathered will inform future developments and guide the necessary next steps for the tailored implementation of the Framework, as well as the objectives for the next round of data collection on gender equality (2025 – 2nd semester).

In 2025, priority will be given notably to:

- maintain and expand dedicated initiatives that further support meaningful gender integration across the project;
- maintaining visibility of gender equality topic at the consortium level; for this, work package meetings, EB meetings, and other gatherings should be used to regularly consult the centralized gender equality repository and resources to stay updated on the latest guidance.

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4 Recommendations

The **recommendations shared in the Gender Equality annotated aggregated data 2024 are being reaffirmed by the latest findings**, indicating continuity in key trends and persisting challenges. This consistency suggests that the priority areas identified—such as the need for capacity-building and tailored guidance on gender integration in research—remain highly relevant. It also highlights the importance of sustained efforts to implement these recommendations through concrete actions, including training, updated tools, and regular monitoring.

In light of these findings, more **specific recommendations for partner organisations** based on the 2025 first-semester data collection include:

- **embedding gender equality prompts and discussions in internal communications** to ensure gender considerations remain visible and actively addressed across all project activities;
- **providing training sessions on gender mainstreaming in research**, with special attention to intersectional (Gender+) approaches and emerging areas, such as AI and NBS.

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6.5 Annex 5: Repository for gender equality and ethics in climate change research and innovation projects, updated version 2025

Repository for gender equality and ethics in climate change research and innovation projects

Updated Edition / January 2025

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Introduction

Climate change represents one of the most pressing challenges of our time. Concerted efforts are needed in research and innovation to mitigate and adapt to its inevitable consequences. In this turbulent context for science and technology advancement, ethical considerations and gender inclusivity emerge among primary requirements for efficiency and justice in climate change projects. The different needs of individuals, their inequalities, and the specific knowledge that can contribute to solutions need to be considered to ensure equitable outcomes and respect for all actors involved, regardless of their gender identity and sociocultural background.

EU-funded Research and Innovation projects are governed by ethical principles, which establish a framework to conduct, disseminate, and apply the findings of the research, with justice and fairness. Integrating gender perspectives in the climate change projects implies acknowledging the unique needs and vulnerabilities of women and individuals of gender minorities, as well as offering the opportunity to share experiences and participate in the decision-making processes. Embracing the inclusive approach ensures that research methodology takes into consideration the variety of the society, thus leading to more robust and nuanced outcomes.

The concept

This repository, centralizing relevant completed deliverables from RESIST project, mandatory and key documents, guidelines as well as various tools in one central location, essentially functions as a handbook for the project.

The repository is a living document that will be updated regularly. It is meant to serve as support for the conception, implementation and monitoring of inclusive and ethical dimensions in climate change research and innovation projects.

The repository supplements the following resources:

- [RESIST Project Handbook](#)

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- RESIST Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework
- RESIST Ethics and Gender monitoring tool
- RESIST Ethics HelpDesk
- Personal data:
 - RESIST Ethics and data protection decision tree
 - RESIST Ethics and data protection
- Artificial Intelligence
 - Ethics By Design and Ethics of Use Approaches for Artificial Intelligence
 - Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI
 - Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI)
- Inclusive communication:
 - RESIST_Checklist for Including the Gender Dimension in Research
 - RESIST_Gender Sensitive and Inclusive Communication Guidelines
 - RESIST_Inclusive communications Checklist for Social Media Posts
 - RESIST_Checklist for Organising Inclusive Stakeholders Meetings

The repository is divided into two sections, covering (I) **gender mainstreaming and inclusiveness** and (II) **ethics**. Both sections contain:

- mandatory and key documents that the beneficiaries must observe when conducting the activities under the project;
- relevant guidelines and
- selected tools.

The **first edition of this report** was shared with the project partners in 2024. This updated version incorporates new resources on **topics such as the use of AI, engaging vulnerable populations in addressing climate change, communicating on climate change, integrating gender equality into research and nature-based solutions**. These additions were made in response to the needs identified by during the data-gathering campaigns conducted in 2024, as documented in **RESIST_Ethics Compliance_Annotated Aggregated Data_2024** and **RESIST_Gender Equality_Annotated Aggregated Data_2024**.

To continue raising awareness and building the capacity of project partners on key topics related to gender equality and ethics, a **newsletter** will be launched in 2025. The newsletter will provide regular

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updates tailored to support the progress of ongoing project activities, ensuring partners receive timely and relevant information while maintaining momentum on these important issues.

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1 Gender equality mainstreaming and inclusiveness in climate change projects

1.1 Framework

The **RESIST Grant Agreement** requires beneficiaries to actively promote equal opportunities between individuals in implementing actions. This entails adhering to a gender equality plan where applicable. The beneficiaries must strive for gender balance across all personnel levels involved in the action, including supervisory and managerial positions.

In 2021, the European Commission and the Council emphasized the importance of prioritizing gender equality in research and innovation through the **Ljubljana Declaration on Gender Equality in Research and Innovation**. This declaration underscored the need for concerted efforts to address gender disparities and ensure equal opportunities for all genders in research and innovation. Alongside this effort, the **EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020 – 2025**, and **EU LGBTIQ Equality Strategy 2020 – 2025** provide comprehensive frameworks for advancing gender equality and the rights of lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, intersex, and queer (LGBTIQ) individuals across Europe. These strategies aim at promoting diversity, combating discrimination, and fostering inclusive environments in society.

The Council of Europe's work in the area of gender equality is reflected in several key initiatives, including the **Gender Mainstreaming Toolkit** and the free **new online training course on gender equality and gender mainstreaming**.

In line with these documents, **RESIST Gender Equality Framework** goes beyond gender equality and strives to apply an intersectional approach considering diversity factors such as age, disability, socio-economic backgrounds, religion, ethnicity, urban/rural that can be considered amplifying existing vulnerabilities to climate change related disasters. Using an intersectional framework to identify vulnerabilities to climate change impacts on local populations and using the findings can help design a robust gender-responsive climate action.

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1.2 Guiding principles to achieve gender-responsive climate action

Principle	Comments
Project team : social and gender experts (not only technical experts on climate actions)	Involve men, women and individuals from other gender identities in the project (both technical and social experts) to incorporate social and human rights dimension in the research project.
Involve more individuals, including women, on the ground, both in consultation (to build and incorporate their skills and knowledge) and in implementation of climate research	What are the needs and contributions of various gender minorities and women? Provide opportunities for improving health, education and livelihoods. From the initial phases of the project, involve all individuals in discussions and analyse their roles and responsibilities such that they will be able to benefit from the project as participants.
Leadership & participation of women and gender diverse individuals in the decision-making process	Effective participation of women and gender diverse individuals in all levels of the decision-making process is paramount to ensure inclusive climate change policies / programs.
Capacity building , knowledge-sharing and the communication of activities undertaken to enhance gender-responsive climate action and its impacts in advancing women's and gender diverse individuals' leadership	Develop gender-sensitive training / educational programs to ensure effective women's and gender diverse individuals' access to and participation in the projects.
Monitoring & reporting	Monitor, collect and publish gender-disaggregated data regularly. Undertake gender-analysis of climate change policies, programs, projects etc.

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1.3 Resources

The resources below contain information about the relevance of gender in climate change, how to integrate gender into research (staff and content), how to mainstream gender throughout the project cycle, how to ensure inclusive communication and monitoring, as well as trainings and practical examples. The information is organized in chronological order.

Many of the resources cover the African countries and are produced by different agencies / programs of the UN in cooperation with independent experts. They usually contain a theoretical section and an appendix with relevant other resources. These resources should be considered as a reference and guidance in climate change projects.

The information is structured in 3 chapters:

- Guidelines / Toolkits / Manuals
- Trainings
- Action plans

1.3.1 Guidelines / Toolkits / Manuals

TITLE	DESCRIPTION	YEAR / ORGANIZATION
<p>EU Toolkit Gender in EU-funded research</p>	<p>The Toolkit provides the research community with practical guidance on how to integrate gender into research (staff and content):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • an overall introduction to gender equality in research (definitions & concepts, legal basis) • how to make research gender-sensitive <p>Topics covered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • health • food, agriculture and biotechnology • nanosciences, materials and new production technologies • energy • environment • transport • socio-economic sciences and humanities • science in society • specific activities of international cooperation 	<p>2011 / EU</p>

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<p>Guide on gender mainstreaming in energy and climate change projects</p>	<p>The Guide is intended to help UNIDO's staff, national and local counter-parts, agencies, international and private-sector partners, and individual experts involved in energy and climate change interventions to apply a gender perspective to their work and, more specifically, to mainstream gender throughout the project cycle.</p>	<p>2014 / UNIDO</p>
<p>Guide on Gender Mainstreaming in environmental management projects</p>	<p>The Guide is intended to help UNIDO's staff, national and local counter-parts, agencies, international and private-sector partners, and individual experts involved in environmental management interventions to apply a gender perspective to their work and, more specifically, to mainstream gender throughout the project cycle.</p>	<p>2015 / UNIDO</p>
<p>Gender in environment and climate change</p>	<p>The publication gathers information about the relevance of gender in climate protection policies (specifically in the design and implementation of adaptation and mitigation strategies as responses to climate change), the main issues, the policy objectives and cycles and provides several practical examples.</p>	<p>2016 / EIGE</p>
<p>Sex and Gender Equity in Research: rationale for the SAGER guidelines and recommended use <i>(general application)</i></p>	<p>This article describes the rationale for an international set of guidelines to encourage a more systematic approach to the reporting of sex and gender in research across disciplines.</p>	<p>2016 / Heidari, S., Babor, T.F., De Castro, P. et al.</p>
<p>Mainstreaming Gender in Green Climate Fund Projects</p>	<p>A practical manual to support the integration of gender equality in climate change interventions and climate finance and to support in-country partners to enhance their capacity to address gender concerns in the climate change space.</p>	<p>2017 / GCF – UN Women</p>
<p>Gender and Environment: Support Kit for UN Environment Staff</p>	<p>The kit aims to explain the relevance of gender in the UN Environment's 7 priority areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • climate change • resilience to disasters and conflicts • healthy and productive ecosystems • environmental governance • chemicals, waste and air quality • resource efficiency • environment under review 	<p>2017 / UN Environment</p>

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	<p>The publication provides entry points for integration of gender in project cycle activities and communications; it also aims to provide practical guidance for strengthening gender considerations within UN Environment’s work.</p> <p>The annexes provide definitions of terminology, and further support on mainstreaming gender in project design and inclusive communications.</p>	
<p>Guidelines in Mainstreaming Gender in Climate Change National and Sectoral Adaptation Plans for Monitoring & Evaluation and Planning Staff</p>	<p>The publication aims to enhance capacities in effective gender-responsive planning, monitoring and evaluation and offers concrete guidance on how sectoral and national staff of government entities can comprehensively and explicitly integrate gender perspectives in their programming activities</p> <p>Topics covered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • concepts • steps of gender mainstreaming programme activities • checklists • monitoring & evaluation • Indicators 	<p>2018 / UNDP</p>
<p>Toolbox: How to Mainstream Gender in Environmental Policy</p>	<p>The Toolbox has been developed to assist the Ministry of Environmental Protection of Serbia in integrating gender equality considerations into various sectoral programmes and policies. It provides a practical and workable approach to gender mainstreaming in environmental policy. It has been applied to two programmes chosen by the Ministry of Environmental Protection: the National Waste Prevention Programme for the period 2020-2025 and the Roadmap for circular economy in Serbia. Although the two programmes were used to exemplify the approach during a training session, the toolbox can be applied to any other sector of environmental policy, possibly during thematic workshops, involving the experts in charge of developing a specific programme or policy and internal or external experts on gender.</p>	<p>2021 / UNECE</p>
<p>U.S. Climate Resilience Toolkit</p>	<p>This Toolkit provides resources for assessing and managing climate-related risks and to help them make their communities and businesses more resilient to extreme events. It offers tools and case studies to ensure diverse voices are represented in addressing climate risks, promoting</p>	<p>2021 / U.S. federal government</p>

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	<p>solutions tailored to local needs and resources. Strategies include fostering partnerships, using accessible communication methods, and integrating social and cultural considerations into decision-making.</p>	
<p>Guide to integrate gender and climate action</p>	<p>The guide aims to assist policymakers and practitioners across the Commonwealth to integrate gender equality into national climate action.</p> <p>Topics covered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • policy alignment and clarity of intent • financing gender expertise and gender budgeting • skills for a gender-just transition • evidencing a gender-just transition • institutional collaboration. <p>Each section covers practical steps to facilitate the integration of gender into countries' NDCs, including guiding questions and tips for resolving common hurdles, along with a wide range of examples of best practices from across the Commonwealth to support learning and knowledge-sharing.</p>	<p>2022 / The Commonwealth</p>
<p>The gender equality and environment intersection</p>	<p>This paper presents a preliminary overview of OECD Development Assistance Committee (DAC) members' policy frameworks and financing efforts to address the challenges at the intersection of climate change, environmental degradation, biodiversity loss and gender inequality. It reviews existing research and evidence and explores knowledge gaps in this field. It aims to establish a baseline and to foster exchange that can help DAC members tackle these issues in a more effective and holistic manner.</p> <p>It includes a list of relevant resources.</p>	<p>2023 / OECD</p>
<p>Toolkit for Mainstreaming and Implementing Gender Equality 2023 (general application)</p>	<p>The Toolkit is a practical resource to help governments, parliaments and judiciaries implement the OECD Recommendation on Gender Equality in Public Life. It contains self-assessment tools to guide governments and other decision-making institutions in assessing the strengths and weaknesses of their policies, mechanisms, and frameworks for gender equality, and in setting priorities for improvement, as well as examples of good practices. The Toolkit highlights a range of possible actions to take and</p>	<p>2023 / OECD</p>

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	pitfalls to avoid in implementing the various provisions of the Recommendation.	
Communicating on Climate Change	The article provides tips on how to educate and mobilize audiences to take action in confronting the climate crisis. Everyone can play a part by raising their voice, sharing solutions, and advocating for change – shaped by different experiences, cultural contexts, and underlying values. When creating a communications product – such as a video, a podcast, a written article, or a graphic on climate change – the tips will help make it a valuable, effective, and reliable piece of content.	UN
ALBA Guidelines: Designing inclusive forms for gender and sexual diversity	This guideline aims to set out best practices for improving the inclusion of LGBTQIA+ (Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans, Queer/Questioning, Intersex, Asexual and other identities) people, that is, individuals with varying genders, sexualities, and transgender and intersex people. The guidelines are applicable to any setting in which such identities are surveyed, and it is recommended they are used for conference registration forms, HR surveys and demographic surveys for human participants in research projects . The goal is to help anyone unfamiliar with these identities improve their forms or surveys to more accurately capture these individuals.	2024 / ALBA Network
Inclusive Forms	This guideline ensures that all communication with community members is inclusive, respectful, and mindful of their wellbeing and diversity.	The University of British Columbia
Gender Equality Action Plans	This factsheet provides information on creating and implementing a GEP. Gender equality plans in academia and research: roadmap to effective implementation	2024 / EIGE
Mainstreaming Gender Equality and Social Inclusion in Nature-Based Solutions for Climate Change Adaptation	This technical report offers contextual information, tools, and recommendations to help plan, design, and implement nature-based solutions (NBS) for adaptation that advance gender equality and social inclusion while enhancing resilience, biodiversity, and ecosystem integrity.	2024/ IISD

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1.3.2 Trainings

TITLE	DESCRIPTION	YEAR / ORGANIZATION
Resources and training opportunities	<p>The page contains information on available capacity-building resources and training opportunities on climate finance in general, and gender-responsive climate finance in particular.</p> <p>Ex:</p> <p>Gender mainstreaming in adaptation projects and programmes</p> <p>Women in technology for climate action resource</p>	UNCC
Gender and Climate Change Training Module	<p>UNDP presents updated versions of 12 training modules and issue briefs on gender dimensions of climate change covering a range of themes and sectors. These resources include a general overview and discussions on adaptation and disaster risk reduction, agriculture and food security, sustainable energy, climate finance, and REDD+ under the new development and climate change frameworks, such as the 2030 Agenda and the Paris Agreement. These knowledge products are designed to build capacity in member countries with respect to gender and climate change within the context of sustainable development.</p>	2017 / UNDP
Mainstreaming Gender-Environment and Climate Change Nexus in Sectors' Policy, Planning and Budgeting Agriculture, Energy, Industry and Urbanization - Integrated Training Manual	<p>The Manual builds on several existing policies, reports and manuals on gender equality and gender mainstreaming in environment and climate change; the training manual aims to enhance the knowledge and gender mainstreaming skills in in policy cycle, including gender analysis and the integration of gender –environment nexus into the design, planning and budgeting of high-priority sectors interventions for environment and climate change; this manual is particularly relevant for environment and natural resources-related interventions and practices that seek to promote participation and reduce the inequality that exists between natural resources-dependent women and men, especially among the poor or marginalized people living in rural areas.</p> <p>It covers various concepts, policies and exercises.</p>	2019 / Rwanda Environment and Management Authority through the Poverty-Environment Action - UNDP
Gender in climate action Training Pack	<p>The resource helps climate and development professionals to integrate gender perspectives into climate projects and programmes</p>	2023 / CDKN Global

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	<p>The pack contains presentations and exercises to help climate and development professionals to integrate gender perspectives into climate projects and programmes. Specifically, the training aims to help participants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • understand internationally accepted and widely committed frameworks for gender equality in development and climate action • understand why gender and social inclusion are relevant to climate policies, programmes and activities • learn how to think critically about gender and social inclusion issues throughout a typical programme / project cycle, from the design and consultation stages, through planning, budgeting, delivery and monitoring and evaluation • appreciate how gender-responsive and socially-inclusive approaches increase the effectiveness and sustainability of climate action; and how gender-blind approaches undermine the effectiveness of climate action • learn about tried, tested and recommended tools for identifying and addressing gender- and social inclusion-related concerns and be able to apply them, through guided group work and practice • learn how to set outcomes, targets and indicators for gender-equitable, socially inclusive outcomes and how to develop budgets to ensure that activities achieve these outcomes • learn from the experiences of other practitioners, providing best practice examples and enabling participants to share knowledge and experience with each other. 	
<p>Training course 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and Gender Equality</p>	<p>The course serves as an introduction for beginners in the area of gender equality; it can help gender equality advocates to position and contextualize their work within the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development; and it can assist practitioners working on other SDGs, beyond SDG 5 on gender equality, begin to understand how gender equality is related to their work, identify what the entry points for promoting gender equality are, and how gender equality is integrated into the measurement criteria for the achievement of a particular SDG and its targets.</p> <p>Modules:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The history and scope of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and the interlinkages with gender equality including through the Leave No One Behind framework 	<p>UN Woman</p>

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How and why gender equality is integrated across the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and the SDGs • The arguments for gender equality and how it relates to each of the 17 SDGs • Gender equality and 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development targets and indicators • The way forward including through stakeholder engagement and ideas and examples of good practice. 	
<p>Online webinar: Engaging vulnerable groups in building resilient futures</p>	<p>This webinar is a joint initiative of FUTURESILIENCE, R4C and ACCTING. It aims to raise awareness on the importance of involving vulnerable populations in the framing and design of policies and activities to build resilience. It provides practical insights on how to involve these stakeholders while considering intersectionality and gender+ equality, ultimately contributing to the development of resilient societies.</p>	<p>2024 / EU – ACCTING/ FUTURESILIENCE R4C</p>

1.3.3 Action Plans

This section provides concrete examples of gender action plans that can serve as a source of inspiration.

TITLE	DESCRIPTION	YEAR / ORGANIZATION
<p>Gender Action Plan</p>	<p>The enhanced gender action plan sets out objectives and activities under five priority areas that aim to advance knowledge and understanding of gender-responsive climate action and its coherent mainstreaming in the implementation of the UNFCCC and the work of Parties, the secretariat, United Nations entities and all stakeholders at all levels, as well as women’s full, equal and meaningful participation in the UNFCCC process.</p> <p>Summary</p>	<p>2019 / UN FCCC</p>
<p>UNECE Gender Action Plan</p>	<p>The UNECE Gender Action Plan serves as a roadmap for advancing gender equality and empowering women in the UNECE region through targeted interventions and collaborative initiatives.</p> <p>The action plan guides all UNECE subprogrammes, including the Environment subprogramme. The gender dimension is incorporated into several programmes under the Environment Division. While promoting and raising</p>	<p>2020 / UNECE</p>

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	<p>awareness of the importance of taking gender perspectives into account is a key objective, many programmes go well beyond awareness-raising and are mainstreaming gender issues in the development of environmental policies.</p>	
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**Information on gender mainstreaming in more specialized areas of action (water, energy, waste management, development of warning systems and other technologies etc.) is available and accessible online. Please contact ESF for further support in case you need more specific information.*

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2 Ethics in climate change projects

2.1 Framework

The legal basis outlined in Article 14 of the **RESIST Grant Agreement** emphasizes the necessity for actions to adhere to the highest ethical standards and relevant EU, international, and national laws. This includes compliance with ethical principles, research integrity, and various legal frameworks protecting human rights, privacy, non-discrimination, environmental protection, and health for each beneficiary.

Additionally, the **European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity** must be followed by each beneficiary, ensuring reliability, honesty, respect, and accountability in their research practices. Ethical issues must be addressed in accordance with additional requirements by ethics panels, with necessary approvals obtained before undertaking tasks with ethical implications.

Article 18 of the **RESIST Grant Agreement** further underscores the importance of implementing principles related to recruitment, working conditions, transparent recruitment processes, and career development, as outlined in the **Commission Recommendation on the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers**, to ensure awareness and adherence among all researchers and participants involved in the action.

Consequently, RESIST project should foster an environment of transparency, fairness, and professional development for all researchers and participants involved by embedding a holistic approach to ethics and integrity, striving for responsibility and inclusivity throughout all activities.

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2.2 Guiding principles to ensure integrity of the climate change research

Principle	Comments
Transparency	The research process needs to be fully transparent in terms of methods, data sources, potential conflict of interests.
Inclusivity	Research should consider the diverse perspectives of people according to their gender, disability, ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation, socio-economic status and age.
Participation in research should be based on specific and informed consent	Processes need to be put in place to ensure that participants are informed and understand the project, the purpose, and that their participation is voluntary.
Minimize personal and social harm	For research participants, procedures need to ensure that stress and sensitivities be minimized. Safety needs to be guaranteed for the researchers.
Interdisciplinarity	Climate change is a complex topic that involves an interdisciplinary approach. Researchers should cooperate with experts from social, economical, and policy fields to develop comprehensive solutions.
Reduce environmental harm	Researchers should do their best to reduce environmental impact and use sustainable practices, whenever possible.
Dissemination	Have a clear dissemination strategy on how findings will be brought to the attention of the relevant stakeholder.

2.3 Resources

The resources provided below offer valuable insights into the significance of ethics, codes of ethics, ethical issues, and methods for evaluating and managing the ethical aspects of EU-funded projects. They also outline ethical principles that should guide project implementation.

The information is organized in chronological order.

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Many of the resources do not specifically focus on climate change research but cover broader ethical principles that apply to all research endeavours. They usually contain an appendix with other relevant resources.

The information is structured in 5 chapters:

- mandatory documents
- key documents
- EU Guidelines
- guidelines
- action plans

2.3.1 Mandatory documents

TITLE	DESCRIPTION	ORGANIZATION / YEAR
<p>Commission Recommendation 2005/251/EC of 11 March 2005 on the European Charter for Researchers and on a Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers (OJ L 75, 22.3.2005, p. 67).</p>	<p>When carrying out activities under the project, beneficiaries must adhere to the set of principles established in the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers.</p> <p>The Charter & Code are key elements of the European Union policy for making research an attractive career and stimulating economic growth and employment in Europe.</p> <p>The European Charter for Researchers is a set of general principles and requirements which specifies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ the roles, ▪ responsibilities and ▪ entitlements <p>of researchers as well as of employers and/or funding bodies of researchers. It constitutes a framework for researchers, employers and funders which invites them to act responsibly and as professionals within their working environment, and to recognise each other as such.</p> <p>The Code of Conduct for the recruitment of researchers consists of a set of general principles</p>	<p>2005 / EU</p>

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	<p>and requirements that should be followed by employers and/or funders when appointing or recruiting researchers. These principles and requirements are complementary to those outlined in the European Charter for Researchers. Institutions and employers adhering to the Code of Conduct will openly demonstrate their commitment to act in a responsible and respectable way and to provide fair working conditions to researchers, with a clear intention to contribute to the advancement of the European Research Area.</p> <p>The Charter and the Code contain 40 principles and general conditions which are structured on four dimensions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) ethical and professional issues; (2) recruitment; (3) working conditions and social security; (4) training. <p>To support the research institutions adopting the Charter and Code principles, the Commission has set out a strengthened procedure through which those institutions interested in including them, could design their Human Resources (HR) Strategy.</p>	
<p>The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA Code)</p> <p><i>(Respect of this code is a requirement as per the Article 14 of the GA)</i></p>	<p>The primary purpose of the ALLEA Code is to help preserving the trustworthiness of the research system and its results and to serve the research community as a framework for self-regulation.</p> <p>In the 2024 revised edition of the AGA - Annotated Grant Agreement (pg. 338), the ALLEA Code and SOPs4RI (mentioned below) are specifically referenced:</p> <p><i>“In order to meet the highest standards of research integrity, the beneficiaries must follow the principles listed in this provision and ensure that the persons carrying out research tasks comply with the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (i.e. follow the good research practices listed in this Code and refrain from any research integrity violations it describes).</i></p>	<p>2023 / ALLEA</p>

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	<p><i>They also must ensure that appropriate procedures, policies and structures are in place to foster responsible research practices, to prevent questionable research practices and research misconduct, and to handle allegations of breaches of the principles and standards in the Code of Conduct (see Guidelines for Promoting Research Integrity in Research Performing Organisation).</i></p>	
<p>Guideline for Promoting Research Integrity in Research Performing Organisations</p>	<p>This document describes the appropriate procedures, policies and structures that were declared at proposal stage by the coordinator to be “in place to foster responsible research practices, to prevent questionable research practices and research misconduct, and to handle allegations of breaches of the principles and standards in the [ALLEA] Code of Conduct”, and confirmed as correct by each partner in RESIST during the Grant Agreement Preparation.</p> <p>In the 2024 revised edition of the AGA - Annotated Grant Agreement (pg. 338), the SOPs4RI is specifically referenced, along with the ALLEA Code (as mentioned above).</p>	<p>SOPs4RI consortium</p>
<p>The EU AI Act</p>	<p>The AI Act is the first-ever comprehensive legal framework on AI worldwide. The aim of the new rules is to foster trustworthy AI in Europe and beyond, by ensuring that AI systems respect fundamental rights, safety, and ethical principles and by addressing risks of very powerful and impactful AI models.</p> <p>The AI Act is part of a wider package of policy measures to support the development of trustworthy AI. These measures guarantee the safety and fundamental rights of people and businesses when it comes to AI. They also strengthen uptake, investment and innovation in AI across the EU.</p> <p>Tool to interpret the AI act.</p>	<p>2024 / EU</p>
<p>The Framework Convention on Artificial Intelligence</p>	<p>The Convention aims to ensure that activities within the lifecycle of artificial intelligence systems are fully consistent with human rights, democracy and the rule of law, while being conducive to technological progress and innovation.</p>	<p>2024 / Council of Europe</p>

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2.3.2 Key documents

TITLE	DESCRIPTION	ORGANIZATION / YEAR
Declaration of Ethical Principles in relation to Climate Change	This Declaration sets out a shortlist of the globally agreed ethical principles that should guide decision-making, policy-making and other actors involved in actions related to climate change and help mobilize people to address climate change.	2017 / UNESCO
Code of Ethics & Professional Standards of Conduct	This document aims to serve as an aspirational model for climate change professionals globally, regardless of job function, cultural differences, or local laws and regulations.	2018 / ACCO
The Declaration of Helsinki	<p>A statement of ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects, including research on identifiable human material and data.</p> <p>While the Declaration of Helsinki primarily pertains to medical research involving human subjects, its principles of ethical conduct, respect for participants' autonomy, and protection of their rights have broader implications and may inform ethical considerations in various fields, including climate change research.</p> <p>In climate change research, ethical considerations may arise regarding the treatment of human populations affected by environmental changes, the fair distribution of resources and burdens, and the potential impacts of research interventions on communities and ecosystems.</p>	2022 / WMA

2.3.3 EU Guidelines

TITLE	DESCRIPTION	YEAR / ORGANIZATION
Horizon Europe Program Guide	The guide contains information regarding the process to assess and address the ethical dimension of activities funded under Horizon	2023 / EU

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	<p>Europe Programme, from the conceptual stage of the proposal not only to respect the legal framework but also to enhance the quality of the research.</p> <p>More information can be found on the online platform.</p>	
<p>EU Grants: How to complete your ethics self-assessment</p>	<p>This guidance is designed to help applicants and beneficiaries of EU projects make the proposal ethics compliant.</p> <p>The guidance aims to help applicants to identify and deal with ethics issues that may arise from their project and provide help with filling out their application.</p> <p>This document covers most of the ethics issues that usually arise in EU projects and gives advice on dealing with classic cases.</p>	2021 / EU
<p>Identifying serious and complex ethics issues in EU-funded research</p>	<p>This Guidance note aims to guide those independent ethics experts with responsibility for screening proposals and identifying whether serious and complex ethics issues are likely to arise in the execution of those projects. This document is also designed to help applicants identify any such issues while preparing their proposals (and understand why their proposal may have been selected for an ethics assessment).</p>	2021 / EU
<p>Ethics in Horizon Europe</p>	<p>The document provides information and guidelines on how to proceed with ethics screening in in projects funded under Horizon Europe.</p>	2022 / EU
<p>Ethics Advisors and Ethics Advisory Boards Roles and Function in EU-funded Projects</p>	<p>This document aims to provide guidance on the roles and operation of Ethics Advisors (EAs) and Ethics Advisory Boards (EABs) appointed to monitor, guide and counsel EU-funded projects.</p> <p>The aim is to offer a focused and practical guidance for EAs and EABs in projects funded under Horizon Europe or any other EU Funding Programmes.</p>	2023 / EU

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	It includes a glossary .	
Annotated Grant Agreement	This document, published in May 2024, provides in-depth explanations and practical examples to help beneficiaries understand and implement the terms of their grants effectively. Ethics remains a central focus in Horizon Europe projects, with additional concrete examples provided.	2024/ EU

2.3.4 Guidelines

TITLE	DESCRIPTION	YEAR / ORGANIZATION
Research Ethics in Ethnography/ Anthropology	Section 1 in the paper deals with basic theoretical assumptions and methodology . Sections 2 and 3 establish the ethical principles by which all scientific research should be assessed. In section 4 those general ethical principles are applied to the 'special consideration' that needs to be given to ethnographic and anthropological research, given the nature of its theoretical assumptions and primary research methods.	2021 / EU
Ethics in Social Science and Humanities	This document aims to help researchers in social sciences and humanities (SSH) identify and address ethical dimensions when involved in research and innovation actions financed by the EU Framework Programme. It is also designed to help the wider research community deal with the ethical issues that may arise in interdisciplinary research using SSH methodology. Used together with other guidance documents provided by the European Commission, it should help you integrate research ethics in proposal preparation and in research.	2021 / EU
Guidance note — Research on	Research on refugees, asylum seekers and migrants concerns a particularly vulnerable	2021 / EU

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<p>refugees, asylum seekers and migrants</p>	<p>group which needs particular safeguards in terms of research ethics. This note provides some guidelines to help researchers make their research ethics compliant.</p>	
<p>RESIST SharePoint documents</p>	<p>RESIST SharePoint contains a series of documents: checklists, forms, guidelines to help partners in the project comply with and get information regarding ethics requirements.</p>	<p>2023 / RESIST Ethics HelpDesk</p>
<p>Ethics, climate change and health – a landscape review</p>	<p>This paper forms part of a larger WHO project designed to embed ethics in climate change health policy and practice, including all aspects of associated research. This review sketches out the current landscape regarding ethics, climate change and human health, including interventions—and research into interventions—aimed at both mitigating and adapting to its health-related impacts. This landscape review is divided into several parts: (i) the first discusses—briefly—the most up to date scientific literature regarding climate change as set out by the IPCC and includes a discussion of scientific uncertainty concerning climate stability; (ii) the second engages with identified and anticipated health impacts of climate change, relying on recent syntheses of the literature; (iii) the third section discusses the ethics of health and climate change with a focus on policy and implications for researchers and public health practitioners broadly understood; (iv) the final section discusses available ethical frameworks that can help inform practice</p>	<p>2023 / MSF, WHO</p>
<p>Ethical implications of the impact of our research on climate change</p>	<p>The webpage covers the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What to include in response to the question under 'Climate action and environmental impact' in the ethics process • Understanding the research partner or funder's approach • Reducing carbon emissions from research 	<p>University of Bath</p>

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Principles to follow 	
<p>Health, climate change and ethics – an overview</p>	<p>This paper is the outcome of a scoping exercise carried out by the Nuffield Council on Bioethics to identify ethical issues arising in climate change and health, including human actions designed to mitigate and adapt to climate change. It examines these ethical issues under three linked headings: the ethics of the climate crisis; ethical issues arising in responses to the climate crisis; and ethical issues relating to research into those responses.</p> <p>The paper seeks to take a step towards addressing that gap, highlighting the emerging ethical issues and splitting them into three linked themes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The broad ethics of the climate crisis, which includes asking what is owed to emerging, future and hypothetical generations? The ethical issues arising in mitigation and adaptation strategies, which includes challenging the perception of collective action and individual choice – If my individual actions make next to no difference, what moral obligations do I have to act? The issues relating to research into climate action, which includes emphasising the need for fairness throughout required cooperation from a range of national and international bodies. 	<p>2023 / Nuffield Council on Bioethics</p>
<p>Living guidelines on the responsible use of generative AI in research</p>	<p>The guidelines focus on one particular area of AI used in the research process, namely generative Artificial Intelligence. One of the goals of the guidelines is that the scientific community uses this technology in a responsible manner. The guidelines intend to set out common directions on the responsible use of generative AI. They have to be considered as a supporting tool for research funding bodies, research organisations and researchers, including the ones applying to the European Framework Programme for Research and Innovation.</p>	<p>2024 / EU</p>

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Ethical framework principles for climate intervention research	The framework provides guidance for ensuring: 1. Responsible research, 2. Climate justice, 3. Inclusive public participation, 4. Transparency, and 5. Informed governance.	AGU
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2.3.5 Action Plans

This section provides concrete examples of ethical framework that can serve as a source of inspiration.

TITLE	DESCRIPTION	YEAR / ORGANIZATION
University of Bath Climate Action Framework principles	The Climate Action Framework has eleven principles which set out the University’s commitment to responding to climate change.	University of Bath
Ethical Framework for Climate Intervention Research, Experimentation and Deployment	This framework of Principles, first proposed in a 2022 AGU White Paper, builds on work such as the Oxford Principles, the Tollgate Principles and the Asilomar Conference Recommendations on Principles for Research into Climate Engineering but also draws from ethical guidance developed for other rapidly advancing areas of technologies. The Principles are designed to help guide governments, researchers, international organizations, NGOs, and the private sector that may be engaged in climate intervention research or policy in planning their work from an early stage. These Principles are important to ensuring public trust and societal legitimacy for such research by integrating more voices into the process, and by ensuring the direct undertaking of important ethical questions around justice, transparency, inclusivity, and respect.	2023 / American Geophysical Union (AGU), in partnership with scientific and policy stakeholders around the globe

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6.6 Annex 6: Checklist for Organising Inclusive Stakeholders Meetings, updated version 2025

Checklist for Organising Inclusive Stakeholders Meetings

Updated Edition/ January 2025

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In RESIST, inclusion in stakeholders' meetings is vital for promoting just participation, inclusive collaboration, and the development of innovative solutions that can contribute to enhancing the resilience of regions affected by environmental changes/ challenges. Therefore, inclusion in stakeholders' meetings is crucial for several reasons:

- **Diverse Perspectives:** Inclusion ensures the representation of diverse stakeholders in meetings, including individuals from marginalized, vulnerable and underrepresented groups. This diversity brings a range of perspectives, experiences, and insights to the table, which can be invaluable for addressing the complex challenges posed by climate change.
- **Enhanced Decision-Making:** Inclusive meetings foster a collaborative environment where different stakeholders feel empowered to contribute their unique viewpoints. This inclusivity can lead to more informed and robust decision-making processes, as it considers a broader range of factors and potential consequences.
- **Egalitarian Participation:** Inclusion promotes just participation, ensuring that all stakeholders, regardless of their background, gender, age, or identity, have an equal opportunity to engage in the discussions and decision-making processes related to climate adaptation strategies. This aligns with the principles of fairness and justice.
- **Innovation and Creativity:** A diverse and inclusive meeting environment encourages innovation and creativity. Climate change adaptation requires innovative solutions, and diverse perspectives can spark new ideas and approaches that may not have been considered otherwise.
- **Building Trust and Collaboration:** Inclusive meetings contribute to building trust among stakeholders. When individuals from marginalized and other underrepresented groups see their perspectives valued and included, it fosters a sense of trust and collaboration. This, in turn, can strengthen the effectiveness of the RESIST project by promoting cooperation among stakeholders.
- **Reflecting Community Needs:** Climate change affects communities differently, and an inclusive approach ensures that the needs and concerns of various communities are adequately considered. This is essential for tailoring climate adaptation strategies to be relevant and effective in different regions.

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- Compliance with Ethical Standards:** Inclusion aligns with ethical standards and principles of fairness. It reflects a commitment to treating all stakeholders with dignity and respect, which is particularly important when addressing challenges as significant as climate change.

The following checklist is based on a series of resources that compile good practices in the matter, especially the **“Inclusive Meeting Guide”** from Harvard University. It aims to highlight actions that make the preparation, conduction, finalization, and follow-up of stakeholders’ meetings more inclusive.

BEFORE THE MEETING		
ASSESS ACCESSIBILITY		
Tip	Comment	
Include a statement in the meeting invitation inviting attendees to request accommodations if needed	For instance, dietary restrictions or allergies and physical accessibility.	
Design materials in a way that is easy to understand, friendly, and accessible to people with disabilities	Design materials to be accessible by using clear, simple and inclusive language and logical layouts with headings and bulleted lists for easy navigation. Ensure high-contrast colors and large, easy-to-read fonts. Offer materials in multiple formats (e.g., digital, print, braille, audio). Use inclusive visuals that reflect a variety of ages, races, abilities, and genders. Test materials with accessibility tools or real users with disabilities to ensure usability.	
Consider sending the materials in advance	While everyone values being prepared for a meeting, it is especially crucial for neurodiverse individuals and those with disabilities.	

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<p>Be prepared on how to ensure accessibility in person and online</p>	<p>You can follow these resources: Hosting Accessible Remote Meetings and Events Digital Accessibility (harvard.edu)</p>	
<p>BE INTENTIONAL</p>		
<p>Review the gender+ perspective of the meeting’s theme and objectives</p>	<p>Identifying key stakeholders can be difficult, but a clear understanding of the issues you aim to address will enable you to integrate an inclusive perspective more effectively into the planning, execution, assessment, reporting, and follow-up of your meeting or event.</p>	
<p>Take stock of who is attending and who is not. Are you missing people who could provide diverse perspectives on the topic or who are directly affected by the discussion?</p>	<p>Consider the following criteria to ensure diversity and inclusion: sex, gender, race, colour, age, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, demographics, association with a national minority, the inclusion of vulnerable populations and other relevant status.</p>	
<p>Proactively consider how diversity and power dynamics might affect attendee engagement</p>		
<p>Make sure the time and date of the meeting are during normal work hours and avoid overlaps with cultural or religious holidays</p>	<p>Meetings during normal work hours are especially helpful for attendees who are caregivers.</p>	
<p>Make sure to schedule the meeting in a manner that allows attendees who might need to travel to do so on weekdays rather than the weekend</p>	<p>Consider organizing meetings on Tuesdays, Wednesdays, or Thursdays. Alternatively, you may start on Monday afternoon and conclude meetings by noon on Friday.</p>	

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COMMUNICATE EXPECTATIONS		
When communicating on the event, share your commitment to gender balance and inclusivity both in the selection of speakers and attendees, as a key priority of the event.	Include a statement such as: “This event promotes gender equality and inclusivity by ensuring balanced representation among speakers and participants.”.	
Make sure all attendees understand their roles in promoting an inclusive and respectful environment		
Set standards about professional conduct and gender-inclusive appropriate language	If you are not sure what gender someone is, you can ask for the pronouns (e.g. he/ she/ they etc.).	
Be clear about meeting roles ahead of time so attendees have time to prepare	Decide how facilitation and note taking will be conducted (women tend to end up taking notes, so a rotation system could be helpful).	
Inform attendees about expectations regarding engagement, including the use of video and chat features during virtual meetings	For virtual meetings, consider the option of providing attendees with the choice of participating anonymously or using pseudonyms. If this is applicable, please inform them in advance of this possibility.	
Inform attendees and speakers about sex and gender data gathering upon registration	Invite speakers and attendees to fill in a questionnaire collecting sex and gender data. Explain why collecting data on sex and gender is needed (e.g., to ensure inclusivity, improve event planning etc.). Assure them that the information will be kept confidential and emphasize that participation is optional.	

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	<p>For more details on how to collect sex and gender disaggregated data, please refer to the dedicated section following the checklist.</p>	
CRAFT AN AGENDA		
<p>Send out an agenda ahead of time. This can be very helpful for those who need extra time to prepare their thoughts and could lead to more engaging discussions during the meeting</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ State the goal: What should participants think, do, or decide by the end of the meeting? ✓ Post agenda items as questions: Questions help people prepare, make it easy to keep the discussion on track, and make it easier to determine when the discussion is complete. ✓ Estimate timing: Allow a certain amount of time per question. ✓ Encourage comments: Ask participants for feedback on the agenda before the meeting. 	

DURING THE MEETING		
SET THE TONE		
Tip	Comment	
Remind everyone of the meeting's purpose and agenda	Using an agenda to guide the meeting can help provide focus to people with ADHD	
Remind everyone about the accessibility options and facilities	For example the possibility to use captions during virtual meetings	
State expectations of behaviour upfront	For example: no interrupting, mute yourself when not speaking, what is shared in the meeting stays in the meeting, and encourage alternate perspectives	
Ask attendees to use the "Raise hand" function during virtual meetings to reduce interruptions and allow everyone equal access to engagement		
Model the behaviours you expect from attendees	For example, use gender-sensitive language from the very beginning and ask the pronouns of the attendees	
If this is a group that meets regularly, check in on how people are doing	For example, at the start of a virtual meeting, ask how the group feels about having cameras on or off	
Remind attendees and speakers about the sex and gender data gathering	Reiterate the information about the purpose of the data collection and provide assurances about the safeguards in place, including confidentiality of the data and the option to opt out of providing any information.	

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	<p>Provide a point of contact for attendees or speakers with questions about the data gathering process.</p> <p>Ensure there's a mechanism for feedback or concerns regarding the collection and use of sex and gender data.</p>	
SHARE PRONOUNS		
<p>During introductions, ask attendees to include their pronouns, if they feel comfortable doing so</p>	<p>It is a positive and inclusive practice that fosters a respectful and welcoming environment for all participants and speakers.</p> <p>E.g. Chris Smith (they/them); Ahmed Doe (he/him); Yuki Zhen (she/her)</p>	
<p>Show attendees how to include their pronouns in Zoom, and encourage everyone to make this change if they feel comfortable doing so</p>		
FACILITATE THE CONVERSATION		
<p>Facilitators should tailor language so that all the participants (minorities, children, people with different education levels, and non-native speakers) can follow the discussions and intervene in the debate</p>		
<p>Ensure attendees speak one at a time</p>	<p>This is especially important for people who are hard-of-hearing</p>	
<p>Look out for conversation dominators</p>	<p>If someone is controlling the dialogue, redirect the conversation back to the broader group. Keep in mind that dominators may not just be one person, but rather a group of allies who share commonalities, such as gender or job seniority.</p>	

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<p>If someone is interrupted, step in quickly. Use phrases like: “Before we move on, I want to hear more of what Jack has to say” or “Wait a minute – I want to make sure I understand Maria’s point before we add to it.”</p>		
<p>Amplify the voices of others by acknowledging their contributions and giving public attribution to their ideas</p>		
<p>Be mindful of conformity bias, which occurs when people feel pressured to agree with everyone else in the room</p>	<p>Consider asking the group for differing view points</p>	
<p>PROVIDE MULTIPLE WAYS TO ENGAGE</p>		
<p>Allow attendees to contribute in the way they feel most comfortable, this is particularly relevant for introvert people</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Speaking up during the meeting independently ✓ Being invited to speak during a planned pause at the end of a discussion point ✓ Including text-based contributions added to the chat box of a video conference ✓ Allowing contributors to send first and final thoughts via email before or after a meeting takes place 	
<p>MANAGE TIME EFFECTIVELY</p>		
<p>Allow for some time to think and reflect</p>	<p>Some attendees may not feel comfortable sharing ideas right away, especially some introverts or neurodivergent people</p>	

<p>To avoid getting off topic, suggest that alternate topics be written down and placed in a virtual "parking lot" to be discussed at the end of the meeting if there is time</p>	<p>This can help attendees who have trouble focusing and to avoid conversation dominators</p>	
<p>CHECK IN AND RECAP</p>		
<p>Re-iterate the group's consensus and provide opportunities for attendees to voice agreement or concerns</p>	<p>This is helpful for people who are hard-of-hearing or who have a hard time focusing during discussions when multiple people are talking. This also can help ensure everyone could speak and be heard</p>	
<p>AFTER THE MEETING</p>		
<p>If possible, send a summary or meeting notes to attendees within one day</p>		
<p>Check-in with your attendees about tasks they were assigned during the meeting</p>		
<p>Ask attendees on their thoughts about how the meeting went and if they have any suggestions for future meetings. Propose the option to anonymise feedback, if needed</p>		
<p>Reflect</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ What went well? ✓ What could be better next time? ✓ What could I practice or model at the next meeting? ✓ What do I need to learn more about? 	

Collecting sex and gender disaggregated data at meetings

Collecting data on speakers and attendees for meetings or events is essential for planning, engagement, and follow-up activities. It also ensures that each voice is heard and that no one is left behind. In this way, the conclusions of the meetings can be more relevant and better inform the research/ project activities, and follow-up initiatives can better be tailored to the needs of community.

Collecting sex and gender disaggregated data on attendees and panellists at meetings / events		
Tip	Comment	
Identify what data is relevant for your activity	E.g.: name, sex, gender, sexual identity, age, race, income, cultural aspects, contact details etc.	
Offer multiple choices for sex and gender categories	E.g. sex assigned at birth: male/ female/ intersex/ prefer not to say; gender identification: man, woman, non-binary, self-identification, other, prefer not to say Communicate that providing sex and gender data is optional.	
Use neutral, non-discriminatory language when describing sex and gender questions		
Build the questionnaire using a user-friendly and mobile-compatible online platform	Pay attention to the language used. Think about distributing the questionnaire also on paper while communicating on the event.	
Ensure attendees and speakers are informed about data collection early	E.g. via the invitation, registration, or event materials Liaise with local leaders/ NGOs to help you spread the questionnaire	

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	and support potential attendees in completing it.	
Explain why and for what purpose sex and gender data is being collected	Provide assurances that personal information will be kept confidential.	
Obtain explicit consent for data collection and any follow-up communications		
Comply with national and EU data protection laws		

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6.7 Annex 7: Checklist for Including the Gender Dimension in Research, 2024

Checklist for Including the Gender Dimension in Research

16 January 2024

Authors: Agostina Allori, Ioana Bara-Busila, Eugenia Vilarchao, Ildiko Ipolyi – ESF

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Why Integrating the Gender Dimension into Research Matters for the RESIST Project?

Incorporating the gender dimension into research activities and outcomes is a key challenge directly linked to achieving excellence. Excellence in research refers to the highest standards of quality, innovation, and impact in the scientific or scholarly work conducted by researchers. It involves the pursuit of new knowledge, the development of novel methodologies, and the generation of insights that contribute significantly to the advancement of a particular field or discipline.

Gender equality is intricately linked to excellence in research through the recognition that diverse perspectives, experiences, and talents contribute to the richness and depth of research outcomes. Achieving gender equality in research involves ensuring equal opportunities, representation, and recognition for individuals of all genders. Ensuring an ethically sound process is essential for producing high-quality results when considering the gender dimension in research activities. Notably, prominent research funding organizations, such as the European Commission, pay special attention to the analysis of the gender dimension in research, prompting researchers to reassess and align their research plans accordingly. This evolving landscape underscores the significance of addressing the gender dimension in research for both ethical considerations and alignment with funding priorities.

In the RESIST project, incorporating the gender dimension into research is vital for a comprehensive response to the diverse impacts of climate change. This commitment is driven by the acknowledgment that recent extreme weather events have unveiled significant gender differences in experiences, responses, and the prevalence of post-traumatic stress disorder. Through a focus on gender equality and inclusion, RESIST seeks to correct the oversight of nuanced distinctions by technological solutions, preventing the perpetuation of gendered outcomes. Additionally, given the historical dominance in decision-making, particularly within industries contributing to climate change, there is a compelling need to reassess policy responses. RESIST emphasizes that integrating gender considerations not only addresses existing disparities but also advances social justice, avoiding unintended consequences. This inclusive approach aligns with the project's goal of exploring climate change adaptation through a lens that responds to and accommodates diverse gender experiences and intersections.

The following checklist was based on several good practices in the subject matter (referenced at the end of this document), especially the Gender Impact Assessment (GIA) Checklist elaborated by the Horizon 2020 project **RESET** (Redesigning Equality and Scientific Excellence Together).

This checklist aims to assist the researchers of RESIST in achieving excellence by mainstreaming the gender dimension in the different phases of the research cycle.

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Planning Phase of the Research Task/Activity					
Question	Comments/ Examples	Yes	No	Not sure	N/A
Have you conducted a literature review and included sex and gender in your search of keywords?	Example: In the literature review on climate change adaptation, you ensured to include keywords like "gender and climate change impacts" to capture studies that specifically address how men and women are affected differently.				
Did you take into consideration the diversity of quoted authors?	For instance, in terms of sex, gender, geographical origin				
Do you indicate the first name of the authors in the bibliography?	Example: In the bibliography, you consistently indicated authors' first names, such as "Maria Rodriguez" instead of just "Rodriguez," to highlight the diversity of author identities.				
Have you considered gender implications at the time of elaborating your research question and your research goals?	Example: When formulating your research question on urban development, you specifically considered how gender dynamics might influence access to resources and community participation				
When thinking about the research or data gaps, have you considered that gender may play a role in producing such gaps?	Example: While identifying gaps in the research on renewable energy, you critically assessed how gender roles might contribute to the underrepresentation of women in leadership positions within sustainable energy organizations				

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Do you use sex/gender-disaggregated data at the level of design of the research?					
If any differences in sex/gender-disaggregated data exist, do you ask yourself whether these differences are influenced by gender roles in society?					
Does your way to interpret sex/gender-disaggregated data (if it exists) include self-reflection on the influence of stereotypes and unconscious biases?					
Do you consider diverse communities in your sample?	Example: In your study on community resilience to natural disasters, you ensured a diverse sampling approach by including participants from various age groups, genders, and cultural backgrounds to capture a comprehensive range of perspectives				
Have you considered the gender-specific risks associated with your research and have designed measures to mitigate these risks?					
Have you verified existing gender theories that concern the subject of your research?					
Do you have a gender expert in your team?	Example: Recognizing the importance of gender expertise in your project on environmental policy, you included a sociologist specializing in gender studies to provide insights on potential gender biases in policy formulations.				
Implementation: Execution Phase of the Research					
Do you collect/use sex/gender-disaggregated data whenever possible?					

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Have you designed data collection tools to consider gender stereotypes and social and cultural factors that may introduce gender bias into the data?					
Have you designed data collection tools to mitigate gender stereotypes and social and cultural factors that may introduce gender bias into the data?					
Is your team balanced in terms of sex, gender, and diversity?	Nationality, age, origin, status, academic age				
Have you considered sex, gender and diversity dimensions in the recruitment, job descriptions and career paths of research group member?					
Do you create opportunities throughout the research cycle to be reflexive and aware of your own and your team's gender assumptions, biases and power as researchers?					
Are there dimensions other than sex and gender to consider?					
Even if the team is not obviously diverse (e.g : all members come from the same field, gender, ethnicity,...), do you take into account points of view and experiences of all social groups?					
Are all points of views heard and all members listened to?					
Are tasks in your team circulated or distributed in a way that does not reproduce gender stereotypes?					
Are researchers trained in gender equality included in your team?					
Impact- Dissemination Phase of the Research					
Are you using appropriate terminologies and language that do not reflect gender stereotypes and that do not assume only two genders?					

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When considering authors, inviting keynotes, planning publications and providing visibility for researchers and their work on websites do you pay attention to gender balance?					
Is the sex/gender dimension included in the presentation of findings?					
Are Research reports/publications/outputs revised by a gender expert?					
Do you consider that the results of your research (project) can have different effects on men and women, boys or girls and people of non-binary genders?					
Does your research contribute to the advancement of gender equality in society?	Example: You believe that your research on sustainable agriculture practices can contribute to the advancement of gender equality by promoting equal access to resources and opportunities for men and women in the agricultural sector.				

If you have replied “no” or “not sure” to any of the questions on the checklist, you can contact the ESF team for tailor-needed support at the time of including the gender dimension in your research.

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Conclusion

In conclusion, when undertaking EU-funded projects focused on climate change research and innovation, it is imperative to get acquainted with, gain a solid understanding of, and apply the available tools on gender mainstreaming and ethics.

Gender mainstreaming ensures that the perspectives and needs of all genders are integrated into every aspect of the project, promoting equality and inclusivity. Furthermore, ethical considerations must be paramount throughout the project's lifecycle, encompassing adherence to the highest ethical standards, as well as compliance with relevant EU, international, and national laws.

By prioritizing gender mainstreaming and ethics in EU-funded climate change research and innovation projects, researchers and stakeholders can ensure the integrity, fairness, and effectiveness of their endeavours, ultimately contributing to more sustainable, inclusive and equitable solutions for addressing the challenges of climate change.

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6.8 Annex 8: Guidelines for inclusive communication, 2024

GUIDELINES FOR INCLUSIVE COMMUNICATION

10 January 2024

Authors: Agostina Allori, Eugenia Vilarchao, Ioana Bara-Busila, Ildiko Ipolyi - ESF

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Summary

Climate action requires communication that considers gender differences and fosters inclusivity. The RESIST Project recognizes that climate impacts vary for people from different genders, due to social disparities. Tailoring communication to these diverse needs ensures more effective and sustainable climate policies.

Inclusive communication ensures active participation in climate discussions, particularly from women facing climate impacts. Challenging stereotypes promotes equitable resource distribution, fostering shared responsibility within communities.

Considering gender in communication addresses information gaps, especially for women in marginalized communities. Tailored methods enable broader participation in climate action by providing knowledge and tools to all. Gender-sensitive communication enhances the overall effectiveness of climate initiatives by promoting social cohesion and community engagement. Recognizing and addressing gender disparities is crucial for building resilient communities, aligning with RESIST Project goals.

These guidelines provide the RESIST consortium with directions for gender-sensitive and inclusive communication. They cover various communication types and specific topics like addressing gender stereotypes, promoting inclusive language, managing audiovisual representations, and effective communication on climate action. An appendix includes a checklist for agile revision in social media publications. The aim is to empower the RESIST Project in fostering inclusive and impactful communication for sustainable climate outcomes.

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○ Introduction

1 The Importance of Gender Equality and Inclusion in the RESIST Project

In the RESIST project considering gender equality and inclusion is crucial due to the distinct impacts of climate change on men and women, as indicated in Annex 4 of the Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework ([Deliverable 1.9](#)). Recent extreme weather events have highlighted gender differences in disaster experiences, evacuation responses, and post-traumatic stress disorder prevalence. Technological solutions often overlook these nuances, perpetuating gendered outcomes. Decision-making, particularly in industries contributing to climate change, has been traditionally male-dominated, necessitating a re-evaluation of policy responses. The gendered nature of risk perception, environmental concern, and energy consumption underscores the importance of nuanced approaches. Women's roles in reproductive, caring, and community management work, often unpaid and overlooked, further emphasize the need for gender considerations. In RESIST, considering the binary gender perspective despite its limitations reflects a commitment to addressing gender disparities and ensuring inclusive adaptation measures, aligning with the project's goal of exploring climate change adaptation with a gender and intersectional lens. This approach is essential for social justice and avoiding unintended consequences, recognizing that power imbalances can hinder successful climate adaptation.

2 Why Gender Sensitive and Inclusive Communication Matters for RESIST?

Gender-sensitive and inclusive communication is crucial for effective climate action for several reasons. First, it recognizes that climate change affects men and women differently due to existing social, economic, and cultural disparities. By acknowledging and addressing these gender-specific impacts, communication strategies can be tailored to the diverse needs and vulnerabilities of different groups.

Second, inclusive communication ensures that the voices of all individuals, regardless of gender, are heard and considered in climate discussions. Women, who often bear the brunt of climate impacts, must be actively involved in decision-making processes. Inclusive communication promotes diverse perspectives, which leads to more comprehensive and sustainable climate policies and initiatives. Moreover, gender-sensitive communication helps challenging stereotypes and traditional gender roles that may contribute to unequal distribution of resources and opportunities. It encourages a more equitable distribution of responsibilities and benefits related to climate action, fostering a sense of shared ownership and responsibility within communities.

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In addition, considering gender in climate communication helps bridging the gaps in access to information and resources. Women, especially in marginalized communities, may have limited access to education and information. Tailoring communication methods to reach these groups ensures that everyone has the knowledge and tools to participate in climate action.

Last, gender-sensitive communication contributes to the overall effectiveness of climate initiatives by promoting social cohesion and community engagement. Recognizing and addressing gender disparities fosters a sense of inclusivity and shared responsibility, which is essential for building resilient communities and achieving sustainable climate outcomes, key aims of the RESIST Project.

3 Scope

The scope of these guidelines is to offer the RESIST consortium some directions and recommendations on how to communicate in a gender-sensitive and inclusive manner. It includes practical examples for different types of communication (written, verbal, interpersonal interactions, and audiovisual communication). The document also provides some indications on sensitive communication of climate change-related topics.

These guidelines address the following topics:

- Gender Stereotypes in Language (section 2);
- Inclusive Language (section 3);
- Audiovisual Representations (section 4);
- Communicating on Climate Action (section 5).

To help you revise social media publications, please consult the “[Diversity & Inclusivity Checklist for Social Media Posts](#)”.

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○ Unravelling Gender Stereotypes in Language

According to the *Toolkit on Gender Sensitive Communication* of the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), stereotypes are generalised images about people within a society. A gender stereotype is a preconceived idea where individuals are assigned characteristics and roles determined and limited by their gender. Stereotypes about gender often take one of two forms. One assumes all members of a category (such as a profession) share a gender, for example, the assumption that all company directors are men, and all secretaries are women. The other is assuming that all members of a gender share a characteristic, for example believing that all women love to shop or that 'boys don't cry'. These stereotypes hurt people of all genders by placing expectations on what people should be or how they should act.

In many cases unconscious cultural stereotypes are expressed through the language we use, meaning people use these expressions even when they do not hold these assumptions. Repeating these stereotypes reinforces the assumptions at their core, therefore one should actively avoid stereotypes in the language you use. The sections below highlight some instances where one may come across gender stereotypes in language⁶:

- ✓ Adding irrelevant information about gender in a description of an individual.
- ✓ Assigning gender to inanimate objects.
- ✓ Using gender stereotypes to describe objects or events.
- ✓ Describing people of different genders using different adjectives (descriptive words).
- ✓ Perpetuating stereotypes in non-verbal communication, such as images and symbols⁷.

⁶ European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), *Toolkit on Gender Sensitive Communication*, 2019, p.19. See: [Toolkit on gender-sensitive communication | European Institute for Gender Equality \(europa.eu\)](#). Last visit: 08/01/2024.

⁷ Ibid.

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“I need to speak to the Secretary. Is she in the office?”

Tip!

Professions and occupations are often gender stereotyped. Take special care to avoid stereotypes when talking about people’s occupations.

Example 1: Gender stereotypes when referring to an occupation (EIGE Gender-sensitive communication Toolkit, Guidelines, p. 19).

1 Avoid Gendered Pronouns (He or She) when the Person’s Gender is Unknown

When employing a gendered pronoun, such as 'he' or 'she,' the speaker is making an assumption about the gender of the person under discussion. Frequently, individuals use gendered pronouns even when unaware of the person's gender or when referring to a group with unspecified genders. This habit reinforces gender stereotypes by reiterating widely held assumptions about the gender associated with specific roles. To counter this, it is advisable to utilize gender-neutral language. A prevalent method is the use of the plural 'they,' which is increasingly accepted in standard English⁸.

-“Your boss needs to know he can rely on you”
-“But my boss is a woman...”

Example 2: Using Gendered Pronouns (EIGE Gender-sensitive communication Toolkit, Guidelines, p. 20).

2 Avoid Irrelevant Information about Gender

When talking or writing about jobs, avoid mentioning gender if it's not relevant. Including unnecessary gender details reinforces the stereotype that certain professions are associated with a specific gender. For instance, saying 'female lawyer' suggests that lawyers are usually male. Therefore, terms like 'female professor' or 'male nurse' should be avoided. Instead, use the job title without specifying gender. Another prevalent method of incorporating gender into writing when it's unnecessary is by using gendered nouns, such as "policeman" and "policewoman." To promote

⁸ EIGE, *supra note* 1, p. 20.

inclusivity, refrain from using these gender-specific nouns and opt for gender-neutral alternatives, such as "police officer"⁹.

Examples

X Gender discriminatory language

The eco-action group chairman Moni Patel works closely with the chairman of the social action committee Matthieu Dubois to plan events.

✓ **Gender neutral language**

The eco-action group chair Moni Patel works closely with the chair/chairperson of the social action committee Matthieu Dubois to plan events.

X Gender discriminatory language

Priti is a career woman.

✓ **Gender neutral language**

Priti is focused on her career.

Example 3: Irrelevant Information about Gender (EIGE Gender-sensitive communication Toolkit, Guidelines, p. 21).

3 Avoid Gendering Inanimate Objects

Attributing a gender to an inanimate object using gendered pronouns imparts cultural associations to its characteristics. These associations are tied to gender stereotypes and contribute to their perpetuation. When discussing inanimate objects, it is advisable to use the pronoun "it" to avoid reinforcing these stereotypes¹⁰.

⁹ EIGE, *supra note* 1, p. 21.

¹⁰ EIGE, *supra note* 1, p. 23.

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Examples

X Gender discriminatory language
The ship slipped her moorings.

✓ **Gender neutral language**
The ship slipped its moorings.

X Gender discriminatory language
Delegates are free to make presentations in their mother tongues and translations will be provided.

✓ **Gender neutral language**
Delegates are free to make presentations in their native languages and translations will be provided.

X Gender discriminatory language
Last month, France and her citizens woke up to heavily snowfall.

✓ **Gender neutral language**
Last month, France and its citizens woke up to snowfall.

Example 4: Gendering Objects (EIGE Gender-sensitive communication Toolkit, Guidelines, p. 23).

4 Avoid Using Different Adjectives for Women and Men

In English, there are instances where distinct adjectives are employed to characterize the same attribute in women and men. Additionally, certain words, while not explicitly gendered, carry strong connotations exclusively associated with either women or men. This phenomenon arises from societal perceptions wherein certain character traits, like ambition, are viewed as positive in men but negative in women. Identifying adjectives that reinforce gender stereotypes is not always straightforward. The table below presents examples of words to be cautious about using when describing women. There are also words that are supposed to have a female equivalent but have gained negative connotation, such as: governor/governess; master/mistress; patron/matron; sir/madam; bachelor/spinster; host/hostess¹¹.

¹¹ EIGE, *supra note 1*, p. 24.

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○ Inclusive Language

Gender-sensitive communication means using inclusive language, which promotes gender equality and the equal visibility of all genders¹². Following the Council of Europe’s Committee of Ministers Recommendation R (90) 4 on the elimination of sexism from language, it entails:

- Encouraging the use of non-sexist language to take account of the presence, status, and role of women in society, as current linguistic practice does for men.
- Bringing the terminology used in legal drafting, public administration, and education into line with the principle of gender equality.
- Encouraging the use of non-sexist language in the media.

In practice, and as stated in the *Style Guidelines for English text* of the European Citizen Science Association¹³, as a general rule it is important to always write with respect, care and sensitivity and, if possible, to consult those we are writing about. When writing about someone, it is best to consult how they would like to be referred to. It is also key to understand language as a reflection of culture in constant evolution and that there might not be full consensus around certain terms and definitions. While this guide has an emphasis on gender equality, a gender+ approach¹⁴ will be adopted, where other categories such as disability; race, ethnicity and nationality; and Indigenous and First Nations peoples are taken into account. Such perspective is also central to understand and communicate properly the multiple inequalities that arise in the context of climate crisis, climate action and the European Green Deal.

1 Gender Sensitive Language

The SUPERA Project¹⁵ has developed a comprehensive guideline on inclusive communication that will be adapted to the RESIST Project context in this section.

¹² Supporting the Promotion of Equality in Research and Academia (SUPERA), Guidelines for Gender Sensitive Communication in Research and Academia”, May 2021. Available here: [D8.2-TAILOR-MADE-guides-for-gender-sensitive-communication-in-research-and-academia-v.1.1-.pdf](https://superaproject.eu/D8.2-TAILOR-MADE-guides-for-gender-sensitive-communication-in-research-and-academia-v.1.1-.pdf) (superaproject.eu). Last access: 27/11/2023.

¹³ European Citizen Science Association (ESCA), *Style Guidelines for English Text*, May 2023.

¹⁴ As defined by the ACCTING Project, “The plus in gender+ is an invitation to be curious about the complex ways in which gender dynamically interacts with “race,” class, sexuality, (dis)ability, ethnicity, religion, and citizenship status (among others), in shaping human lives and inequalities in contemporary society”. See: <https://accting.eu/what-does-gender-mean/>. Last access: 27/11/2023.

¹⁵ Supporting the Promotion of Equality in Research and Academia (SUPERA).

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Examining language from a gender perspective to enhance awareness of the potential implications of linguistic choices is valuable for avoiding expressions that may be perceived as biased or discriminatory. It is crucial to emphasize that there is an opportunity and a necessity for enhancements in both written and spoken language within any organisation. This is a gradual process that may encounter resistances. Implementing a gender-sensitive language protocol or arranging specialized training sessions with language experts can be positive steps in this endeavour for any organisation.

In response to a growing interest in recent years, numerous guidelines addressing gender-sensitive language have been developed and implemented in various international institutions, professional associations, universities, news agencies, and several European countries (EU, 2018).

In a multilingual setting such as the European context, it is essential to recognize that different languages necessitate distinct strategies in terms of gender sensitivity. The *EU Gender-neutral language in the European Parliament* toolkit (2018)¹⁶ categorizes language families as explained in table 1¹⁷. This is important to consider because, although the primary language of the RESIST Project is English, given its implementation in several regions of Europe, communication materials might need to be translated into other languages.

LANGUAGE FAMILY	STRATEGY	EXAMPLES
Natural gender languages (such as Danish, English, Swedish)	Personal nouns are mostly gender-neutral and there are personal pronouns specific to each gender. These languages can replace the use of gender-specific terms with gender neutral terms	Chairman→chair/chairperson Spokesman→ spokesperson Headmaster/headmistress→ director/principal “He” used as a generic reference→ He or she
Grammatical gender languages (such as German, Romance languages and Slavic languages)	Every noun has a grammatical gender and the gender of personal pronouns usually matches the reference noun. Various approaches are recommended, such as the use of feminine correspondents of masculine terms (for instance, job titles) Replacing the generic masculine with double forms for specific referents has	Profesora Administradora Geschäftsführein Rettrice Tutti I professori e tutte le professoresse ;

¹⁶ See: *European Parliament, EU Gender neutral language in the European Parliament*, 2018. Available here: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/cmsdata/151780/GNL_Guidelines_EN.pdf. Last access: 27/11/2023.

¹⁷ SUPERA, *supra* note 3.

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	also gained acceptance in many languages. As a result of this increasingly widespread form, the use of generic masculine terms is no longer the only accepted practice, even in legislative and official acts.	Todos os investigadores e todas as investigadoras
Genderless languages (such as Estonian, Finnish and Hungarian)	They have no grammatical gender and no pronominal gender	No need for a particular strategy to be gender-sensitive

Table 1: Language families and strategies for gender-sensitive language (SUPERA Guidelines, p. 50).

As for the EIGE’s *Gender Sensitive Communication Toolkit*¹⁸, it is intended for English speakers. The toolkit begins with two definitions:

- Gender-sensitive language** aims to apply gender equality to written and spoken language. It is realised when women, men and those who do not conform to the binary gender dichotomy are made visible and addressed in language. Different strategies that can be used to express gender relationships with accuracy, such as avoiding, to the greatest possible extent, the use of language that refers explicitly or implicitly only to the male gender, and ensuring, through inclusionary alternatives and according to each language’s characteristics, the use of gender-sensitive and inclusive language. Due to the importance of the gender dimension in public policy, law- and policy-makers are always advised to use gender-sensitive language: enhancing gender visibility is an important way for public policy to positively affect all members of society. This is a relevant aspect to consider for all the normative and administrative texts within universities and research institutions and companies;
- Gender-neutral language** is a not gender-specific language that refers to people in general, with no reference to women or men. One potential benefit of this approach is that it can be more inclusive to those who do not identify in a binary way with one gender. This form can be seen, for instance, when rephrasing a sentence avoiding mentioning specifically the

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gender or using a term that includes all genders (e.g., “people” instead of “women and men”; “la comunità studentesca” used in Italian with reference to the students of all genders)¹⁹.

According to the EIGE toolkit and SUPERA’s guidelines, there are three broad categories under which gender-discriminatory language may fall, some of which have been already mentioned in section 2:

1. **Assigning gender** when gender is unknown or irrelevant as a result of **stereotypes**.

This can occur:

- **Using gendered pronouns.** When using a pronoun such as “he” or “she”, the speaker is assuming the gender of the person they are talking about. This practice repeats the most common expectations about the gender of people in certain roles in universities and research institutions. Instead, the gender-neutral plural “they” should be used. It is also important not to rely on “he/him/man” when talking about an individual in the abstract as this excludes women from conversations.
- **Adding irrelevant information about gender in a description of an individual.** When speaking or writing about occupations, it is important not to provide irrelevant information about people’s gender. For example, in academia, saying “female professor” implies that professors are normally/usually male. Instead, the occupation title with no gender description should be used.
- **Using gender stereotypes to describe objects or individuals.** Do not employ gender stereotypes to describe the way something is or the way the action is done. Avoid using words implying a gender connotation to describe an aspect of a person or object, in particular when the gendered term is used as an insult. Derogatory expressions such as “behave like a girl”, “ladylike”, the verb “to man up”, all describe something as feminine to suggest its weakness or inefficacy. This kind of language is still widespread also in interpersonal interactions, also in academic/scientific working environments: it is a sexist behaviour that should be avoided (see table 2)²⁰.

¹⁹ SUPERA, *supra note 3*, p.51.

²⁰ SUPERA, *supra note 3*, p.51-52.

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DEROGATORY ADJECTIVES	ALTERNATIVES
Bossy or pushy	Assertive
Loose	Having sexual confidence
Emotional or hormonal	Passionate, enthusiastic, empathetic
Hysterical	Irrational, nervous

Table 2: Derogatory Adjectives and Alternatives (SUPERA Guidelines, p. 52).

2. **Invisibility and omission:** language that casts the male as the generic norm and keeps women from being visible in research institutions and in public life in general. Examples are using “man”/”mankind” referring to all the human beings; using “he” when referring to the generic experience of all people as this removes women from the common experience (“he or she” could be used as an alternative; some people have started to use gender-neutral pronouns in place of traditional gender pronouns, like the pronoun “ze”); referring to a mixed gendered group using expressions such as “the guys”: although very common in working and study environments, these expressions take the male as generic and representative of the whole group and therefore should be avoided.
3. **Subordination and trivialisation:** language which paints one gender as inferior or belittles them. Very often, concepts related to women are trivialised through terms that make something sound “small” or “cute”. This may appear benign but can have the effect of reinforcing women’s subordinate place in society at large. It occurs in different types of circumstances, that have been listed in Table 3.

TYPE	EXAMPLES
Naming conventions	Use Ms instead of Mrs/Miss because (as Mr) does not denote marital status.
	Always use the same naming conventions for men and women: using a first name to refer to a woman and a surname for a man indicates a lack of respect, as well as using the formal titles in an asymmetrical form.

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Word phrase hierarchy	Consider switching the order of these expressions each time you use one: Men and women, Ladies and gentlemen, Boys and girls. When they are used several times in the same text or speech, invert the order of the words in order to not create gender imbalances.
Patronising language	The addition of diminutive affixes to denote that the referent is female is patronising.
	Language which refers to people unknown to you in terms of endearment (“my dear”, “darling”, “love”, “dear”) is patronising and promotes trivialisation. These forms should not be used in any working contexts.
	Another common way of trivialising women is to refer to adult women as “girls”. This should be avoided also in academia and research institutions.
	Common expressions in the media regarding women in science are: “the angels of science”, “the ladies of research”. They should be replaced with less derogatory expressions. Communication and media relations offices should accurately select words and metaphors when publishing institutional press releases or creating contents for news websites.

Table 3: Subordination and Trivialisation Examples (SUPERA Guidelines, p. 53)

Scientifics, academics, and policymakers in general operate within unique communicative contexts that necessitate the use of gender-neutral or gender-sensitive language. Key considerations relevant to RESIST Project partners include:

- ✓ In interpersonal communication within working environments, such as meetings, labs, and lectures, special attention is needed to identify and address gender stereotypes in oral language. Employees should receive training on respectful and inclusive communication, particularly in interactions with individuals with special needs, including those with disabilities, pregnant women, foreign students and researchers, and individuals with non-conforming genders;
- ✓ Both in publications and interpersonal communications, it should be ensured that statements about women are respectful and avoid any patronizing language. Refrain from attributing material or educational deprivations to women, focusing instead on addressing systemic challenges and fostering empowerment;
- ✓ In academic writing, a best practice is to explicitly mention authors' first names in references to enhance the visibility of female researchers. Bibliographies and references should be

reviewed to prevent gender unconscious biases that may lead to less frequent citations of female researchers compared to their male counterparts²¹.

2 Inclusive Language Regarding Disabilities

Within the broader framework of promoting inclusivity, it is crucial to pay special attention to our language when addressing individuals with disabilities. By adopting person-first language, avoiding negative connotations, and recognizing individual agency, we aim to contribute to a communication environment that respects the diverse experiences and preferences within our communities. In that respect it is recommended to:

- ✓ Embrace person-first language, such as 'people with disabilities,' rather than 'disabled people';
- ✓ Steer clear of language with negative connotations; for instance, use 'person with a mental health condition' or 'neurodiverse person' instead of 'suffering from a mental disorder' and 'wheelchair user' rather than 'confined to a wheelchair.' Opt for 'person who has experienced' instead of 'victim' or 'survivor';
- ✓ Avoid using 'disabled' as a collective noun ('the disabled');
- ✓ Refrain from language that implies passivity or victimization, such as 'afflicted by' or 'suffers from'. Eliminate outdated and potentially offensive terms like 'mentally handicapped' or 'invalid';
- ✓ Extend these principles to writing in general, recognizing individuals as autonomous beings not solely defined by characteristics or conditions. For example, use 'older people/persons' or 'older adults' instead of 'the elderly' or 'senior citizens';
- ✓ Keep in mind that terminology preferences may vary among different communities. For instance, some Indigenous communities prefer 'elders in the community' rather than 'older people'²².

²¹ SUPERA, *supra note 3*, p.54.

²² ESCA, *supra note 2*, p.7.

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3 Inclusive Language Regarding Race, Ethnicity and Nationality

In RESIST's commitment to fostering an inclusive and respectful communication environment, it is imperative to approach references to race, ethnicity, or nationality with care. We offer here specific guidance on when and how to refer to such characteristics in a manner that is necessary and relevant to the information being communicated. By emphasizing specificity, avoiding outdated terms, and acknowledging the diverse backgrounds and identities of individuals, we aim to promote sensitivity and precision in our language²³:

- ✓ Do not use broad geographical labels and be specific –say Ugandan rather than African, Vietnamese rather than Asian, German rather than European;
- ✓ Write 'Black' in upper case, 'white' (not Caucasian) in lower case;
- ✓ For countries, avoid using outdated terms such as 'third world' or 'underdeveloped';
- ✓ Be as specific as possible when referring to a person or group's background or heritage. Remember that some people identify with more than one ethnic group or a mixed ethnic group;
- ✓ Avoid using broad terms such as 'minorities' or 'Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic (BAME)'²⁴.

4 Inclusive Language Regarding Indigenous and First Nations Peoples

Within the context of RESIST, which has climate action at its core, it is essential to approach references to Indigenous and First Nations peoples with respect and cultural sensitivity. These guidelines provide specific direction on language usage to ensure that our communication reflects an understanding of and appreciation for the diversity within these communities:

- ✓ Always capitalise 'Indigenous' and 'First Nations' when referring to a group of people;
- ✓ There is no single Indigenous identity;
- ✓ Use 'Indigenous peoples' (plural) when referring to more than one distinct community;
- ✓ Be specific and always consult the community that you are writing²⁵.

²³ See as well: Oxfam inclusive language guide. Available here: <https://oxfamilibrary.openrepository.com/bitstream/handle/10546/621487/gd-inclusive-language-guide-130323-en.pdf;jsessionid=528E54623569D9DD2C6F82CA7F89BF33?sequence=4>.

²⁴ ESCA, *supra note 2*, p.7.

²⁵ ESCA, *supra note 2*, p.7.

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○ **Audiovisual Representations**

Audiovisual communication plays a pivotal role in conveying the values and identity of the project. The digitization of information has amplified the dissemination of pictures, infographics, and videos, giving visuals a central role in enhancing the visibility of messages and shaping perception of the topics. Therefore, it is crucial to embrace a gender-sensitive approach in managing visuals and graphics for all the RESIST communications.

Visuals can actively reinforce the message of a welcoming and inclusive environment, helping overcome gender stereotypes and amplifying the visibility of underrepresented categories. The risk of "tokenism" arises when images neglect certain groups or portray them as exceptions to the norm. Visual representation of gender diversity and other forms of diversity contributes to emphasizing the identity of an inclusive and open community.

It is imperative that visuals avoid perpetuating gender stereotypes to prevent reinforcing gender imbalances in messages and all communication touchpoints, including stands and banners in international conferences, and the visual layout of offices and meeting rooms. In this regard, careful consideration should be given to the content of visuals to ensure they align with the goal of promoting inclusivity and avoiding stereotypical representations²⁶.

When communicating climate actions, it is vital to incorporate audiovisuals that portray a diverse range of ages, abilities, styles, ethnicities, professions, and genders (beyond the binary categorization of men and women). This inclusivity is crucial for individuals to identify with the content, making the message more relatable and easily comprehensible.

According to the SUPERA Guidelines, the following aspects should be considered:

- ✓ Colours are often arbitrarily connected to one gender, such as pink for women and blue for men. It would be advisable to avoid this classical representation and also to avoid using pastel colored palettes associated with the feminine (EIGE, 2018). Using different colors (like greens, yellow or orange) can be a good alternative. Avoid using pink or purple when a communication material addresses women specifically;
- ✓ All genders should be represented in a diverse and realistic way. Women in visuals should represent the activities of the project or organisation (e.g., study, research, teaching or working) and they should not be chosen as merely decorative contents. Texts and images should be coherent (for instance, captions should include the female gender or gender diversity in the languages in which this applies);

²⁶ SUPERA, *supra note 3*, p.55-56.

- ✓ The depiction of women and men should attempt to break with notions of gender roles that perpetuate gender inequalities. Women should be depicted as being able to leverage opportunities or as having equal opportunities, also being in positions of power as professors, doctors, principal investigators, directors or team leaders. It is important to be mindful of subliminal messages about gender norms. For example, it is recommended to choose images in which postures, expressions, gestures and clothing convey equal status and authority for any member of the university community²⁷.

Example 5: Non-stereotypical colors and symbols in data visualisation (SUPERA Guidelines, p. 57).

- ✓ Icons are another critical element in visuals because they easily tend to represent stereotypes: for instance, the typical female icon comes with a skirt. When choosing icons, consider carefully the risk of reiterating stereotypes in publics' perception;

²⁷ Ibid.

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- ✓ Infographics combine texts, figures and graphics to convey articulated contents; they are gaining a lot of attention especially on the web, where they are often quickly shared by digital publics in their personal accounts and profiles. This makes it extremely important to address specific attention on their creation and on the subjects they represent. In infographics, synthesis is the norm: it is therefore easy to stumble into stereotypes with icons and colors. It is important to pay special attention on how human figures are depicted: are they diverse? Are stereotypes used to define genders?²⁸

To help you revise social media publications, please consult the “[Diversity & Inclusivity Checklist for Social Media Posts](#)”.

²⁸ SUPERA, *supra note 3*, p.57-58.

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o Communicating on Climate Action

Considering the core focus of the RESIST Project on climate mitigation and climate action, and taking into account the phenomenon of 'climate anxiety,' it is deemed important to include a section related to communication on this topic, based on the Guidelines for Climate Action of the United Nations²⁹:

- 1. Always use authoritative scientific information:** misinformation and false information about climate change are big problems that make it hard to deal with the climate crisis. Wrong or confusing messages about climate science and solutions can lead to delays in taking action or doing things that make the situation worse. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), spreading incorrect information and not trusting science creates misunderstandings about what most scientists agree on, makes people unsure, ignores risks and urgency, and causes disagreements. So, it's important to stop false information to make progress in tackling climate change;
 - ✓ **Check your sources:** when sharing information, ensure its reliability by sourcing science-based, objective data from reputable outlets such as peer-reviewed articles; DG Clima (European Commission) or the UN's Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change;
 - ✓ **Stop misinformation:** exercise caution when sharing online content, as information spreads rapidly; before sharing, investigate its origin, sources, funding, and potential motives, and combat misinformation among your followers by employing the 'Fact, Myth, Fallacy' model for a memorable and effective response.

- 2. Convey the problems and the solutions:** while it is crucial to convey the enormity of the climate crisis, it can be overwhelming, causing people to lose interest. Despite being a significant challenge, the fight against climate change is not hopeless. Acting now can prevent the worst impacts. To avoid disillusionment, it is effective to emphasize hopeful messages centred on solutions, empowering and motivating people to get involved;

²⁹ See: <https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/communicating-climate-change>. Last visit: 28/11/2023.

- ✓ **Tell a story, make it real:** to engage your audience effectively, avoid presenting data alone and instead make it relatable, local, and personal, using individual stories related to issues like air pollution, clean energy job opportunities, or power outages during hurricanes, as they forge an emotive connection, instill care, and make global challenges seem less daunting;
- ✓ **Empower people:** empower individuals by highlighting their ability to make a difference through both personal actions, like changing consumption patterns, and advocating for systemic changes, emphasizing that collective small steps can create significant pressure on leaders to address crucial issues;
- ✓ **Link it to justice:** climate change is not just a scientific matter; it's also a justice issue, disproportionately impacting the poor and people a marginalized situation, who often contributed the least to emissions, while unfulfilled financial commitments from wealthier nations underscore the need to address both the climate crisis and its associated injustices for the benefit of all;
- ✓ **Avoid stereotypes:** poorer countries and underserved communities, including indigenous peoples who have protected the environment for generations, are often portrayed solely as victims of climate change, rather than positive agents of change. The same is often the case for women and girls. Make sure to highlight the voices, expertise, innovations, positive action, and solutions by people from all walks of life and communities from all parts of the world.
- ✓ **Focus on solution:** particularly when addressing the intersectionality of climate change and socio-economic aspects, a good way to overcome distress is to communicate a positive message centered around solutions and to link it to justice.

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6.9 Annex 9: Diversity & Inclusivity Checklist for Social Media Posts, 2024

Diversity & Inclusivity Checklist for Social Media Posts

10 January 2024

Authors: Agostina Allori, Eugenia Vilarchao, Ildiko Ipolyi (ESF)

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○ The Importance of Gender Equality and Inclusion in the RESIST Project

In the RESIST project considering gender equality and inclusion is crucial due to the distinct impacts of climate change on men and women, as indicated in Annex 4 of the Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics Framework ([Deliverable 1.9](#)). Recent extreme weather events have highlighted gender differences in disaster experiences, evacuation responses, and post-traumatic stress disorder prevalence. Technological solutions often overlook these nuances, perpetuating gendered outcomes. Decision-making, particularly in industries contributing to climate change, has been traditionally male-dominated, necessitating a re-evaluation of policy responses. The gendered nature of risk perception, environmental concern, and energy consumption underscores the importance of nuanced approaches. Women's roles in reproductive, caring, and community management work, often unpaid and overlooked, further emphasize the need for gender considerations. In RESIST, considering the binary gender perspective despite its limitations reflects a commitment to addressing gender disparities and ensuring inclusive adaptation measures, aligning with the project's goal of exploring climate change adaptation with a gender and intersectional lens. This approach is essential for social justice and avoiding unintended consequences, recognizing that power imbalances can hinder successful climate adaptation.

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○ **Why Gender Sensitive and Inclusive Communication Matter for Resist?**

Gender-sensitive and inclusive communication is crucial for effective climate action for several reasons. First, it recognizes that climate change affects men and women differently due to existing social, economic, and cultural disparities. By acknowledging and addressing these gender-specific impacts, communication strategies can be tailored to the diverse needs and vulnerabilities of different groups.

Second, inclusive communication ensures that the voices of all individuals, regardless of gender, are heard and considered in climate discussions. Women, who often bear the brunt of climate impacts, must be actively involved in decision-making processes. Inclusive communication promotes diverse perspectives, which leads to more comprehensive and sustainable climate policies and initiatives. Moreover, gender-sensitive communication helps challenge stereotypes and traditional gender roles that may contribute to unequal distribution of resources and opportunities. It encourages a more equitable distribution of responsibilities and benefits related to climate action, fostering a sense of shared ownership and responsibility within communities.

In addition, considering gender in climate communication helps bridge gaps in access to information and resources. Women, especially in marginalized communities, may have limited access to education and information. Tailoring communication methods to reach these groups ensures that everyone has the knowledge and tools to participate in climate action.

Last, gender-sensitive communication contributes to the overall effectiveness of climate initiatives by promoting social cohesion and community engagement. Recognizing and addressing gender disparities fosters a sense of inclusivity and shared responsibility, which is essential for building resilient communities and achieving sustainable climate outcomes, key aims of the RESIST Project.

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1 Brief Social Media Publications

Given the speediness and number of publications in social media, a checklist has been prepared to provide guidance in a simple manner about gender mainstreaming in those fast communication interactions. The checklist is based on a collection of existing good practices and toolkits on the subject³⁰. In addition to this checklist, ESF is working on an “Inclusive Communication Guideline” for the RESIST Consortium that will complement this tool.

RESIST Checklist for Brief Social Media Communications

Written Communication		
Tip	Justification/Example	
Ensure that women, men, and non-binary persons are equally represented	Aim for a gender balance across the examples, testimonies, images, or case studies used. Present women and men in non-traditional roles.	
Use an inclusive approach with pronouns	Avoid gender-specific pronoun(s) such as “he, him, his, she, her, hers” except when referring to a specific person. Use the pronoun they or them.	
Be mindful when using generic terms to describe people, jobs, and things	Generics are nouns and pronouns intended to be used for all genders. Use terms that include women and men, e.g. humanity instead of mankind.	
Promote gender equality through titles and forms of address	It is important to avoid addressing women by their marital status (as somebody’s wife or widow, unless absolutely necessary, or if this is how individual women prefer to be addressed. An alternative to “Miss” and “Mrs.” when addressing or referring to a woman is “Ms.” (which doesn’t indicate marital status) or, if the term applies, “Professor” or “Dr.”).	

³⁰See: Value for Women, “Communications & Gender Checklist: Things to Consider”, 2019; Belgian Federal Government, “La check-list de genre: quelques conseils pour intégrer le gender mainstreaming dans la communication fédérale”, available here: https://igvmiefh.belgium.be/fr/publications/de_genderchecklist#:~:text=Une%20check%2Dlist%20pour%20aider,des%20femmes%20et%20des%20hommes. ; EIGE, “Toolkit on Gender-Sensitive Communication: A resource for policymakers, legislators, media and anyone else with an interest in making their communications more inclusive”, 2019; Council of Europe, “Gender Sensitive Communication Checklist”, available here: <https://rm.coe.int/09000016809ebbff>; Oxfam inclusive language guide. Available here: <https://oxfamilibrary.openrepository.com/bitstream/handle/10546/621487/gd-inclusive-language-guide-130323-en.pdf;jsessionid=528E54623569D9DD2C6F82CA7F89BF33?sequence=4>.

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Promote representation that challenges gender stereotypes and contributes to breaking the status quo for both women and men	Avoid the use or the representation of certain roles or occupations as only appropriate for, or held by, women and men. For example, businessowners and supervisors are men, caregivers are women, etc.	
Use language that empowers and highlights women as active agents of change rather than portraying them as passive recipients of aid	While describing development-oriented efforts or activities, for instance, avoid presenting beneficiary populations as disempowered	
Think about intersectionality	Consider how gender intersects with class, race, ethnicity, ability, age and other factors. It is important to represent women and men from all areas where activities take place. Example: Represent a diversity of women and men of varying ethnicities and ages, include images of people with disabilities	
Choose language that respects the agency and resilience of individuals in marginalized conditions, including women and others, steering clear of any victimizing portrayals	<p>Gender blind, neutral or biased:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •“Martha has become a very successful businesswoman even though her parents are uneducated indigenous people from Peru.” <p>Gender positive or gender forward:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Martha, an indigenous woman from Peru, is a very successful businesswoman.” <p>Avoid using adjectives to describe people by the conditions in which they live (e.g. marginalized women). Instead, describe the conditions in which they live (e.g. “women living in marginalized conditions”).</p>	
Ensure that statements about women are respectful and avoid any patronizing language. Refrain from attributing material or educational deprivations to women, focusing instead on addressing systemic challenges and fostering empowerment	<p>Gender biased:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •“Women need to be educated about their rights to improve their self-esteem.” <p>Gender blind, neutral or biased:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •“An enterprise in Cambodia succeeded despite being led by women.”; “The business is led by an indigenous woman, but it is doing really well.” <p>Gender positive or gender forward:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •“When women receive education about their rights, they improve their self-esteem.” •“An enterprise in Cambodia succeeded despite the fact that the women leading it faced many obstacles and discrimination in accessing finance.” 	
Ensure diversity in your sources and quotes	Make all voices heard with a special eye on vulnerable populations that could be the most affected by climate change effects.	
Mitigate climate anxiety in publications by steering	Climate change fact:	

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clear of catastrophizing language, and instead, emphasize constructive solutions, positive narratives, and images regarding climate challenges	<p>“Each year we are seeing stronger and more deadly extreme weather events in every part of the Earth.”</p> <p>Resilient climate change communication:</p> <p>“Each year we observe heightened and increasingly impactful climate events occurring across the Earth. Engaging communities most affected by the climate crisis not only benefits the planet but also improves health and livelihoods.”</p>	
When addressing the intersectionality of climate change and socio-economic aspects, a good way to overcome distress is to communicate a positive message centered around solutions and to link it to justice.	<p>Let people know that they have the power to effect change by shifting behaviour.</p> <p>Consider addressing injustice and inequity by putting at the center of the story the most vulnerable people (who usually are those who contributed the least to the climate change). Even though they are the most exposed to effects of climate change and usually helpless, avoid portraying them solely as victims (or even worse, as the guilty party) but rather focus on their experiences, knowledge and skills that could be useful in the process.</p>	
Use accessible language that is simple and easy to understand for people with various socio-economic backgrounds	Consider tailoring the language and using non-scientific words so that all groups of people resonate with the message.	

Audiovisual representations	
Tip	
Represent both women and men actively participating in diverse aspects of public and private life (at home, school, the workplace, in public and family life, and in the community)	
Choose images that show women, men and non-binary persons in nontraditional and non-stereotypical roles and professions, such as women as businessowners and community leaders or men as caregivers	
Ensure equal numbers of women, men, non-binary persons in your image selection	
Portray diversity: Make sure to include and balance the representation of women and men from diverse racial/ethnic backgrounds, cultural identities, ages, and men and women with disabilities	
Avoid sexualizing or objectifying women through images	
Present women and non-binary persons in positions of authority and power	
Consider posture, expressions, gestures, positioning and clothing within a picture or image to convey balance, equal status, and authority. For example, avoid portraying men behind desks and women standing to the side, or a man explaining something to a women’s-only group	
Ensure people’s clothing/attire/appearance is appropriate for the context. For example, do not use stock images of fashion models if the text is referring to the workplace or agricultural markets, etc. Try not to reinforce traditional/dominant ideologies of beauty – focus on the roles of the people in the images rather than their appearance	

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Be mindful of people's many complementary identities at work and in the home. For example, a professor can also be a caregiver, and a caregiver can also be professor	
Be mindful about colours (avoid clichés such as pink for women and blue for men)	
Remind to always include the source of pictures/images	

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